

**The Influence of Periodontal Treatment and Exercise Training on the Oral
Microbiome and Nitrate Metabolism**

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Abstract

The signalling molecule nitric oxide (NO) has multiple physiological functions, including contributions to vascular homeostasis and oral health. Nitric oxide synthase (NOS) enzymes produce NO endogenously via the breakdown of L-arginine. Alternatively, NO can be produced exogenously, with the support of NO₂⁻-producing bacteria, located primarily on the dorsal surface of the tongue. These species are associated with oral health and reduce nitrate (NO₃⁻), predominantly derived from plant-based dietary sources to the NO precursor nitrite (NO₂⁻). Emerging evidence suggests increasing salivary NO₃⁻ and NO₂⁻ levels via dietary NO₃⁻ consumption may support oral health. The impact of other interventions, such as dental treatment and exercise training, remains unexplored.

This thesis aimed to determine the effects of the successful treatment of periodontitis and aerobic exercise training on NO metabolism and the oral microbiome. Ozone-based chemiluminescence and high-performance liquid chromatography were used to quantify NO₃⁻ and NO₂⁻ bioavailability in the saliva. Next-generation Illumina and Pac-Bio sequencing of the 16S rRNA gene were used to evaluate oral microbiome changes. In addition, a mixed-methods study investigated the knowledge, attitudes, and opinions of athletes, coaches and dental healthcare professionals (DHPs) regarding dental disease prevention in competitive sports.

In Chapter 3 a cohort of patients received treatment for periodontitis. Salivary NO₃⁻ and NO₂⁻ levels and the composition of the subgingival microbiome were examined at baseline and 1, 7 and 90 days post-treatment. While no significant changes were observed in the concentrations of salivary NO₃⁻ and NO₂⁻ following treatment (all $p > 0.05$), NO₂⁻-producing bacteria increased in relative abundance between baseline and all subsequent timepoints (all $p < 0.001$). In Chapter 4, 11 untrained males underwent 8 weeks of high-intensity interval training, followed by 12 weeks of detraining. Nine bacterial species, five of which possess NO₂⁻-producing capacity, increased in relative abundance on the participants' tongue dorsa following training (all $p < 0.05$). Salivary NO₂⁻ levels increased after training ($p = 0.02$), while NO₃⁻ levels remained unchanged ($p = 0.10$). In Chapter 5, competitive athletes were compared with untrained controls. Salivary NO₃⁻ ($p = 0.003$) and NO₂⁻ ($p = 0.03$) were higher in the athlete group. The composition of the tongue dorsum microbiome also significantly differed between athletes and controls ($p = 0.046$) and the relative abundance of NO₂⁻-producing *Rothia mucilaginosa* and unclassified sequences assigned to the genus *Gemella* were higher on the tongue dorsa of athletes. No

significant differences were detected in the supragingival plaque (all $p > 0.91$). The final study (Chapter 6) used an online questionnaire to collect quantitative and qualitative data from athletes, coaches and dental healthcare professionals (DHPs). All three groups demonstrated limited awareness of the existence and contents of resources supporting dental disease prevention in competitive sports, despite 15% of athlete respondents indicating that dental disease had impacted their performance. The coaches did not feel they had a large role in delivering advice to prevent dental disease but were prepared to provide advice to support general health, well-being, and sports performance. The DHPs discussed their role in applying key principles of preventative care, feeling that this should not change, regardless of an individual patient's exercise training status. These results show that the awareness of the educational resources aimed at preventing dental disease in elite-level sports could be improved among athletes and their support teams to support dental disease prevention in the competitive sports environment.

The collective results of this thesis suggest that aerobic exercise increases salivary NO_3^- and NO_2^- levels. In addition, periodontal treatment and exercise training were associated with a greater relative abundance of species known to contribute to NO_2^- production. Finally, dental disease prevention in competitive sports appears to be overlooked by both athletes and their support teams, potentially contributing to the increased prevalence of dental disease previously observed among athlete cohorts.

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Declaration

The work in this thesis is the sole work of the candidate. This work has not previously been submitted for award at any other institution. To the best of my knowledge and belief, the thesis contains no material previously published by another person except where due reference is made in the thesis itself.

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List of Abbreviations

16S rRNA	16 Svedberg ribosomal ribonucleic acid
ANCOM-BC	Analysis of compositions of microbiomes with bias correction
ANOVA	Analysis of variance
ASV	Amplicon sequence variant
AUC	Area under the curve
BH ₄	Tetrahydrobiopterin
BMI	Body mass index
BOP	Bleeding on probing
BP	Blood pressure
Ca ²⁺	Calcium ion
CAL	Clinical attachment loss
CCA	Canonical correlation analysis
CHO	Carbohydrate
CI	Confidence interval
CPD	Continued professional development
CPITN	Community index of periodontal treatment needs
CPX	Cardiopulmonary exercise testing
DADA	Divisive Amplicon Denoising Algorithm
DBP	Diastolic blood pressure
DHP	Dental healthcare professional
DNA	Deoxyribonucleic acid
DNRA	Dissimilatory nitrite reduction
EDTA	Ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid
eNOS	Endothelial nitric oxide synthase
FISABIO	Foundation for the Promotion of Health and Biomedical Research of the Valencian Community
FMPS	Full mouth plaque score
GDP	General dental practitioner
GET	Gas exchange threshold
HIIT	High-intensity interval training
HPLC	High performance liquid chromatography
HR	Heart rate
IL	Interleukin
iNOS	Inducible nitric oxide synthase
IOC	International Olympics Committee
IQR	Interquartile range
MAP	Mean arterial pressure
N ₂	Nitrogen
NADPH	Nicotinamide Adenine Dinucleotide Phosphate
NaOH	Sodium hydroxide

NH ₄	Ammonium
nNOS	Neuronal nitric oxide synthase
NOA	Nitric oxide analyser
NOC	N-nitroso compounds
NO ₃ ⁻	Nitrate
NO ₂ ⁻	Nitrite
NOS	Nitric oxide synthase
O ₂	Oxygen
OHI	Oral hygiene instruction
ONRC	Oral nitrate reduction capacity
ONPC	Oral nitrite production capacity
PERMANOVA	Permutational multivariate analysis of variance
PISA	Periodontally inflamed surface area
PMPR	Professional mechanical plaque removal
PPD	Periodontal pocket depth
RED-S	Relative energy deficiency in sport
RER	Respiratory exchange ratio
RNA	Ribonucleic acid
RPE	Rate of perceived exertion
SBP	Systolic blood pressure
SDCEP	Scottish Clinical Dental Effectiveness Programme
SILVA	(from Latin Silva, forest), ribosomal RNA gene database project
SMRT	Single molecule, real time
$\dot{V}E$	Pulmonary ventilation
$\dot{V}O_{2max}$	Maximum rate of oxygen consumption attainable during physical exertion
VO_{2peak}	Highest rate of oxygen consumed at peak exercise
W _{GET}	Percentage of power corresponding to gas exchange threshold
WHO	World Health Organisation
W _{peak}	Peak power output
XOR	Xanthine oxidase
ZnSO ₄	Zinc sulfate

1. Chapter 1 General Introduction

1.1 The Burden of Oral Disease

Oral health includes the ability to carry out all oral functions in the absence of discomfort and disease (Glick *et al.*, 2020). Throughout this thesis, ‘dental diseases’ will refer to conditions which arise from changes to the oral environment and their resulting impact on microbiome composition and behaviour, not conditions caused by malignancy or orofacial trauma. The oral microbiome is introduced, and pathogenesis of common dental diseases are briefly described below.

1.2 The Oral Microbiome

The microbiome refers to the complete community of all bacteria, archaea, fungi, viruses, and protozoa resident within the body (the microbiota) and the molecules they produce (Berg *et al.*, 2020). At each site, a combination of the human cell types, pH and oxygen availability dictate conditions for bacterial growth (Donaldson, Lee and Mazmanian, 2016). This means human hosts should be considered a collection of ecosystems, with microbiome composition and behaviour influenced by local environmental demands. The greatest degree of microbiome diversity is found in the gut, followed by the oral cavity (Hou *et al.*, 2022).

More than 700 bacterial species have been identified as potential members of the oral microbiome (Dewhirst *et al.*, 2010). While each individual is host to 100-200+ different species, 65% of these bacteria are conserved between individuals (Dewhirst *et al.*, 2010; Griffen *et al.*, 2012). This ‘core oral microbiome’ comprises the majority of the bacterial community (Griffen *et al.*, 2012) and remains stable over the short (Lazarevic *et al.*, 2010) and long term (Vogtmann *et al.*, 2018), while low abundance species vary widely depending on host factors including diet, genetics and age (David *et al.*, 2014). Despite this, functional pathways are highly conserved as the oral microbiota contends with similar pressures, regardless of composition at the species level (Huttenhower *et al.*, 2012).

1.1.1 Dental Caries

The pathology of dental caries is displayed in Figure 1-1. Tooth tissue is comprised of a hydroxyapatite matrix, vulnerable to dissolution below a pH of 5.5. Caries-associated bacteria include species from the genera *Streptococcus*, *Actinomyces*, *Lactobacillus* and *Atopobium* (Torlakovic *et al.*, 2012; Takahashi, 2015). These bacteria are acidogenic (they ferment carbohydrates to form organic acids) and aciduric (tolerant of acidic conditions). As a result,

they gain a survival advantage when their host regularly consumes fermentable carbohydrates or when salivary buffering is impaired (Rosier, Marsh and Mira, 2018).

A - Poor oral hygiene and frequent consumption of dietary sugars leads to decreased oral pH, leading to tooth tissue demineralisation. This demineralisation front moves progressively deeper into the structure of the tooth.

B - A low pH and high carbohydrate availability benefits acidogenic and aciduric caries-associated bacteria.

Figure 1-1: The pathology of dental caries. Created in Biorender.com

1.2.2 Periodontal Disease

Periodontal disease pathogenesis is shown in Figure 1-2. Initially, inadequate oral hygiene leads to the build-up of plaque biofilm, causing gingivitis, reversible soft tissue inflammation. In susceptible patients, failure to remove this biofilm means the disease progresses to periodontitis, characterised by a chronic inflammatory infiltrate and periodontal pocket formation (Kinane, Stathopoulou and Papapanou, 2017).

The periodontitis-associated microbiota consists of inflamophilic, proteolytic anaerobes (Rosier, Marsh and Mira, 2018). These bacteria evade detection by the immune response and may metabolise inflammatory mediators, thriving as a result of the mechanisms which aim to eradicate them (Hajishengallis and Diaz, 2020). Treatment aims to eradicate this harmful biofilm and prevent its reestablishment, via plaque removal by the dental team and patient.

A - Poor oral hygiene leads to the build-up of plaque biofilm, causing gingivitis. In susceptible patients, failing to remove dental plaque means gingivitis progresses to periodontitis.

B - An inflammatory response aims to control biofilm growth. Disease-associated species evade this response and metabolise inflammatory mediators, driving biofilm dysbiosis.

Figure 1-2: The pathology of periodontal disease. Created in Biorender.com

While some alterations to the oral microenvironment benefit pathogenic bacteria, others support health-associated species (Rosier, Marsh and Mira, 2018). Host behaviours that promote homeostasis may prevent pathogen growth so are particularly important in preventing dental disease.

1.3 The Oral Microbiome in Health

Most of the resident microbiome consists of commensal organisms, which coexist in a dynamic balance with the immune response and other members of the microbiome. Others act as symbiotes, carrying out reactions which benefit their human host (Wang *et al.*, 2017). Oral nitrite (NO_2^-)-producing bacteria are a prime example of symbiotic oral bacteria. Concentrated on the dorsal surface of the tongue, these species reduce inorganic nitrate (NO_3^-) to NO_2^- , a precursor for the multifunctional signalling molecule nitric oxide (NO) (Hezel and Weitzberg, 2015). Multiple body systems are reliant on NO to ensure normal function. Systemic roles of NO include modulation of the vascular system (Bryan *et al.*, 2008; Webb *et al.*, 2008; Kapil *et al.*, 2020), control of skeletal muscle contraction (Bailey *et al.*, 2009), contribution to normal immune system function (Bogdan, 2001), promotion of wound healing (Luo and Chen, 2005), glucose homeostasis (Gilchrist *et al.*, 2013) and attenuation of oxidative stress and inflammation (Carlström *et al.*, 2011). Furthermore, emerging evidence shows bacterial NO_2^- production contributes to oral health (Rosier *et al.*, 2022). Mammalian cells are incapable of efficient NO_3^- reduction, meaning oral NO_2^- -producing bacteria play a vital role in the maintenance of host function (Lundberg and Govoni, 2004; Lundberg and Weitzberg, 2010).

The propagation of the disease associated microbiome via some behavioural changes, such as carbohydrate consumption and smoking, have been well explored (Santonocito *et al.*, 2022; Shapiro *et al.*, 2022). The effects of healthy behaviours, such as improved plaque control and exercise training have received less attention (Bescos *et al.*, 2020; Rosier *et al.*, 2022). This thesis presents findings from a series of research studies which aimed to investigate host-microbiome interactions, focusing on how periodontal treatment and exercise training could influence the composition of the oral microbiome, in the context of NO_2^- production and dental disease risk.

2. Chapter 2 Literature Review

The composition and behaviour of the oral microbiome is exquisitely sensitive to any changes to the microenvironment. This literature review will provide detailed information on the following topics as they are of particular relevance to the original research in the following chapters:

- The role of the oral microbiome in NO generation
- The role of NO and its metabolites NO_3^- and NO_2^- in the maintenance of oral health
- The impact of host behaviours on the oral microenvironment and oral microbiome

2.1 NO - A Small Molecule with a Big Biological Impact

The first biological function of NO to be discovered was its role as a vasodilator (Furchgott *et al.*, 1984; Ignarro *et al.*, 1987). Since then, it has become clear that it has multiple physiological functions, as summarised in Figure 2-1. These effects are possible due to the unique molecular properties of NO. The outer shell of NO contains an unpaired electron, allowing rapid reaction with the oxygen (O_2), superoxide radicals and transition metals present in many enzymes. It is also lipophilic, enabling ready diffusion to initiate changes in cellular behaviour (Lancaster, 2015).

Figure 2-1: A simplified overview of the physiological functions of NO within the human body. Figure is adapted from (Lundberg and Weitzberg, 2022; Rosier *et al.*, 2022). Created in BioRender.com.

Endogenous NO production is mediated by the enzymatic breakdown of the amino acid L-arginine by NO Synthase (NOS) enzymes (Bryan and Loscalzo, 2011). A complimentary exogenous pathway of NO synthesis also exists, in which dietary NO_3^- is reduced to NO_2^- by commensal oral bacteria of the enterosalivary NO_3^- - NO_2^- -NO pathway (Lundberg, Carlström and Weitzberg, 2018).

Due to its many functions, reduced NO bioavailability results in inflammation and endothelial dysfunction (Levine, Punihale and Levine, 2012). Decreased NO bioavailability is an inevitable consequence of ageing, as a result of NOS uncoupling and oxidative stress (Landmesser *et al.*, 2003). Conversely, some behaviours increase NO bioavailability, enabling the maintenance of health. These include the completion of regular structured exercise (Mendes-Ribeiro *et al.*, 2009), which increases the expression of NOS enzymes and the endogenous production of NO (Nosarev *et al.*, 2014), and the consumption of a diet rich in plant-based sources of NO_3^- , which provides a substrate for the oral NO_2^- producing microbiome (Jackson *et al.*, 2018). An overview of the pathways of human NO production are shown in Figure 2-2.

Figure 2-2: Diagram of NO generation within the human body. The endogenous pathway of NO synthesis by NOS enzymes is shown on the right and the exogenous pathway of NO generation from the diet on the left. Created in BioRender.com.

2.2 Endogenous NO Production

Endogenous NO synthesis takes place in almost all mammalian tissues (Förstermann and Sessa, 2012). NOS enzymes produce NO and L-citrulline from the reaction of L-arginine with molecular O₂ and nicotinamide adenine dinucleotide phosphate (NADPH). These homodimeric enzymes consist of a heme-containing N-terminus oxygenase domain linked to a C-terminus reductase domain by calmodulin binding sequences and bind most efficiently to L-arginine and Tetrahydrobiopterin (BH₄) in an O₂-rich environment (Moncada, Palmer and Higgs, 1991). Three NOS isoforms exist: endothelial NOS (eNOS), neuronal NOS (nNOS), and cytokine-inducible NOS (iNOS) (Förstermann and Sessa, 2012).

The free electron in the outer shell of NO makes it relatively unstable. This means NO is rapidly oxidised to NO₂⁻ and then further to NO₃⁻ by the action of ferrous oxyheme-containing enzymes (Cosby *et al.*, 2003). NO₂⁻ reductase enzymes, including Hb, Mb, neuroglobin and xanthine oxidoreductase (XOR) can then reverse this reaction to increase NO bioavailability (Shiva, 2013).

NO generation is necessary for health and NOS dysfunctions are characteristic of pathology (Lauer *et al.*, 2008; Kina-Tanada *et al.*, 2017), so there is an interest in the therapeutic manipulation of NO cycling (Omar *et al.*, 2016). While supplementation with L-arginine does not demonstrate significant benefits (Abukhodair, Abukhudair and Alqarni, 2021), increasing NO bioavailability through increased inorganic NO₃⁻ consumption does show promise (Lundberg *et al.*, 2011).

2.3 Exogenous NO Production

Inorganic NO₃⁻ can be obtained from various sources, most notably leafy-green vegetables and beetroot, as well as grains and cured meats (Hord, Tang and Bryan, 2009). There are concerns regarding the association between cured meat consumption and increased colorectal cancer risk, as the nitrate salts added to these foodstuffs as preservatives can support the formation of carcinogenic N-nitroso compounds (NOCs) when exposed to acid (Berends *et al.*, 2019). However, plant-based NO₃⁻ sources instead appear to have protective effects against gastric cancer development (Xie *et al.*, 2016). This is due to their antioxidant and vitamin C content, which prevent NOC formation (González *et al.*, 1994; Dellavalle *et al.*, 2014; Lundberg, Carlström and Weitzberg, 2018; Schrenk *et al.*, 2023).

An overview of the exogenous pathway of NO production is provided in Figure 2-3. Dietary NO_3^- is absorbed from the gut and enters the bloodstream. Around 75% of this NO_3^- is excreted in urine (Carlsson *et al.*, 2003). The remainder is actively concentrated into the saliva via sialin, an electrogenic $2\text{NO}_3^-/\text{H}^+$ transporter, found in acinar cells of the salivary glands (Qin *et al.*, 2012). Fasted salivary NO_3^- levels are around 10-fold higher than those seen in the plasma, ranging from 100–500 μM . Following a NO_3^- -rich meal, this increases to 5–8 mM, remaining elevated for several hours depending on NO_3^- dose and water intake (Lundberg and Govoni, 2004; Burleigh *et al.*, 2019; Rosier *et al.*, 2021).

Mammalian cells are incapable of efficient NO_3^- reduction, albeit with small increases in plasma NO_2^- observed in germ-free mice following intraperitoneal NO_3^- administration (Huang, Borniquel and Lundberg, 2010). This increase is halted following the administration of XOR inhibitor allopurinol, implicating XOR as a mammalian NO_3^- reductase enzyme, in addition to its role in NO_2^- oxidation to NO (Peleli *et al.*, 2016). Instead, commensal oral bacteria are required to ensure efficient NO_2^- generation (Lundberg and Govoni, 2004; Lundberg and Weitzberg, 2010). These bacterial species possess the NO_3^- -reductase genes necessary to perform the two-electron reduction of NO_3^- to NO_2^- during anaerobic respiration (Moreno-Vivián *et al.*, 1999), using NO_3^- as their final electron acceptor (Martínez-Espinosa *et al.*, 2007).

Once this NO_2^- is swallowed, some is rapidly protonated by the low gastric pH, forming nitrous acid (HNO_2), which can be converted to a dinitrogen trioxide (N_2O_3) before further degradation into nitrogen dioxide (NO_2), the nitrosonium ion (NO^+), or NO (Lundberg *et al.*, 1994; Tiso and Schechter, 2015). The remaining NO_2^- is resorbed from the small intestine into the systemic circulation, increasing plasma NO_2^- after a NO_3^- -rich meal (Lundberg, Carlström and Weitzberg, 2018). This increase is attenuated if swallowing is paused (Lundberg and Govoni, 2004) or, in some studies, following the administration of antimicrobial mouthwash (Kapil *et al.*, 2013; Bondonno *et al.*, 2015; Bescos *et al.*, 2020). The decrease in serum NO_2^- post-mouthwash suggests the oral microbiome may be responsible for up to 25% of circulatory NO_2^- (Kapil *et al.*, 2013).

Upon reaching the circulation and tissues, NO_2^- may be converted to NO by a variety of different processes, including via deoxyhemoglobin, deoxymyoglobin, mitochondrial

cytochrome oxidase enzymes and XOR (Lundberg, Carlström and Weitzberg, 2018). Plasma NO_2^- conversion to NO does not require the presence of O_2 (Cosby *et al.*, 2003) and is instead facilitated when the physiological pH is decreased (A *et al.*, 2001).

Figure 2-3: A simplified overview of the enterosalivary NO_3^- - NO_2^- -NO pathway. Created in BioRender.com.

2.4 NO_3^- and NO_2^- Storage Within the Human Body

Systemic NO_3^- and NO_2^- are stored if not used immediately. Instead, NO_2^- is stored throughout the body, including in the blood, heart, and liver (Cosby *et al.*, 2003; Bryan *et al.*, 2007; Li *et al.*, 2008; Webb *et al.*, 2008; Carlström *et al.*, 2011). Skeletal muscle is also an important site for NO generation (Stamler and Meissner, 2001), reduction of NO_2^- (Ormerod *et al.*, 2011; Totzeck *et al.*, 2014) and for NO_3^- and NO_2^- storage (Wylie *et al.*, 2019).

Most data regarding the NO cycle in skeletal muscle has been collected from rodent models. These show significantly higher levels of NO_3^- in skeletal muscle tissue compared with other organs and blood (Piknova *et al.*, 2015), with decreased stored NO_3^- in nNOS (Piknova *et al.*, 2015) and myoglobin knockout mice (Park *et al.*, 2019). In a rat model, the consumption of a low NO_3^- diet decreased skeletal muscle NO_3^- stores (Gilliard *et al.*, 2018). When followed by

a period of high NO_3^- consumption, NO_3^- levels in the muscle rapidly increased to exceed basal levels, indicating compensatory mechanisms protect NO homeostasis (Gilliard *et al.*, 2018). Transportation of dietary NO_3^- from the systemic circulation into the muscle may occur via multiple transporter proteins, including sialin (Srihirun *et al.*, 2020) and chloride channel protein 1 (Poroca, Pelis and Chappe, 2017). To support activity, some of this NO_3^- appears to be oxidised to NO_2^- and NO during an acute bout of aerobic exercise (Piknova *et al.*, 2016).

Initial studies carried out in humans suggest the existence of similar mechanisms. For example, muscle NO_3^- levels are higher than those in the plasma (Nyakayiru *et al.*, 2017; Wylie *et al.*, 2019) and the sialin, NO_3^- transporters and XOR necessary for the active uptake, storage and reduction of NO_3^- are all present within human skeletal muscle (Wylie *et al.*, 2019). Similar increases in NO_3^- following dietary changes and decreases following acute exercise bouts are observed in human muscle as have been observed in rodent models (Wylie *et al.*, 2019).

There are still many gaps in our understanding of NO cycling within skeletal muscle. The impact of longer-term behavioural changes, for example, a switch from inactivity to regular exercise on NO_3^- and NO_2^- levels, has yet to be investigated. It is feasible that adaptations to endogenous NO production following regular exercise training might also alter reserves of NO_3^- and NO_2^- in skeletal muscle tissue, to provide greater NO availability during physical activity.

2.5 The Therapeutic and Ergogenic Potential of Enterosalivary NO_2^- Production

Increasing systemic NO_2^- levels increases NO bioavailability, with potential therapeutic benefits for physiological systems reliant on NO to function (Lundberg, Carlström and Weitzberg, 2018). In addition, NO_3^- is recommended by the International Olympic Committee (IOC) as an ergogenic aid to support exercise performance (Maughan *et al.*, 2018).

Systematic reviews and meta-analyses support the ergogenic effects of NO_3^- on performance-related testing outcomes (McMahon, Leveritt and Pavey, 2017) through its effects on multiple physiological pathways (Jones *et al.*, 2021). These include a reduced adenosine triphosphate (ATP) cost of muscle force production (Bailey *et al.*, 2010) and increased efficiency of the mitochondria and of oxidative phosphorylation (Larsen *et al.*, 2011).

These ergogenic effects appear limited in highly trained individuals ($\dot{V}O_{2\max} >65\text{mL/kg/min}$) (Senefeld *et al.*, 2020). This is believed to be due to the increased endogenous NO production efficiency (McConnell *et al.*, 2007b), high dietary NO_3^- intake and a reliance on aerobic type-I muscle fibres in these groups (Jones *et al.*, 2016). Preliminary data also suggests exercise training augments oral NO_2^- -production, which is associated with improved aerobic exercise capacity (Thomas *et al.*, 2019).

2.6 The Oral NO_2^- -Producing Microbiome

The species of oral bacteria which have been reported to produce NO_2^- vary. This is likely due to methodological differences between studies. These include the collection of samples from different environmental niches and varied DNA isolation techniques and primer designs (Velmurugan *et al.*, 2016; Vanhatalo *et al.*, 2018; Burleigh *et al.*, 2019; Jockel-Schneider *et al.*, 2021; Rosier *et al.*, 2021). Despite this, representative species from the genera *Rothia*, *Neisseria*, *Actinomyces*, *Veillonella*, *Haemophilus*, and *Corynebacterium* are regarded as common oral NO_2^- -producing bacteria (Doel *et al.*, 2005; Rosier, Moya-Gonzalvez, *et al.*, 2020; Sato-Suzuki *et al.*, 2020; Wicaksono *et al.*, 2020).

Bacterial species which possess NO_3^- -reducing capacity can be isolated *in-vitro* when NO_2^- production is detected following their culture with NO_3^- . While much of this NO_2^- likely results from bacterial reduction of NO_3^- , other metabolic pathways may also produce NO_2^- , including bacterial oxidation of ammonium (NH_4^+) and NO (Rosier, Moya-Gonzalvez, *et al.*, 2020). As a result, if a species has not been confirmed to reduce NO_3^- , the term ‘ NO_2^- -producing species’ is more accurate and will be used throughout this thesis. Bacteria confirmed to possess NO_3^- -reducing capacity, NO_2^- -producing capacity or which are associated with a high NO_3^- -reduction capacity are shown in Table 2-1.

In an early study, Doel *et al.*, (2005) identified the deep, anaerobic clefts of the tongue dorsum as the oral site with the greatest NO_2^- -production capacity, through the use of NO_3^- -soaked filter paper discs. The findings of this study have influenced subsequent research, with multiple studies sampling the microbiome of the tongue dorsum, using this site as a proxy, to determine the impact of supplementation with NO_3^- on the oral environment and behaviour of the NO_2^- -producing microbiome (Burleigh *et al.*, 2019, Liddle *et al.*, 2019, Rosier, Moya-Gonzalvez, *et al.*, 2020) However, the technique used by Doel *et al.*, (2005) may favour the relatively flat and

accessible surface of the tongue dorsum, meaning equally effective NO_2^- -production may take place at other oral sites, so these results, and the impact of an increase in oral NO_3^- and NO_3^- levels in other niches should be interpreted with caution.

This study also used a potassium NO_3^- mouth rinse to demonstrate NO_2^- production efficiency differs between individuals, suggesting biofilm composition impacts on NO_2^- production capacity. *In vitro* examination of selected laboratory strains showed *Actinomyces odontolyticus*, followed by *Rothia mucilaginosa*, *Rothia dentocariosa*, *Veillonella dispar*, and *Veillonella atypica* demonstrated the most effective NO_2^- production. Hyde *et al.*, (2014) analysed metabolic pathway coverage of oral bacteria, showing genes encoding for nitrogen-metabolism were only slightly lower in samples with lower NO_3^- reduction capacity, indicating community complexities within the oral NO_2^- -producing microbiome. Burleigh *et al.*, (2018) examined how microbiome variations affected NO_2^- production following an increase in dietary NO_3^- , while Liddle *et al.*, (2019) assessed variability in physiological NO_3^- and NO_2^- levels and in the relative abundance of oral bacteria known to possess NO_2^- production capacity. Both studies showed individuals with a greater abundance of NO_2^- -producing bacteria generated salivary NO_2^- more efficiently, suggesting microbiome modification could enhance the effects of increased NO_3^- availability.

Rosier, Moya-Gonzalvez, *et al.*, (2020) collected dental plaque and tongue coating samples from 5 dentally and medically healthy donors and isolated NO_3^- -reducing bacteria. Ten *Rothia* species were selected as potential probiotics, bacteria which encourage beneficial behaviours of the oral microbiome (in this case effective NO_3^- reduction) (Hill *et al.*, 2014). Introduction of these isolates into *in vitro* communities increased their NO_3^- reduction capacity, suggesting that the oral microbiome composition can be manipulated to increase the NO_3^- reduction capacity, with potential benefits for NO bioavailability and for oral and systemic health.

While specific species demonstrate more efficient NO_2^- production (Doel *et al.*, 2005; Hyde *et al.*, 2014; Rosier, Moya-Gonzalvez, *et al.*, 2020), many studies fail to assess the NO_2^- -producing microbiome at the species level, instead relying on short-read 16s rRNA sequencing. This may obscure intra-community dynamics and is problematic when many species belonging to a given genus may not be capable of effective NO_2^- production.

Table 2-1: Oral bacteria with Confirmed NO₃⁻-Reduction and NO₂⁻-Production Capacity.

Genus	Species			References
	Confirmed NO ₃ ⁻ - Reducing Species	Confirmed NO ₂ ⁻ - Producing Species	Increased Abundance Associated with Higher NO ₃ ⁻ Reduction Capacity of Oral Community	
<i>Rothia</i>	<i>R. mucilaginosa</i> , <i>R. dentocariosa</i> , <i>R. aeria</i>	<i>R. mucilaginosa</i> , <i>R. dentocariosa</i> , <i>R. aeria</i>		A - (Rosier, Buetas, <i>et al.</i> , 2020) B - (Doel <i>et al.</i> , 2005; Sato-Suzuki <i>et al.</i> , 2020)
<i>Neisseria</i>	<i>N. mucosa</i>	<i>N. flavescens</i> , <i>N. macacae</i> , <i>N. oralis</i> , <i>N. subflava</i> , <i>N. elongate</i> , <i>N. sicca</i>	<i>N. mucosa</i> , <i>N. flavescens</i> , <i>N. subflava</i> , <i>N. sicca</i>	A - (Grant and Payne, 1981) B - (Sato-Suzuki <i>et al.</i> , 2020) C - (Hyde <i>et al.</i> , 2014)

<i>Actinomyces</i>	<i>A. viscosus</i> , <i>A. oris</i> ,	<i>A. viscosus</i> , <i>A. naeslundii</i> , <i>A. johnsonii</i> , <i>A.</i> <i>graevenitzii</i> , <i>A.</i> <i>hongkongensis</i> , <i>A.</i> <i>georgiae</i> <i>A. massiliensis</i> , <i>A. lingnae</i>	<i>A. viscosus</i> , <i>A. oris</i>	A - (Hyde <i>et al.</i> , 2014; Rosier, Buetas, <i>et al.</i> , 2020) B - (Doel <i>et al.</i> , 2005; Sato-Suzuki <i>et al.</i> , 2020) C - (Hyde <i>et al.</i> , 2014)
<i>Schaalia</i>	<i>S. odontolytica</i>	<i>S. odontolytica</i>	<i>S. odontolytica</i>	A - (Rosier, Buetas, <i>et al.</i> , 2020) B - (Doel <i>et al.</i> , 2005; Sato-Suzuki <i>et al.</i> , 2020) C - (Hyde <i>et al.</i> , 2014)
<i>Vellonella</i>	<i>V. dispar</i>	<i>V. dispar</i> , <i>V. parvula</i> , <i>V.</i> <i>atypica</i> , <i>V. tobetsuensis</i>	<i>V. dispar</i> , <i>V. parvula</i> , <i>V.</i> <i>atypica</i>	A - (Hyde <i>et al.</i> , 2014)B - (Doel <i>et al.</i> , 2005; Sato- Suzuki <i>et al.</i> , 2020) C - (Hyde <i>et al.</i> , 2014)
<i>Kingella</i>	<i>K. denitrificans</i>			A - (Grant and Payne, 1981)
<i>Pseudo- propionibacterium and Propionibacterium</i>	<i>Propionibacterium acnes</i>	<i>P. acnes</i> , <i>Pseudopropionibacterim</i> <i>propionicum</i>		A - (Allison and Macfarlane, 1989) B - (Doel <i>et al.</i> , 2005; Sato-Suzuki <i>et al.</i> , 2020)

<i>Streptococcus</i>	<i>S. salivarius, S. sanguinis, S. australis, S.oralis, S. parasanguinis, S. mitis, S. infantis, S. mutans</i>		B - (Sato-Suzuki <i>et al.</i> , 2020)
<i>Capnocytophaga</i>	<i>C. ochracea, C. gingivalis, C. sputigena</i>		B - (Doel <i>et al.</i> , 2005; Sato-Suzuki <i>et al.</i> , 2020)
<i>Selenomonas</i>	<i>S. noxia, S. flueggei, S. artemidis</i>		B - (Doel <i>et al.</i> , 2005; Sato-Suzuki <i>et al.</i> , 2020)
<i>Corynebacterium</i>	<i>C. matruchotii, C. durum</i>		B - (Doel <i>et al.</i> , 2005)
<i>Haemophilus</i>	<i>H. parainfluenzae, H. segnis</i>	<i>H. parainfluenzae</i>	B - (Doel <i>et al.</i> , 2005; Sato-Suzuki <i>et al.</i> , 2020) C - (Hyde <i>et al.</i> , 2014)
<i>Prevotella</i>	<i>P. melanginogenica, P. salivae</i>	<i>P. melanginogenica, P. salivae</i>	B - (Sato-Suzuki <i>et al.</i> , 2020) C - (Hyde <i>et al.</i> , 2014)

Other	<i>Paraburkholderia</i>	<i>Granulicatella adiacens</i>	B - (Doel <i>et al.</i> , 2005;
	<i>fungorum</i>		Sato-Suzuki <i>et al.</i> , 2020),
	<i>Fusobacterium nucleatum</i>		C - (Hyde <i>et al.</i> , 2014)
	<i>Eikenellacorrodens</i>		
	<i>Granulicatella adiacens</i>		

A - Confirmed NO₃⁻-Reducing Species, B - Confirmed NO₂⁻-Producing Species, C - Increased Abundance Associated with Higher NO₃⁻ Reduction Capacity of Oral Community. Table adapted from (Rosier *et al.*, 2022)

2.6.1 Steps of N₂ Metabolism by Oral Bacteria

For the host to benefit from the enterosalivary pathway, NO₂⁻ must be produced from NO₃⁻. NO₃⁻-reductase Nar genes capable of carrying out this reaction have been identified in oral bacteria (Schreiber et al., 2010; Rosier, Moya-Gonzalvez et al., 2020; Carda-Diéguez et al., 2021). Subsequently, any NO₂⁻ that remains unswallowed may be converted to other products.

Schreiber *et al.*, (2010) used quantitative polymerase chain reaction to demonstrate dental plaque bacteria possess genes capable of performing all steps in denitrification (F. Schreiber *et al.*, 2010). Genomic analysis of *Rothia* species also revealed genes for denitrification, alongside genes for NO₂⁻ assimilation (the conversion of NO₂⁻ to NH₄⁺) and for the oxidation of NO, which can be harmful to bacteria at high concentrations, to NO₃⁻, to maintain homeostasis (Rosier, Moya-Gonzalvez, *et al.*, 2020). *In-vitro*, NH₄⁺ concentration increases when saliva is incubated with NO₃, further confirming the performance of NO₂⁻ assimilation (Rosier, Buetas, *et al.*, 2020). Finally, metatranscriptomic analysis of the tongue dorsum biofilm showed evidence of denitrification, NO₃⁻ assimilation and gene transcripts for the nitrification of N₂ to NH₄⁺ (Carda-Diéguez *et al.*, 2021). Steps of oral N₂ metabolism are shown in Figure 2-4.

Figure 2-4: Steps of N₂ metabolism carried out by the oral microbiota. Oral bacteria can carry out all steps in denitrification, from NO₃⁻ to N₂. Some species can also carry out dissimilatory NO₂⁻ reduction to NH₄⁺ (DNRA) in the presence of NO₃⁻. Genes for the nitrification of N₂ to NH₄⁺ and for NO₃⁻ assimilation to NH₄⁺ have also been found. Adapted from (Rosier *et al.*, 2022) Created in BioRender.com.

2.6.2 Salivary NO₃⁻ Concentration and Oral Health

NO₂⁻ producing bacteria are found in greater abundance in the absence of dental disease (Agnello *et al.*, 2017; Meuric *et al.*, 2017; Feres *et al.*, 2021). Increases in oral NO₃⁻ availability are accompanied by increases in the relative abundance of these NO₂⁻ producing bacteria (Velmurugan *et al.*, 2016; Vanhatalo *et al.*, 2018; Burleigh *et al.*, 2019; Rosier, Buetas, *et al.*, 2020; Jockel-Schneider *et al.*, 2021; Rosier *et al.*, 2021), alongside decreases in disease associated species (Burleigh *et al.*, 2019; Rosier, Buetas, *et al.*, 2020). Additionally, increases in NO₃⁻ availability appear to alter the behaviour of the oral microbiome, preventing the environmental changes associated with dental disease development (Li *et al.*, 2007; Martínez-Espinosa *et al.*, 2007; Jockel-Schneider *et al.*, 2016; Yamamoto *et al.*, 2017; Burleigh *et al.*, 2019, 2020; Rosier, Buetas, *et al.*, 2020; Rosier, Moya-Gonzalvez, *et al.*, 2020; Jockel-Schneider *et al.*, 2021; Rosier *et al.*, 2021). These changes are summarised in Figure 2-5 and described in greater detail below.

Figure 2-5: An increase in oral NO₃⁻ availability may benefit oral health by modifying the composition and behaviour of the oral biofilm. Denitrifying bacteria carry out all steps in the reduction of NO₃⁻ to NO₂⁻ and NO. The acidic decomposition of NO₂⁻ to NO can also take place when the oral pH ≤ 5. NO has demonstrated antipathogen effects, so may modify the composition of the microbiome. NO₂⁻ can be reduced to NH₄⁺ by the bacterial DNRA and assimilatory pathways, increasing the pH by consuming H⁺ from the oral environment. Lactic acid may be used as an electron donor and carbon source by some NO₂⁻-producing species, further preventing falls in pH. Hydrogen sulfide (H₂S) acts as an electron donor during denitrification and the reduction of sulfate reduction requires more energy than denitrification, reducing the quantity of H₂S in the presence of NO₃⁻. These environmental changes are detrimental to disease-associated bacteria but increase the abundance of health associated NO₂⁻-producing species. Adapted from (Rosier et al., 2022) Created in BioRender.com.

In-vivo and *in-vitro* studies show a clear advantage for health-associated NO₂⁻-producing species when salivary NO₃⁻ availability is increased. At the genus level, *Rothia* and *Neisseria* are consistently seen to increase (Vanhatalo *et al.*, 2018; Burleigh *et al.*, 2019; Rosier, Buetas, *et al.*, 2020; Jockel-Schneider *et al.*, 2021; Rosier *et al.*, 2021), while *Prevotella* and *Veillonella* decrease in relative abundance (Vanhatalo *et al.*, 2018; Burleigh *et al.*, 2019; Rosier, Buetas, *et al.*, 2020). *In-vivo*, these changes are relatively consistent regardless of age, health status and duration of supplementation. A summary of these changes is shown in Table 2-2.

Beetroot juice significantly increasing the relative abundance of *Neisseria flavescens* compared to placebo in patients with hypercholesterolemia (Velmurugan *et al.*, 2016). The remainder of studies have been carried out on medically fit cohorts. Vanhatalo *et al.*, (2018) investigated if the impact of NO₃⁻ supplementation on the oral microbiome differed with age. *Neisseria meningitidis* and *R. mucilaginosa* increased in relative abundance, while *Veillonella parvulum* and *P. melanginogenica* decreased (Vanhatalo *et al.*, 2018). Burleigh *et al.*, (2019) investigated the impact of NO₃⁻ supplementation on the tongue dorsum microbiome, previously indicated to possess the greatest NO₃⁻-reduction capacity (Doel *et al.*, 2005). At the species level, *Neisseria subflava* increased, while *P. melanginogenica* decreased in relative abundance. When ((Rosier *et al.*, 2021) supplemented 6 individuals with NO₃⁻, *R. dentocariosa* increased in abundance in the saliva after 4 hours. These studies indicate a NO₃⁻-rich diet will not benefit every NO₂⁻-producing bacterium, but that these changes encourage the growth of effective NO₂⁻-producers

Table 2-2: Oral microbiome changes following increases in salivary NO₃⁻ availability.

Participant Characteristics	Intervention	Microbiome Analysis	Result	Reference
Saliva from 12 healthy donors	Saliva used to grow <i>in-vitro</i> biofilms with and without 6.5 mM NO ₃ ⁻ , in a glucose-rich medium.	Microbiome: Illumina Sequencing (covering V3–V4 of the 16s rRNA gene)	Increased relative abundance of <i>Rothia</i> and <i>Neisseria</i> and decreased relative abundance of <i>Streptococcus</i> , <i>Veillonella</i> , <i>Oribacterium</i> , <i>Porphyromonas</i> , <i>Fusobacterium</i> , <i>Leptotrichia</i> , <i>Prevotella</i> , and <i>Alloprevotella</i> in the NO ₃ ⁻ -rich medium.	(Rosier, Buetas, <i>et al.</i> , 2020)
Individuals with untreated hypercholesteremia.	Beetroot juice (n = 33) or placebo (n = 32) consumed daily for 6 weeks	Illumina Sequencing (covering V1–V3 of the 16s rRNA gene)	Relative abundance of <i>N. flavescens</i> increased in the saliva following beetroot juice consumption.	(Velmurugan <i>et al.</i> , 2016)
Young (18–22 yrs) and elderly (70–79 yrs) normotensive males.	Eighteen individuals consumed beetroot juice or placebo for 10-days in a cross-over trial.	Illumina Sequencing (covering V1–V3 of the 16s rRNA gene)	Relative abundance of <i>Rothia</i> and <i>Neisseria</i> increased while <i>Prevotella</i> and <i>Veillonella</i> decreased in the saliva.	(Vanhatalo <i>et al.</i> , 2018)

Young, healthy males.	Eleven individuals consumed beetroot juice or placebo for 7-days in a randomised crossover trial.	Illumina Sequencing (covering V3–V4 of the 16s rRNA gene)	Relative abundance of <i>Neisseria</i> increased, while <i>Prevotella</i> , <i>Streptococcus</i> , and <i>Actinomyces</i> decreased in the microbiome of the tongue dorsum	(Burleigh <i>et al.</i> , 2019)
Twenty-six 70–80-year-old men and women without any known medical or dental condition.	Eighteen individuals consumed beetroot juice or placebo for 10-days in a cross-over trial.	Illumina Sequencing (covering V1–V3 of the 16s rRNA gene)	Increased relative abundance of Proteobacteria and decreased relative abundance of Bacteroidetes, Firmicutes, and Fusobacteria in saliva.	(Vanhatalo <i>et al.</i> , 2021)
Six systemically healthy individuals who reported they did not have active caries during their last dental visit	A single dose of beetroot supplement mixed with water	Illumina Sequencing (covering V3–V4 of the 16s rRNA gene)	Increased relative abundance of <i>Rothia</i> and <i>R. dentocariosa</i> in saliva.	(Rosier <i>et al.</i> , 2021)
Patients with a diagnosis of periodontitis.	Consumed NO ₃ ⁻ -rich lettuce juice (23) and or NO ₃ ⁻ -depleted placebo (21) daily for 4 weeks, alongside dental intervention.	Illumina Sequencing (covering V3–V4 of the 16s rRNA gene)	Increased relative abundance of <i>Rothia</i> and <i>Neisseria</i> in subgingival plaque	(Jockel-Schneider <i>et al.</i> , 2021)

Only one clinical trial to date has examined the effects of dietary NO_3^- in patients with confirmed dental pathology. Jockel-Schneider *et al.*, (2016, 2021) used 14 days of $\sim 200\text{mg/day}$ NO_3^- , in the form of lettuce juice, as an adjunctive treatment for gingival inflammation in patients with diagnosed periodontitis. Provided alongside professional supra- and subgingival debridement, NO_3^- decreased gingival inflammation post-treatment compared to a placebo (Jockel-Schneider *et al.*, 2016). These differences in inflammation were despite comparable decreases in gingival plaque, the etiological agent of gingival inflammation (Loe, Theilade and Jensen, 1965). Genus-level 16s rRNA Illumina sequencing of the subgingival plaque showed increases in *Neisseria* and *Rothia* with supplementation, mirroring changes seen in dentally healthy cohorts (Jockel-Schneider *et al.*, 2021). These results suggest that as well as inducing similar changes in plaque composition, NO_3^- could inhibit gingival inflammation and support the growth of a health-associated microbiome, preventing the progression of periodontal disease.

2.7 NO_3^- and Dental Disease Prevention

The oral environmental changes which accompany an increase in oral NO_3^- levels and the resulting impact on oral microbiome composition and behaviour may prevent dental disease via several mechanisms, summarised in Figure 2-5 and in the sections below.

2.7.1 NO_3^- and Dental Caries

Increasing NO_3^- availability reduces the abundance of caries-associated *Streptococcus*, *Oribacterium*, *Atopobium*, *Veillonella*, and *Actinomyces* (Vanhatalo *et al.*, 2018; Burleigh *et al.*, 2019; Rosier, Buetas, *et al.*, 2020). These bacteria ferment and store dietary carbohydrate, supporting their growth while lowering the environmental pH (Marsh, 2006; Takahashi and Nyvad, 2011; Rosier, Marsh and Mira, 2018). Thus, mechanisms which attenuate pH decreases may protect against dental caries development. Evidence of the role of NO_3^- in dental caries prevention are summarised in Table 2-3.

An early study demonstrated elevated salivary NO_3^- and oral NO_3^- -reduction capacity were associated with decreased caries experience (Doel *et al.*, 2004). *In-vitro*, the addition of NO_3^- (Li *et al.*, 2007) or NO_2^- (Yamamoto *et al.*, 2017) attenuates pH decreases when saliva and plaque samples are exposed to glucose, indicating increased resilience to acidification. Bacteria can utilise lactic acid as a carbon source and electron donor during nitrification, so it was

speculated increasing NO_3^- availability increased lactic acid consumption (Li *et al.*, 2007; Schreiber *et al.*, 2010). This was confirmed following increased production of NO_2^- and NH_4^+ when NO_3^- was added to saliva grown with glucose, alongside attenuated pH decreases compared to a control (Rosier, Buetas, *et al.*, 2020). Denitrification and the conversion of NO_2^- to NH_4^+ will also contribute to this elevated pH, following proton consumption (Rosier, Buetas, *et al.*, 2020).

Increases in salivary NO_3^- have also demonstrated protective effects against oral acidification *in-vivo*. Sports drinks are used to increase carbohydrate availability during exercise (Jeukendrup, 2008) but contain high levels of sugar and citric acid (Hans *et al.*, 2016). Burleigh *et al.*, (2020) administered a single dose of NO_3^- -rich beetroot juice or placebo and either water or a sports-drink to 11 trained males in a crossover trial. Following NO_3^- consumption, pH decreases as a result of sports-supplement consumption and exercise bouts designed to induce dehydration and disrupt salivary flow were significantly attenuated. Rosier *et al.*, (2021) also demonstrated protective effects of NO_3^- consumption on oral acidification in non-exercising participants. NO_3^- was already known to stimulate lactic acid consumption by *Rothia* (Rosier, Buetas, *et al.*, 2020) and *Veillonella* (Wicaksono *et al.*, 2020) species *in-vitro*. Negative associations have also been found between *Rothia* and *Neisseria* and lactate accumulation, suggesting consumption of lactic acid during NO_2^- production (Rosier *et al.*, 2021).

Table 2-3: Impact of increasing salivary NO₃⁻ on dental caries risk.

Participant Characteristics	Intervention	Result	Reference
<i>In-vitro</i>			
Saliva collected from 13 volunteers. Health status unknown.	Saliva samples incubated anaerobically with glucose, in the presence or absence of 1.5 mmol NO ₃ ⁻ .	Decreased drop in salivary pH in the NO ₃ ⁻ condition.	(Li <i>et al.</i> , 2007)
Dental plaque collected from 76 children with caries experience.	Dental plaque incubated with glucose, in the presence or absence of 0.63 mmol NO ₃ ⁻ for 10 minutes.	Decreased drop in plaque pH in the NO ₃ ⁻ condition.	(Yamamoto <i>et al.</i> , 2017)
Saliva from 12 healthy donors	Saliva collected and used to grow <i>in-vitro</i> biofilms in a glucose-rich medium, with and without 6.5 mM NO ₃ ⁻ .	Decreased drop in pH in the NO ₃ ⁻ condition.	(Rosier, Buetas, <i>et al.</i> , 2020)
Saliva from 9 healthy donors	Donor saliva incubated in a glucose-rich medium for 7 hours, with the addition of 6.5 mM NO ₃ ⁻	Decreased drop in pH in the NO ₃ ⁻ only condition.	(Rosier, Moya-Gonzalvez, <i>et al.</i> , 2020)

and *Rothia* isolated confirmed to be effective NO₃⁻-reducers. Decreased lactate production with the addition of some probiotic *Rothia* isolates.

In-vivo

209 children attending the Dental Institute, Barts, London.	No intervention. NO ₃ ⁻ and NO ₂ ⁻ were measured in the saliva.	In children with lower caries experience, salivary NO ₃ ⁻ and estimated NO ₃ ⁻ reduction capacity were higher.	(Doel <i>et al.</i> , 2004)
Young, healthy males.	Eleven individuals consumed beetroot juice (~12.4 mmol NO ₃ ⁻) or placebo for 7-days in crossover trial.	Salivary pH increased following NO ₃ ⁻ supplementation.	(Burleigh <i>et al.</i> , 2019)
Aerobically trained males.	Participants consumed a single dose of beetroot juice (~12.4 mmol NO ₃ ⁻) or placebo, 1 hour before consuming sport drink and the completion of an exercise bout.	Decreased drop in salivary pH 5 to 15 minutes post sports drink consumption after NO ₃ ⁻ consumption compared to placebo.	(Burleigh <i>et al.</i> , 2020)
Twelve systemically healthy individuals with no signs of enamel breakdown or cavitation.	12 individuals consumed a single dose of NO ₃ ⁻ -rich beetroot supplement (4.03 mmol NO ₃ ⁻)	Decreased drop in salivary pH following NO ₃ ⁻ consumption.	(Rosier <i>et al.</i> , 2021)

and placebo in a crossover trial,
2 hours before sugar rinse

Six systemically healthy individuals who reported they did not have active caries during their last dental visit	A single dose of beetroot supplement (3.5mmol NO ₃ ⁻) mixed with water 4 hours before glucose rinse.	Decreased lactate production after NO ₃ ⁻ consumption compared to placebo.	(Rosier <i>et al.</i> , 2021)
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2.7.2 NO₃⁻ and Periodontal Disease

Inflamophilic bacteria exacerbate the disordered immune response seen in periodontitis (Marsh, 2006; Hajishengallis, 2015). The resulting inflammatory infiltrate includes iNOS⁺ immune cells (Wang *et al.*, 2019). As a result, elevated NO₃⁻ and NO₂⁻ levels have been observed in the GCF (Topcu Ali *et al.*, 2014) and saliva (Sánchez *et al.*, 2014) of individuals with periodontal disease.

Many periodontitis-associated species demonstrate sensitivity to oxidative damage by NO and metal oxides (Vargas-Reus *et al.*, 2012; Backlund *et al.*, 2014) and NO acts as a dispersal signal, aimed at controlling biofilm growth (Rosier, Marsh and Mira, 2018). *In-vitro* incubation of saliva with NO₃⁻ decreases levels of *Porphyromonas* and *Fusobacterium* (Rosier, Buetas, *et al.*, 2020). *Prevotella*, a genus which includes several periodontitis-associated species decreases *in-vitro* (Rosier, Buetas, *et al.*, 2020) and *in-vivo* (Vanhatalo *et al.*, 2018; Burleigh *et al.*, 2019) when NO₃⁻ availability increases. Overall biofilm changes are also associated with elevated NO₃⁻, as lower oral microbiome dysbiosis is observed when salivary NO₃⁻ increases (Chen, Marsh and Al-Hebshi, 2022).

NO₃⁻ provision benefits bacteria associated with periodontal health (Griffen *et al.*, 2012; Abusleme *et al.*, 2013; Meuric *et al.*, 2017, 2017). Alongside a reduction in gingival inflammation (Jockel-Schneider *et al.*, 2016), *Rothia* and *Neisseria* levels in the subgingival plaque increase after administration of NO₃⁻-rich lettuce juice in periodontitis patients with gingival inflammation (Jockel-Schneider *et al.*, 2021), mirroring changes previously seen in dentally healthy cohorts (Vanhatalo *et al.*, 2018; Burleigh *et al.*, 2019).

In the absence of supplementary NO₃⁻, changes in gingival inflammation are accompanied by changes in the NO₂⁻-producing microbiome. *Kingella*, *Rothia*, *Actinomyces*, *Corynebacterium*, *Haemophilus* and *Streptococcus* all increase following periodontal treatment, as do *Corynebacterium durum*, *Actinomyces massiliensis*, *Kingella oralis*, *R. dentocariosa*, *Corynebacterium matruchotii* and *Streptococcus cristatus* at the species level (Johnston *et al.*, 2021). This suggests decreases in pathological inflammation enables survival of NO₂⁻ producing bacteria.

Experimental gingivitis studies suggest an inverse relationship between NO_2^- producing bacteria and gingival inflammation. *Neisseria* was associated with inflammatory resolution in one study (Joshi *et al.*, 2014), while in another, a greater abundance of *Rothia* species were associated with limited inflammation (Huang *et al.*, 2021). *Rothia aeria*, proposed as a probiotic by Rosier *et al.*, (2020) was negatively associated with levels of IL-17 and TNF α among patients with rheumatoid arthritis (Corrêa *et al.*, 2019), an inflammatory condition associated with increased incidence of periodontitis (Demmer *et al.*, 2011).

The reductions in gingival inflammation that accompany any increase in salivary NO_3^- are likely due to a combination of NO-mediated killing of disease-associated species, alongside competition from NO_2^- producing species, advantaged by increased substrate availability. Treatment for periodontitis aims to remove the disease-associated microbiome and prevent its regrowth, subsequently reducing gingival inflammation (Graziani *et al.*, 2017). As a result, interventions which reduce inflammatory load and support the health-associated NO_2^- -producing microbiome are of interest to improve outcomes of periodontitis treatment. While NO_2^- producing species increase in abundance after healing is complete (Johnston *et al.*, 2021), changes to the NO_2^- producing microbiome throughout the rest of this period are not well understood. Determining when NO_2^- producing species start to increase in abundance within the subgingival plaque could enable the targeted administration of NO_3^- alongside conventional therapies to support the recovery of the gingival tissues.

2.8 Other Factors Affecting Oral NO_3^- Levels and NO_2^- Production

Most research to date focuses on the impact of dietary changes on oral NO_2^- production (Rosier *et al.*, 2022). However, other factors may influence NO_3^- availability and the NO_2^- producing microbiome. In periodontal health, aerobes and facultative anaerobes predominate the subgingival microbiome (Abusleme *et al.*, 2013). These include NO_2^- producing genera, such as *Rothia* and *Neisseria* (Rosier *et al.*, 2022). As periodontitis develops, the increase in inflamophilic anaerobes is accompanied by decreases in these health-associated bacteria (Chen, Marsh and Al-Hebshi, 2022). As a greater abundance of NO_2^- -producing bacteria is associated with more efficient NO_2^- -production (Doel *et al.*, 2005; Burleigh *et al.*, 2019; Liddle *et al.*, 2019), it is feasible that in untreated periodontitis, enterosalivary NO production is impaired. Despite this, changes in the behaviour and composition of the NO_2^- -producing microbiome in periodontitis have not been well explored.

Aerobic fitness levels also appear to be linked with oral NO_2^- production. Thomas *et al.*, (2019) found a significant association between NO_2^- production from an oral mouth rinse and aerobic exercise capacity. While further investigation is needed into individuals of different training and health status, this initial data suggests being physically active could enhance the activity of NO_2^- -producing bacteria (Thomas *et al.*, 2019). Consistent exercise training increases NO bioavailability, consequently increasing NO metabolite levels (Green *et al.*, 2004; McConell *et al.*, 2007). Additionally, in some (Batista *et al.*, 2019; Souza *et al.*, 2019), but not all studies (Sone *et al.*, 2019; Thomas *et al.*, 2019), the completion of a single bout of exercise increases salivary NO_2^- levels. The impact of consistent exercise training on salivary NO_3^- and NO_2^- levels has yet to be investigated and may have a significant impact on the composition of the oral microbiome and on oral NO_2^- production. A thorough examination of the oral microbiome, in the context of exercise training, is required to investigate this link and to assess if modification of the oral microbiome following exercise could enhance the effectiveness of ergogenic NO_3^- and contribute to oral health.

2.9 The Impact of Physical Activity and Exercise Training on Systemic and Oral Health

Physical activity refers to any activity that requires greater exertion compared to rest, whereas exercise refers to planned physical activity that is structured, repetitive and accompanies a specific objective (Caspersen, Powell and Christenson, 1985). Globally, adults are recommended to carry out either 150 minutes of moderate physical activity or 75 minutes of vigorous physical activity per week, or a combination of the two (World Health Organisation, 2010; Davies *et al.*, 2019). These recommendations are currently only met by 61% of Scottish women and 71% of Scottish men (Scottish Government, 2019).

Sports involve a combination of physical activity and exercise training, governed by rules of competition which direct participants towards specific goals (Khan *et al.*, 2012). Different sports have different physiological demands (Joyner and Coyle, 2008; Vanrenterghem *et al.*, 2017), which should be reflected in the training plans carried out by competitors. This necessitates completion of structured exercise training, accompanied by lifestyle changes to support training load and maximise performance.

Physical activity reduces the risk of mortality and chronic disease development (Samitz, Egger and Zwahlen, 2011; Kyu *et al.*, 2016). Furthermore, a dose-response relationship exists between time spent exercising and reduced mortality risk (Samitz, Egger and Zwahlen, 2011). While the impact of ‘excessive’ exercise on systemic health has come under scrutiny, elite athletes appear to live significantly longer compared to the general population (Runacres, Mackintosh and McNarry, 2021). These benefits appear greatest in individuals who focus on training their cardiorespiratory systems (Clarke *et al.*, 2012; Lee-Heidenreich, Lee-Heidenreich and Myers, 2017).

In the general population, poor oral health is associated with worse medical health (Hakeem, Bernabé and Sabbah, 2019; Kotronia *et al.*, 2021) with a greater number of missing teeth a predictive marker for all-cause mortality risk (Peng *et al.*, 2019). In addition, carrying out physical activity is linked to dental health among most population groups (Sanchez *et al.*, 2020; Ferreira *et al.*, 2019). Drawing causal conclusions regarding this relationship is complicated by the shared risk factors associated with inactivity and dental disease (Pourat, Choi and Chen, 2018; White *et al.*, 2020; Watson *et al.*, 2022). This means further research is needed to identify the precise mechanisms which link dental health with physical activity in the general population.

2.9.1 Incidence of Dental Disease in Elite and Professional Athletes

With the number of shared risk factors between oral and medical health, elite athletes might be expected to have excellent dental health. However, reports of the use of dental services at consecutive Olympic Games (Vougiouklakis *et al.*, 2008; Yang *et al.*, 2011; Needleman *et al.*, 2013) and other elite-level sporting events (Sharma, Verma and Mehrotra, 2012; Opazo-García *et al.*, 2021) indicate high treatment needs among athletes. These individuals may have spent thousands of hours training, only to have their performance potentially jeopardised by preventable dental disease (Peres *et al.*, 2019).

It could be assumed these studies report on population outliers (Mazor *et al.*, 2002), with actual disease prevalence similar to, or better, than that of the general population (Tripepi *et al.*, 2010). Instead, poor oral health is a consistent finding among representative populations of European athletes throughout their usual training calendar. 43% of Dutch athletes demonstrated dental disease requiring intervention in the lead-up to the 2016 Summer Olympics (Kragt *et al.*, 2019).

Another study showed the presence of dental caries severe enough to result in enamel breakdown in 49% of elite British athletes (Gallagher *et al.*, 2018). 77% of the same cohort had periodontal inflammation as a result of poor oral hygiene (Gallagher *et al.*, 2018). Oral health is also poor among professional athletes who do not target Olympic representation. Clinical examination of 187 UK-based professional football players showed 37% had active dental caries, 53% dental erosion and 5% moderate-severe irreversible periodontitis (Needleman *et al.*, 2016) while 24 professional rugby players demonstrated greater caries experience and frequency of gingivitis compared to controls (Minty *et al.*, 2018).

While no control group was included, the UK-based athletes (Needleman *et al.*, 2016; Gallagher *et al.*, 2018) can be compared with the general population, as assessed by the Adult Dental Health Survey (ADHS 2009) (White *et al.*, 2012). The population assessed by the ADHS is weighted towards disadvantaged members of the population, who have high levels of dental disease. Many elite athletes come from advantaged backgrounds (Lawrence, 2017), so would be expected to have good oral health (Ghanbarzadegan *et al.*, 2021). However, 36% of UK adults aged 25-34 assessed by the ADHS have established dental caries (White *et al.*, 2012), compared to up to 49% of elite athletes.

These findings implicate factors specific to the elite sporting environment in increased dental disease risk. While some preventative measures are generalisable, risks and preventative strategies specific to elite-level sports should be implemented to effectively prevent dental disease (Birch *et al.*, 2015; Needleman *et al.*, 2015, 2018).

2.9.2 Incidence of Dental Disease in Competitive Sports

Several studies examine disease prevalence among highly trained individuals, who are not classified as elite-level performers (McKay *et al.*, 2021). Despite their high training loads, these populations do not seem to be at as severe a risk of dental disease development compared to control populations.

A higher risk of erosive wear detected in triathletes compared to controls (Frese *et al.*, 2015). However, members of German national youth teams and perspective squads, from a variety of endurance sports, had little erosive wear, comparable to a control group with no competitive goals (Merle, *et al.*, 2022). The youth squad athletes were around 10 years younger than the

triathletes so this finding may change if the teeth are exposed to an acidic environment over the longer term.

As in elite cohorts, training load appears linked to caries experience. Time spent training was significantly correlated with DMFT among triathletes (Frese *et al.*, 2015), while young endurance athletes had significantly more untreated decayed teeth compared to non-competitive controls (Merle, *et al.*, 2022). However, a comparison of swimmers showed no difference in caries experience between individuals who trained to compete and those who did not (D’Ercole *et al.*, 2016). Finally, the youth squad members demonstrated increased periodontal probing depths, indicative of periodontitis development (Merle, *et al.*, 2022).

2.9.3 Impact of Dental Health on Quality of Life

The impact of pain from sports injuries on quality of life is widely reported (Boneti Moreira *et al.*, 2014) and injury risk can be reduced by proactive monitoring of an athlete’s physiological and psychological load (Soligard *et al.*, 2016) and through proactive injury prevention (Mendonça *et al.*, 2022). Up to 29.9% of athletes report they experience oral pain (Gallagher *et al.*, 2018), with self-reported measures of quality of life significantly associated with clinical evidence of disease (Needleman *et al.*, 2016). Preventing dental disease provides an opportunity to improve on quality of life among individuals involved in sports.

2.9.4 Impact of Dental Health on Sports Performance

The symptoms of an acute dental abscess include sudden onset of pain severe enough to prevent sleeping, trismus (limited jaw opening), fever and malaise (Raof *et al.*, 2022). Operative intervention will be required to safely resolve a severe acute dental infection (Robertson *et al.*, 2015), followed by recovery before usual activity can be resumed (Bayetto, Cheng and Goss, 2020). This has obvious implications for training and competition, as demonstrated by case reports from the 1968 Summer Olympics (Forrest, 1969).

Athletes report missing training or competitions and experiencing disturbed recovery as a consequence of their dental health (Needleman *et al.*, 2013, 2016; Gallagher *et al.*, 2018; Kragt *et al.*, 2019). The strongest links between poor performance and dental disease are seen in athletes with active dental caries. A greater number of carious lesions were associated with athlete-reported measures of performance at the 2012 Olympics (Needleman *et al.*, 2013).

Similar results are seen among athletes not actively seeking treatment as professional football players with more decayed and filled teeth or active lesions were more likely to report adverse effects on performance (Needleman *et al.*, 2016).

The insidious impacts of disease may be less obvious. In the general population, periodontal inflammation negatively impacts exercise performance (Bramantoro *et al.*, 2020). Similar findings have been found among athlete populations. In a professional football club, poor oral hygiene and deeper periodontal pockets were weakly associated a greater number of muscle injuries (Gay-Escoda *et al.*, 2011). Inflammation may impair muscle repair (Howard *et al.*, 2020) and an increased inflammatory load may increase injury risk (Howard *et al.*, 2020). In larger athlete cohorts, despite high levels of gingival inflammation, no association has been found between gingivitis and sports performance (Needleman *et al.*, 2016; Gallagher *et al.*, 2018; Kragt *et al.*, 2019).

2.10 Reasons for Increased Dental Disease Risk in Competitive Sports

Many factors may contribute to disease development among individuals involved in competitive sports. Dietary guidelines aimed at supporting sports performance advise the frequent consumption of high volumes of cariogenic carbohydrates (Broad and Rye, 2015; Needleman *et al.*, 2015). Exercise-induced changes to saliva may impair its protective functions (Ntovas *et al.*, 2022). As individuals become involved in higher-level sports lifestyle demands change. For example, more time spent is travelling (Burns *et al.*, 2022), potentially impacting on access to preventative dental care. Initial research shows differences within the disease-associated oral microbiome of athletes compared to controls (Minty *et al.*, 2018). Figure 2-6 summarises the factors influencing dental disease risk in individuals who train for competitive sports.

Figure 2-6: A summary of the factors influencing dental disease risk in individuals who train for competitive sports. Individual behaviours and the physiological effects of consistent intensive exercise training impact directly on the environment of the oral cavity. The impact of these changes on the oral microbiome are not well understood. The combination of these changes is likely to influence the oral health status of individuals who train for competitive sports.

2.10.1 Dietary Differences

To support sports performance, dietary choices should be directed by competitive goals and informed by sports-specific guidance (Thomas, Erdman and Burke, 2016), individualising the impact of diet on the oral cavity. This means dental healthcare professionals should not consider individuals involved in competitive sports as a homogenous population.

Carbohydrate Supplementation to Support Performance

Skeletal muscle oxidises carbohydrates during intensive aerobic exercise, ensuring glycogen availability to support performance (Hargreaves and Spriet, 2020). This means adequate carbohydrates must be consumed following, during, and in anticipation of, a hard exercise bout (Burke *et al.*, 2011; Thomas, Erdman and Burke, 2016). Recommended carbohydrate intake for active individuals is shown in Table 2-4.

Table 2-4: A summary of carbohydrate intake recommendations for active individuals. Intake should be adjusted depending on the individual and their training load. Data from (Burke et al., 2011).

Situation		Carbohydrate targets
Daily needs for fuel and recovery		
Light	Low-intensity or skill-based activities	3–5 g · kg ⁻¹ of athlete's body mass per day
Moderate	Moderate exercise programme (i.e. ~1 h · day ⁻¹)	5–7 g · kg ⁻¹ · day ⁻¹
High	Endurance programme (e.g. moderate-to-high intensity exercise of 1–3 h · day ⁻¹)	6–10 g · kg ⁻¹ · day ⁻¹
Very high	Extreme commitment (i.e. moderate-to-high intensity exercise of >4–5 h · day ⁻¹)	8–12 g · kg ⁻¹ · day ⁻¹
Carbohydrate consumption in preparation for activity.		
General fuelling	Preparation for events <90 min exercise	7–12 g · kg ⁻¹ per 24 h as for daily fuel needs
Carbohydrate loading	Preparation for events >90 min of sustained/intermittent exercise	36–48 h of 10–12 g · kg ⁻¹ body mass per 24 h
Pre-event fuelling	Before exercise >60 min	1–4 g · kg ⁻¹ consumed 1–4 h before exercise
Carbohydrate consumption during activity.		
Brief exercise	<45 min	Not needed

Sustained intensity exercise	high- 45–75 min	Small amounts including mouth rinse
Endurance including “stop and start” sports	exercise 1.0–2.5 h	30–60 g · h ⁻¹
Ultra-endurance exercise	>2.5–3.0 h	Up to 90 g · h ⁻¹
Carbohydrate consumption for refuelling post-activity		
Refuelling	<8 h recovery between two fuel demanding sessions	1.0–1.2 g · kg ⁻¹ · h ⁻¹ for first 4 h then resume daily fuel needs

Pre-exercise carbohydrate consumption improves exercise capacity by sparing intramyofibrillar glycogen and increasing blood glucose availability (Jensen *et al.*, 2020). To ensure recovery for subsequent training or competition, glycogen stores in the liver and muscle must also be replenished post-exercise (Burke, van Loon and Hawley, 2017), through the consumption of high glycaemic index carbohydrates (Burke *et al.*, 2011; Thomas, Erdman and Burke, 2016). Athletes with higher training loads, such as those training multiple times a day, may need additional meals and snacks to meet fuelling needs (Burke *et al.*, 2003).

Intra-exercise carbohydrate supplementation targets two different pathways. Oral-carbohydrate sensing involves a sugar rinse or gel being held in the mouth for 10-15 seconds before being spat out or swallowed. This is repeated every 10-15 minutes for the duration of activity (Stellingwerff and Cox, 2014). This activates carbohydrate-sensing receptors, linked to the motor pathways (Gant, Stinear and Byblow, 2010) and reward centres of the central nervous system (Chambers, Bridge and Jones, 2009) and improves performance (De Ataide e Silva *et al.*, 2014) by attenuating central fatigue and stimulating motor cortex excitability (Gant, Stinear and Byblow, 2010).

The second pathway targets absorption of carbohydrate from the gut. This increases blood glucose levels, spares liver glycogen and maintains a high rate of carbohydrate oxidation (Jeukendrup, 2004). The amount of carbohydrate consumed should be increased with duration and intensity of exercise (Jeukendrup, 2014; Thomas, Erdman and Burke, 2016).

As intra-exercise carbohydrate supplementation involves the frequent introduction of cariogenic, acidic substances to the oral cavity it has serious implications for the oral health of anyone using intra-exercise carbohydrate supplementation (Broad and Rye, 2015). Current evidence also indicates carbohydrate supplementation increases the risk of dental caries and erosion development. An initial study reported 83.3% of sub-elite triathletes used sports drinks while training (Bryant *et al.*, 2011). These triathletes indicated this was not taken on as a large bolus, instead being consumed in small, frequent quantities, more likely to overwhelm salivary buffering (Hicks, Garcia-Godoy and Flaitz, 2008). Despite this, only 3.2% of triathletes believed their behaviours during training were of high risk to their oral health (Bryant *et al.*, 2011). 28.3% of student-athletes at Nigerian universities reported frequent soft drink consumption, while 59.3% had never visited a dentist, so will never have received preventative care (Azodo and Osazuwa, 2013). The most recent study questioned 344 elite and professional

athletes from a mixture of sporting backgrounds (Gallagher *et al.*, 2019). Only 28.2% were classified as high consumers of sugar, but their levels of carbohydrate supplement usage and frequency of snacking still increased their disease risk. 58.8% reported regular use of energy bars, 70.3% energy gels and 85.7% sports drinks during exercise. While preventative advice aims to reduce cariogenic snacks between meals (Public Health England, 2021), 56% of athletes indicated they did not feel they could do so and maintain their activity levels.

Hydration to Support Sports Performance

In addition to ensuring adequate carbohydrate consumption, athletes aim to exercise in a euhydrated state (McDermott *et al.*, 2017) as thermoregulation causes fluid loss, which impacts performance (Carlton and Orr, 2015). While water can be used in the first instance as a hydration aid, other components are added to sports drinks to support performance and recovery and may impact on oral health.

If the athlete will exercise again within 24 hours or if they are sweating heavily, electrolytes such as sodium and potassium should be consumed (Shirreffs and Sawka, 2011). To prevent caries, sugar-free electrolyte mixes can be selected (Needleman *et al.*, 2018). Carbohydrate or sugar-free sweeteners (non-nutritive sweetening agents) also make drinks more palatable, increasing compliance with rehydration regimes (Passe *et al.*, 2004). Sugar-free sports drinks sound like an attractive recommendation to prevent dental disease, as they cannot be easily fermented by bacteria (Matsukubo and Takazoe, 2006). However, the acids added to flavour these products may still lower the salivary pH, leading to erosive damage (Shen *et al.*, 2017). Additionally, carbohydrates enable refuelling and may assist in fluid retention, so may still be added for this purpose (Baker and Jeukendrup, 2014).

2.10.2 Physiological Changes with Exercise

Changes to Saliva

Dental disease risk increases when salivary flow is impaired (Walsh *et al.*, 2004) and if the composition of saliva is altered (Heo, Ruhl and Scannapieco, 2013). This is because saliva has multiple protective functions which work in tandem to prevent disease (Dodds *et al.*, 2015).

The liquid component of saliva dilutes acid and enables debris clearance (Buzalaf, Hannas and Kato, 2012). Bicarbonate ions, phosphate ions and urea set up a dynamic equilibrium that controls the oral acid-base balance, allowing recovery following consumption of an acidic substance (Bardow *et al.*, 2000).

Saliva also has important immunogenic properties. Antimicrobial peptides disrupt bacterial cell function and aid pathogen clearance (Khurshid *et al.*, 2016) while antibodies bind antigens (Macpherson *et al.*, 2008), allowing for pathogen clearance or further activation of the immune response. Calcium and phosphate, the mineral components of saliva, can repair demineralised tooth tissue, protecting against their acidic dissolution (Farooq and Bugshan, 2020).

Changes to Salivary Flow Rate

Salivary flow rates do not appear to change following short-duration activities (<1 hour) (Walsh *et al.*, 1999; Allgrove *et al.*, 2008; Ligtenberg *et al.*, 2015; Rutherford-Markwick *et al.*, 2017; Leicht, Goosey-Tolfrey and Bishop, 2018), regardless of intensity (Sari-Sarraf, Reilly and Doran, 2006; Allgrove *et al.*, 2008; Leicht, Goosey-Tolfrey and Bishop, 2018). In contrast, longer exercise bouts do decrease salivary flow rates (Ljungberg *et al.*, 1997; Blannin *et al.*, 1998; Bishop *et al.*, 2000).

High levels of erosive wear are seen in highly trained groups (Frese *et al.*, 2015; Kragt *et al.*, 2019), despite no difference in stimulated salivary flow rate compared to controls (Frese *et al.*, 2015). Among healthy, recreationally active individuals, erosive wear is more severe in individuals who experience a greater reduction in salivary flow rate during exercise (Mulic *et al.*, 2012).

Changes to Functional Components of Saliva

Several salivary components implicated in oral microbiome homeostasis change with exercise. Levels of the antimicrobial protein lactoferrin increase after acute exercise (Gillum *et al.*, 2013, 2017), but decrease over the course of a competitive season (He *et al.*, 2010; West *et al.*, 2010) and are lower in competitive athletes (West *et al.*, 2010). Salivary IgA is increased in active members of the general population (Shimizu *et al.*, 2007), but decreases following intensive exercise, potentially compromising biofilm homeostasis and mucosal barrier immunity (Drummond *et al.*, 2022).

The O₂ demand of respiring muscles increases with exercise intensity, eventually exceeding the cardiorespiratory system's ability to maintain aerobic respiration. The body then relies on anaerobic respiratory mechanisms, resulting in lactate accumulation in the blood and saliva (Segura *et al.*, 1996; Yan *et al.*, 2023). Increased lactate fermentation by oral bacteria lowers the salivary pH, increasing the risk of erosion (Frese *et al.*, 2015). These conditions also provide a suitable environment for acidophilic bacteria, which may increase the risk of dental caries and tooth demineralisation (Marsh, 2006).

2.10.3 Microbiome Changes with Exercise

The impact of exercise on the oral microbiome has received little attention. While species abundance was not quantified, a comparison of competitive and non-competitive swimmers showed no significant difference in the number of individuals with *S. mutans* present in their saliva. In contrast, another caries-associated bacteria, *Streptococcus sobrinus*, was present in the saliva of 92% of non-competitive swimmers, compared to 22% of competitive swimmers (D'Ercole *et al.*, 2016).

To date, only one study has examined microbiome variations between elite athletes and controls (Minty *et al.*, 2018). In addition to an increased incidence of dental caries, professional rugby players exhibited an enrichment of caries-associated bacteria. This included a greater abundance of acidifying *S. mutans* and *S. sobrinus* (de Soet, Nyvad and Kilian, 2000). These species correlate negatively with urea production and alkalinisation, which indicates impaired buffering (Gordan *et al.*, 2011). Lactic acid-producing *Streptococcus thermophiles* (Oehmcke *et al.*, 2010) was also elevated. Predictive metagenomic analysis suggested enrichment of genes linked to carbohydrate metabolism within the athlete microbiome. These findings indicate the lifestyle of elite athletes supports the development of a biofilm which, if left unchecked, would support tooth demineralisation.

Conversely, despite increased gingival bleeding, a lower abundance of periodontitis-associated *Fusobacterium* and *Porphyromonas* (Pérez-Chaparro *et al.*, 2014) were seen in the rugby players. From the perspective of NO₂⁻ production, *Rothia* was enriched in rugby players, while *Neisseria* was higher in the controls. *Rothia* grow rapidly in the presence of oxygen (Rosier, Moya-Gonzalvez, *et al.*, 2020) while *Fusobacterium* and *Porphyromonas* are obligate anaerobes (Pérez-Chaparro *et al.*, 2014). Additionally, *Rothia* possess genes for lactate

utilisation (Rosier, Moya-Gonzalvez, *et al.*, 2020), so may benefit from increases in salivary lactate during hard exercise (Thomas *et al.*, 2019). Further investigation is needed to confirm if these changes in the of NO_2^- producing microbiome are seen in cohorts involved in different sports. Supporting analysis of salivary of NO_3^- and of NO_2^- levels would also confirm if these changes results from increases in these ions in the oral microenvironment.

This previous study has several key limitations. Only a small sample (n=24) of male rugby players were included. Participation in rugby requires the use of removable mouthguards and results in different macronutrient requirements compared to other sports (Thomas, Erdman and Burke, 2016). Both factors are likely to influence the composition of the microbiome (D'Ercole *et al.*, 2014; Santonocito *et al.*, 2022), preventing assessment of the impacts of exercise training in isolation. In addition, the microbiome analysis used relied on short-read 16s rRNA sequencing. Quantification of the full length of the 16s gene would grant a high degree of certainty of species-level bacterial abundance and enable accurate comparison between the biofilms of different individuals, improving understanding of the nuances of community interactions (Callahan, McMurdie and Holmes, 2017).

As previously alluded to, the completion of different volumes of exercise training appears to impact on dental disease risk. Assessing oral microbiome changes between individuals of differing exercise training status will indicate if disease-associated species change in abundance. Conversely, it will enable the identification of commensal species which benefit from exercise training. These species may contribute to the maintenance of oral and systemic health. For example, an increased abundance of NO_2^- -producing species could enhance the benefits of NO_3^- supplementation on oral health (Jockel-Schneider *et al.*, 2016; Burleigh *et al.*, 2018, 2020; Rosier *et al.*, 2021). Therefore, certain bacteria may contribute to athletic performance, mirroring findings in the gut, where *V. atypica* isolates from elite athletes improve the running performance of inoculated mice by increasing the efficiency of lactate metabolism (Scheiman *et al.*, 2019).

2.10.4 Other Competitive Sports-Specific Factors Which May Influence Oral Health

Compared to the general population, elite athletes have a higher level of occupational risk acceptance (Chen, Buggy and Kelly, 2019). Most anticipate they will become injured by their work and carry out unhealthy behaviours if they believe they will benefit performance

(Waldron and Krane, 2005). To some dentists, reducing the frequency of sugar consumption might seem an obvious way to improve oral health. Giving non-pragmatic advice on carbohydrate restriction fails to consider the pressure athletes face to perform (Kerksick *et al.*, 2017). This population are accepting of the risk of injury, due to their regular bouts of intensive training and psychological and sociocultural environment (Cunningham *et al.*, 2020). They also may not disclose pain to avoid being removed from the field of play (Kerr *et al.*, 2016). As a result, adherence to radical dietary change is likely to be low, even after interventions from specially trained sports dentists (Gallagher, Ashley and Needleman, 2020).

Sports dentistry aims to provide oral health screening, advice and treatment, specifically for athletes (Gallagher *et al.*, 2021). The IOC are keen to promote all aspects of health among sportspeople (Ljungqvist *et al.*, 2009), so expert advice recommends dentists work closely with athletes, mirroring other health promotion initiatives in elite-level sports (Needleman *et al.*, 2015). The athlete support team consists of all individuals who support athlete performance and well-being, such as coaches, nutritionists, sports scientists, and other medical professionals (IOC, 2020). However, especially at the sub-elite level, the number of athletes who can access easily access a sports dentist is unknown, so, in the UK, athletes are likely to rely on general dental practitioners (GDPs) for their care. Even regular dental attendees, who do not just seek treatment when they are in pain (Steele *et al.*, 2011), only see their GDP a few times a year, as dictated by their dental disease risk (Public Health England, 2021). In contrast, they will interact with other members of their support team much more frequently.

One important role of the GDP is to screen patients for dental disease, requiring individuals to attend their dentist at appropriate intervals (Public Health England, 2021). 20.83% of elite rugby players had attended their dentist within the past year compared to 77.27% of untrained controls (Minty *et al.*, 2018) and less than 80% of German youth squad members indicated they regular dental check-ups (Merle, Wuestenfeld, *et al.*, 2022). Failing to attend appointments means dental diseases will be undetected in their early stages, allowing the development of disease severe enough to impact on quality of life and performance (Needleman *et al.*, 2013, 2016; Gallagher *et al.*, 2018).

Oral Health Behaviours in Sports

The responsibility for dental disease prevention lies primarily with the individual patient who carries out daily oral hygiene and monitors their diet (Birch *et al.*, 2015). They must be

supported by input from their dental team, who provide targeted support (Public Health England, 2021). If a patient is identified as being at increased risk of dental disease, the dental team may decide to provide enhanced preventative care (Birch *et al.*, 2015).

Diet is not the only patient behaviour which impacts the oral cavity. Plaque control and fluoride use also influence disease risk. Despite this, only one study evaluates these behaviours among a population of elite athletes, indicating better oral hygiene habits among athletes compared to the general population (Gallagher *et al.*, 2019). 94% of athletes stated they brushed their teeth twice daily and 43% reported they used interdental cleaning aids compared to 74% and 18% of the general population, as assessed by the ADHS 2009 (Chadwick *et al.*, 2011). This did not mean that oral hygiene was effective, as many had high levels of gingival bleeding indicative of poor plaque control (Gallagher *et al.*, 2019).

A subsequent investigation showed athletes are amenable to behavioural changes that benefit their oral health (Gallagher, Ashley and Needleman, 2020). Elite athletes were offered a targeted intervention, consisting of educational presentations and preventative advice, informed by the results of a clinical examination. Oral health literacy significantly improved among participants. This was accompanied by positive behavioural changes including an increase in the use of fluoride-containing toothpaste and interdental cleaning aids (Gallagher, Ashley and Needleman, 2020). The intervention, delivered by a dentist with an interest in athlete oral health, could be replicated to provide targeted advice to larger groups. However, when surveyed, specialist sports dentists who work with sports teams outside of the UK indicate most of the treatment they provide focuses on trauma prevention and treatment, not preventative care (McGovern, Spolarich and Keim, 2015).

The level of understanding of the athlete lifestyle and its possible consequences for oral health among GDPs is unknown. Responses from the athletes of Gallagher, Ashley and Needleman (2020) revealed only 40.1% could recall having received diet advice. While this could be due to recall failure, GDPs also state a lack of knowledge as a barrier in their delivery of dietary advice to patients (Hayes, Wallace and Coxon, 2016). In the context of competitive sports, this may mean they are unwilling to contradict advice given by sports nutritionists and coaches or unsure of what the appropriate preventative instructions are for this population.

While some members of the athlete support team may be responsible for the delivery of nutrition advice which compromises oral health, they also have opportunities to deliver mitigation advice if given appropriate training. Currently, there is no information available on how much knowledge non-dental members of the athlete support team possesses regarding dental disease prevention. This could mean that the resources developed specifically for dental disease prevention in sports (Eastman Dental Institute, 2017; World Dental Federation, 2019c) are not being used in the field, contributing to further deterioration of dental health and significant impacts on performance and wellbeing.

2.11 Summary and Statement of the Problem

Adequate NO bioavailability is vital for the maintenance of systemic health. Targeting exogenous NO production by increasing NO_3^- availability has received interest as a possible way to improve systemic health (Lundberg, Carlström and Weitzberg, 2018). The first step in exogenous NO production relies on commensal oral bacteria. These species are capable of efficient NO_3^- reduction, alongside all subsequent stages in exogenous NO production (Rosier *et al.*, 2022). Recent studies highlight the apparent importance of exogenous NO production in the maintenance of oral health. In addition to increasing the relative abundance of health-associated NO_2^- -producing bacteria, elevated NO_3^- availability alters the oral environment by increasing resistance to acidification (Li *et al.*, 2007; Yamamoto *et al.*, 2017; Burleigh *et al.*, 2020; Rosier *et al.*, 2021) and reducing gingival inflammation (Jockel-Schneider *et al.*, 2016, 2021). These changes may prevent the development of dental diseases, which are caused by alterations to the oral microenvironment which enable the survival of pathogenic bacteria (Rosier, Marsh and Mira, 2018).

The pre-existing literature focuses on the impact of dietary NO_3^- supplementation on the oral microbiome and environment. However, other factors may alter salivary NO_3^- levels and therefore oral health. These include the successful treatment of dental diseases (Shi *et al.*, 2015; Chen *et al.*, 2018; Johnston *et al.*, 2021) and the performance of regular physical activity, which enhances endogenous NO production (Dyakova *et al.*, 2015) and is associated with altered dental disease risk (Frese *et al.*, 2015; Needleman *et al.*, 2016; Gallagher *et al.*, 2019; Sanchez *et al.*, 2020).

At the start of this PhD, the effects of dietary NO_3^- supplementation on the oral cavity and microbiome were beginning to be understood. However, the impact of some other factors which alter the oral microenvironment and microbiome, especially in relation to oral NO_2^- production, were not known. The successful treatment of periodontitis was known to increase the abundance of health-associated bacteria. However, its impact on salivary NO_3^- and NO_2^- levels, and on the NO_2^- -producing microbiome during healing had never been assessed. While exercise training was known to elevate NO_3^- and NO_2^- bioavailability in the plasma, its impact on salivary NO_3^- and NO_2^- and the storage of these metabolites in the muscle was unknown. No data was available assessing the impact of exercise training on the microbiome of the tongue dorsum or dental plaque and no studies had been carried out on the direct impact of consistent exercise on the oral microbiome. Finally, despite the increased risk of dental disease among some highly trained and elite athlete cohorts, the dental care advice provided to individuals training for competitive sports by their dental and coaching teams was unknown.

2.12 Thesis Aims and Objectives

The broad aim of this thesis was to increase the knowledge of how changes to the oral environment impact on the oral microbiome and on physiological NO cycling and assess knowledge, beliefs and attitudes on oral health support for athletes. To achieve this, a series of studies were carried out, examining the impact of successful treatment of periodontitis and changes in exercise training status on the oral microbiome and to assess the current delivery of preventative care to athletes. The aims and hypotheses of each study are outlined below.

2.12.1 Study 1

Aim 1 - To determine the impact of successful treatment of periodontitis on the NO_2^- -producing microbiome of the subgingival plaque throughout post-treatment biofilm reformation.

Aim 2 - To determine the impact of successful treatment of periodontitis on salivary NO_3^- and NO_2^- levels.

Hypothesis 1 relating to Aim 1 - Relative to baseline, the NO_2^- -producing microbiome would increase in relative abundance once periodontal healing and subgingival biofilm reformation was complete.

Hypothesis 2 relating to Aim 1 - Relative to baseline, the NO_2^- -producing microbiome would increase in relative abundance at earlier post-treatment timepoints.

Hypothesis 3 relating to Aim 2 - Following successful treatment and completion of periodontal healing, salivary NO_3^- and NO_2^- levels would be found to increase relative to baseline.

2.12.2 Study 2

Aim 1 - To determine the impact of a change from a sedentary lifestyle to carrying out weekly high-intensity interval training (HIIT), sufficient to meet WHO guidelines for minimum aerobic exercise levels, on NO_3^- and NO_2^- levels in the saliva, plasma, and muscle.

Aim 2 - To determine the impact of a change from a sedentary lifestyle to carrying out weekly HIIT, sufficient to meet WHO guidelines for minimum aerobic exercise levels, on the composition of the microbiome of the tongue dorsum in a group of healthy males.

Hypothesis 1 relating to Aim 1 - Regular HIIT would alter the efficiency of both endogenous and exogenous NO production. As a result, changes in NO_3^- and NO_2^- levels would be observed in all three of the sampled substances following a period of exercise training. After returning to baseline activity levels, these changes would be reversed.

Hypothesis 2 relating to Aim 2 - Regular HIIT would significantly alter the composition of the tongue dorsum microbiome.

Hypothesis 2 relating to Aim 3 - Regular HIIT would significantly increase the relative abundance of known NO_2^- -producing bacteria of the tongue dorsum microbiome.

2.12.3 Study 3

Aim 1 - To determine the impact of long-term exercise training, aiming to improve performance during competitive sports, on NO_3^- and NO_2^- levels in the saliva and plasma in healthy humans.

Aim 2 - To determine the impact of long-term exercise training, aiming to improve performance during competitive sports, on the tongue dorsum microbiome in a group of healthy humans.

Aim 3 - To determine the impact of long-term exercise training, aiming to improve performance during competitive sports on the supragingival plaque microbiome in a group of healthy humans.

Hypothesis 1 relating to Aim 1 - Long-term training to improve performance in competitive sports would be associated with an increase in the efficiency of both endogenous and exogenous NO production. As a result, elevated NO_3^- and NO_2^- levels would be observed in the plasma and saliva of trained participants.

Hypothesis 2 relating to Aim 2 and 3 - The consistent completion of regular exercise training would be associated with alterations in the composition of the oral microbiome at both sampled sites.

Hypothesis 3 relating to Aim 2 and 3 - The consistent completion of regular exercise training would be associated with an increase in the relative abundance of known NO₂⁻-producing bacteria of the tongue dorsum microbiome.

Hypothesis 4 relating to Aim 2 and 3 - The consistent completion of regular exercise training would be associated with an increase in the relative abundance of disease-associated bacteria in the supragingival plaque.

2.12.4 Study 4

Aim 1 - To assess the knowledge, beliefs, and attitudes of athletes on oral health support available to them.

Aim 2 - To assess the knowledge, beliefs, and attitudes of sports coaches on oral health support for athletes.

Aim 3 - To assess the knowledge, beliefs, and attitudes of non-specialist dental healthcare professionals on oral health support for athletes.

Hypothesis 1 relating to Aims 2 and 2 - Neither dental healthcare professionals nor sports coaches would feel equipped to deliver targeted dental disease prevention to individuals who train for competitive sports.

Hypothesis 2 relating to Aims 2 and 3 - Both dental healthcare professionals and sports coaches would feel that a lack of knowledge was a significant barrier in the delivery of advice targeting dental disease prevention in individuals who train for competitive sports.

Hypothesis 3 relating to Aims 1 and 2 - Athletes would have received general preventative dental advice and care from the dental team.

Hypothesis 4 relating to Aims 2 and 3 - Athletes would not have received any sort of preventative dental advice from their coaches.

3. Chapter 3 Periodontal Treatment Causes a Longitudinal Increase in NO₂⁻-Producing Bacteria

Key Points

- Treatment of periodontitis does not alter the concentration of NO₃⁻ and NO₂⁻ in the saliva.
- Following treatment of periodontitis, the grouped relative abundance of NO₂⁻-producing species increases and the grouped relative abundance of periodontitis-associated species decreases. These finding remains consistent throughout the duration of periodontal healing.
- Strong, significant negative associations were detected between the grouped NO₂⁻-producing species and grouped periodontitis-associated species at baseline and throughout periodontal healing, suggesting some NO₂⁻-producing bacteria may inhibit the growth of disease-associated species.

Role of Annabel Simpson in This Chapter

- Statistical analysis and interpretation of changes in clinical disease indicators.
- Statistical analysis and interpretation of changes in NO_3^- and NO_2^- levels in the saliva.
- Collation of bacterial species as NO_2^- -producing bacteria and periodontitis-associated species and subsequent statistical analysis and interpretation.
- Construction of all tables and figures.

A version of this chapter has been published in the following journal article:

Simpson A, Johnston W, Carda-Diéguez M, Mira A, Easton C, Henriquez FL, Culshaw S, Rosier BT, Burleigh M. Periodontal treatment causes a longitudinal increase in nitrite-producing bacteria. *Mol Oral Microbiol.* 2024 Aug 22. doi: 10.1111/omi.12479.

3.1 Introduction

Over the past decade, the interplay between oral and systemic health has gained increasing attention. Periodontitis is estimated to affect 62% of dentate adults (Trindade *et al.*, 2023). In addition to its oral effects, it is associated with worse clinical outcomes in systemic conditions, including cardiovascular diseases (Sanz *et al.*, 2020), diabetes mellitus (Preshaw and Bissett, 2019) and Alzheimer's disease (Desta, 2021). Therefore, it is apparent that periodontitis has far-reaching health and economic implications which extend beyond the oral cavity.

The subgingival microbiome in periodontal health is dominated by commensal facultative anaerobic species, which coexist alongside host immunosurveillance (Lamont, Koo and Hajishengallis, 2018). During periodontitis, the increase in periodontitis-associated species at diseased sites is accompanied by decreases in these health-associated species (Chen, Marsh and Al-Hebshi, 2022). In addition to the deregulated inflammation, this change has implications for the host as some bacteria carry out functions which aid in the maintenance of oral and systemic health – such as nitrate (NO_3^-)-reducing bacteria.

Nitrate-reducing bacteria form an essential part of the enterosalivary NO_3^- - NO_2^- -Nitric Oxide (NO) pathway (Hezel and Weitzberg, 2015). The NO_3^- - NO_2^- -NO pathway provides an alternative source of bioactive NO, complimenting the breakdown of L-arginine by human NO synthases (NOS) enzymes (Förstermann and Sessa, 2012). NO is a signalling molecule with multiple physiological functions. These include the maintenance of endothelial function and control of blood pressure (BP) (Bryan *et al.*, 2008; Kapil *et al.*, 2020), regulation of platelet function (Webb *et al.*, 2008), enhancement of exercise performance (Senefeld *et al.*, 2020), improved efficiency of muscle contraction (Bailey *et al.*, 2009), wound healing (Luo and Chen, 2005), insulin sensitivity and glucose homeostasis (Gilchrist *et al.*, 2013), attenuation of oxidative stress and inflammation (Carlström *et al.*, 2011), immune function (Bogdan, 2001) and the maintenance of brain (Wightman *et al.*, 2015), and oral health (Kapil *et al.*, 2013; Rosier *et al.*, 2022; Moran *et al.*, 2024). While NO_3^- -reducing bacteria are commonly classified by their capacity to produce NO_2^- this may be a misnomer since the NO_2^- may be generated from other substrates, such as the oxidation of ammonium (Rosier, Moya-Gonzalvez, *et al.*, 2020). In this study, we therefore refer to these bacteria as NO_2^- producing bacteria. Bacteria which demonstrate NO_2^- -producing capacity include members of the genera *Rothia*, *Neisseria*, *Veillonella*, *Actinomyces*, *Corynebacterium*, *Haemophilus* and *Prevotella* (Doel *et al.*, 2005;

Hyde *et al.*, 2014; Rosier *et al.*, 2022). Of these, genera with oral representatives that were confirmed to reduce NO_3^- (by physiological measurements of NO_3^-), include *Rothia*, *Neisseria*, *Veillonella* and *Actinomyces* (Rosier *et al.*, 2022).

Inorganic NO_3^- is found in dietary sources and is abundant in certain vegetables (e.g., leafy greens, beetroots, and radishes), a food group clearly associated with health benefits (Hord, Tang and Bryan, 2009). Once absorbed from the small intestine, approximately 25% of NO_3^- is transported via the circulation to the oral cavity and actively secreted from the salivary glands (Qin *et al.*, 2012). Salivary NO_3^- can be converted to NO_2^- , and in some instances, further reduced to NO, by denitrifying oral bacteria (Schreiber *et al.*, 2010; Hyde *et al.*, 2014).

Nitrite and NO generated by oral bacteria have direct benefits for systemic health. Swallowed NO_2^- is converted to NO in the acidic environment of the stomach or absorbed and then stored in the blood and tissues where it forms NO following reaction with haemoglobin and other NO_2^- reductases (Kadach *et al.*, 2023). Additionally, NO_2^- and NO can pass through the oral mucosa to reach the systemic circulation directly (Aerts *et al.*, 1997). In light of this, decreased cardiometabolic disease risk is associated with greater oral NO_2^- -production capacity by subgingival plaque (Goh *et al.*, 2022), suggesting links between NO_2^- production in the mouth and systemic NO availability. The administration of commonly used antimicrobial mouthwashes has been shown to disrupt oral NO_2^- production, with subsequent increases in blood pressure (BP) (Bondonno *et al.*, 2015; Brookes *et al.*, 2020). Collectively, this shows that the enterosalivary NO production is dependent on the actions of commensal oral bacteria.

In addition to the systemic effects of the NO_3^- - NO_2^- -NO pathway, common NO_2^- -producing bacteria and their products are implicated in the maintenance of oral health (reviewed by (Rosier *et al.*, 2022)). Most relevant to periodontitis, the addition of NO_3^- to subgingival biofilm samples from periodontitis patients decreases biofilm growth rates and reduces the subgingival microbial dysbiosis index (SMDI), alongside a reduction in the abundance of periodontitis-associated species (Mazurel *et al.*, 2023). *In-vivo*, patients who consumed NO_3^- -rich lettuce juice – compared with patients receiving placebo NO_3^- -depleted lettuce juice - demonstrated reduced gingival inflammation following professional mechanical plaque removal (PMPR) (Jockel-Schneider *et al.*, 2016, 2021).

These results suggest oral NO_2^- production may have a protective effect against periodontitis. Several mechanisms may contribute to this finding. Certain periodontitis-associated bacteria are sensitive to oxidative stress, so are vulnerable to the antibacterial effects of NO (Backlund *et al.*, 2015). NO is produced by denitrification by some oral bacteria, which may impair pathogen growth. Following supplementation with dietary NO_3^- , *Rothia* and *Neisseria* consistently increase in abundance (Vanhatalo *et al.*, 2018; Burleigh *et al.*, 2019; Jockel-Schneider *et al.*, 2021). A greater abundance of *Rothia* species are associated with limited inflammation during experimental gingivitis (Huang *et al.*, 2021) while *Neisseria* rapidly declines after oral hygiene is halted (Hall *et al.*, 2023) and, when found in greater abundance are associated with improved gingival recovery from experimental gingivitis (Joshi *et al.*, 2014). Finally, an increase in NO availability is likely to benefit other elements of the immune response, for example, by increasing blood flow (Hezel and Weitzberg, 2015) and mucous production (Lanas, 2008) at barrier sites.

Recently, evidence of a lower abundance of NO_2^- -producing bacteria in subgingival plaque and impaired oral NO_3^- -reduction capacity in untreated disease was observed (Rosier *et al.*, 2024). The same study demonstrated that periodontal treatment increases the level of NO_2^- -producing bacteria and restores the NO_3^- reduction capacity of the salivary microbiome to a level comparable to dental health (Rosier *et al.*, 2024). However, this observation was found 90 days after periodontal treatment, allowing the healing of the subgingival tissue and reestablishment of the subgingival community (Darcey and Ashley, 2011) and it currently remains unknown how the NO_2^- -producing microbiota and its activity changes between treatment and day 90. Early changes in health-associated species and functions may be amenable to therapeutic manipulation and may determine clinical outcomes at later stages and this should be explored (Johnston *et al.*, 2023).

The aim of this study was to determine how the NO_2^- -producing subgingival microbiota and its activity change over time, during the reestablishment of subgingival plaque after periodontal treatment (i.e., oral hygiene instruction, PMPR, and subgingival instrumentation). For this, the levels of NO_2^- -producing species in subgingival plaque were determined at baseline (BL) (before treatment) and 1, 7 and 90 days after treatment using 16S rRNA gene data of 38 periodontitis patients. Additionally, saliva samples of these patients were obtained to measure the levels of NO_3^- and NO_2^- and determine the effect of periodontal treatment on the NO_3^- - NO_2^- -NO pathway over time. Finally, the relationship between the NO_2^- -producing microbiota and

periodontitis-associated parameters (i.e., disease-associated bacteria and inflammation) was explored.

3.2 Methods

3.2.1 Ethical Approval

All patients gave written, informed consent prior to enrolment. The study was approved by the NHS Greater Glasgow and Clyde Health Board Research Ethics Committee (REC reference number 18/NI/0059) and the Office for Research Ethics Committee Northern Ireland (ClinicalTrials.gov identifier NCT03501316). All procedures were carried out in accordance with the WMA Declaration of Helsinki.

3.2.2 Participants

The patients were enrolled in the Inflammatory Response After Periodontal Treatment (IRAPT) trial at the University of Glasgow Dental Hospital, investigating the systemic inflammatory response to non-surgical periodontal treatment. The inclusion criteria were: male or female patients aged 18–70 years inclusive with probing depths ≥ 5 mm on two or more teeth at non-adjacent sites with cumulative probing depths of ≥ 40 mm. The exclusion criteria were known or suspected high risk for tuberculosis, or blood borne virus infection; history of bleeding diathesis; pregnancy or lactation; self-reported diagnosis of any systemic illnesses including cardiovascular, renal and liver diseases, and/or regular use of medication to control systemic illness; any pharmacological treatment within 1 month before the beginning of the study, including routine use of any over the counter medications and specialist periodontal treatment in the previous 6 months. In total, 42 patients were recruited, aged 32-65 and 38 followed to completion, as shown in Figure 3-1.

3.2.3 Study Procedures

Figure 3.1 shows a timeline of study procedures. Patients attended a BL appointment and returned at Day-1, Day-7, and Day-90 after completion of subgingival instrumentation (full mouth subgingival instrumentation completed in 24 hours). At BL, patients were provided with detailed oral hygiene instruction, dental health education and full mouth supragingival professional mechanical plaque removal (PMPR; Step 1 of treatment) (Treatment provided according to current guidelines at time of study, Scottish Dental Clinical Effectiveness

Programme, 2014, equivalent to Step 1 and 2 of S3 Guidelines, West *et al.*, 2021), following the relevant treatment guidelines. All the clinical treatment and measurements were carried out by an experienced calibrated dental hygienist or specialist trainee in restorative dentistry (as described Johnston *et al.*, 2020).

Figure 3-1: (A) A schematic of the study timeline, showing the data and sample collection procedures at each time point. Adapted scheme from Johnston et al., 2020; 2023. (B) A description of the novel analysis carried out on the dataset of Johnston et al., 2020; 2023. Created in biorender.com.

Clinical disease indicators (full-mouth plaque, bleeding scores and detailed 6-point periodontal pocket charting) were recorded at BL and Day 90. The periodontally inflamed surface area (PISA) was calculated to quantify local inflammation (Nesse *et al.*, 2008). Third molars were excluded unless anterior molar units were missing. Samples of subgingival plaque and saliva were collected at BL, Day 1, Day 7, and Day 90. Systolic BP (SBP) and diastolic BP (DBP) were recorded at each appointment as a health screening measure, using an automated device. Mean arterial pressure (MAP) was then calculated using the following equation $MAP = (2 \times DBP + SBP) / 3$.

3.2.4 Sample Collection and Processing

Four subgingival plaque samples were collected, one from each quadrant, from sites ≥ 5 mm, at all timepoints, as described previously (Johnston *et al.*, 2023). In brief, the supragingival plaque was initially removed, and subgingival plaque samples were subsequently collected using a sterile curette and transferred to a sterile Eppendorf containing 500 μ l of sterile phosphate buffered saline solution (Sigma Aldrich, Gillingham, UK). Bacterial cells were harvested via non-refrigerated centrifuge (15,000 g for 10 minutes). Saliva was collected with the passive drool method and clarified via centrifuge (14,000 g for 5 minutes). All samples were processed immediately in laboratories adjacent to the Glasgow Dental Hospital Clinical Research Facility and stored at -80°C prior to analysis.

3.2.5 NO₂⁻ analysis

A solution of 2.5ml acetic acid, 0.5ml of deionised water and 25mg sodium iodide was placed into a glass purge vessel heated to 50°C and connected to a NO analyser (Sievers NOA 280i, Analytix, UK). A standardisation curve was constructed by injecting 100 μ L of NO₂⁻ solution to achieve a maximum concentration of 3000 nM. Samples were thawed at 37°C in a water bath before being diluted with deionised water at a ratio of 1:100 prior to injection. The NO₂⁻ content was calculated using the area under the standard curve (AUC).

3.2.6 NO₃⁻ Analysis

Vanadium reagent (24 mg of vanadium tri-chloride and 3 ml of 1M hydrochloric acid) was added to the purge vessel and heated to 90°C . A standard curve was constructed by adding injections of 10 μ L NO₃⁻ solution up to a concentration of 100 μ M. Samples were thawed at

37°C in a water bath before being diluted with deionised water at a ratio of 1:100 prior to injection. The NO₃⁻ content was calculated as described above.

3.2.7 Bacterial 16S rRNA Sequencing

All processing and analysis of the microbiome samples was carried out at the oral microbiome lab of FISABIO (Foundation for the Promotion of Health and Biomedical Research of the Valencian Community), Valencia. DNA was isolated from the plaque samples using the MagNA Pure LC DNA isolation kit (Roche Diagnostics, Mannheim, Germany) and sequenced using an Illumina MiSeq Sequencer as described by Johnston et al. (2023). The sequences were classified into genera and species using the DADA2 pipeline in R and different downstream analyses were performed (e.g., Shannon's index and Chao1 index) as described by Johnston et al. 2023. An ANCOM-BC2 filter was applied to the relative abundance values and analysis of the microbiome was carried out on the transformed dataset unless stated otherwise. During analysis, 2 samples (1 at Day 7 and one at Day 90) had <5000 total reads so were excluded from statistical analysis at these timepoints. Bacteria were grouped as periodontal pathogens (Socransky *et al.*, 1998; Pérez-Chaparro *et al.*, 2014) or as NO₂⁻ producers (Rosier *et al.*, 2022) (Supplementary Tables 3-1 to 3-5).

3.2.8 Statistical Analysis

This is a novel, secondary, exploratory analysis of previously published data (explained in figure 2B) Johnston et al. (2020; 2023) divided their population into patients treated using hand or ultrasonic instrumentation. As no significant differences were detected between treatment modality in the clinical response to treatment, systemic markers of inflammation, in any of the investigated measures of microbiome alpha or beta diversity, or in the relative abundance of any genera or species, all individuals were combined together for analysis. SPSS (Version 29.1.01) and R were used for statistical analysis. Figures were constructed in GraphPad PRISM (Version 10.1.2). Data were assessed for normality using the Shapiro-Wilk test and by examination of boxplots. Non-parametric tests used where appropriate. Where appropriate, outliers out with three times the inter-quartile range were removed from analysis. One-way repeated measures ANOVAs or Friedman's tests were used to detect changes in clinical disease indicators, BP, NO₃, NO₂⁻ and in relative abundance of bacteria between Day 1, Day 7, and Day 90. Post-hoc testing consisting of paired samples t-tests or Wilcoxon signed rank tests with Bonferroni adjustment applied were used to determine differences between timepoints where

indicated. Associations between clinical disease indicator, BP, NO₃⁻, NO₂⁻ and groups of bacteria were assessed with Spearman's rank correlation coefficients. A $p \leq 0.05$ was taken to indicate statistical significance. Unless otherwise stated, values are reported as mean \pm SD.

A post-hoc power calculation to was carried out in G*power (Version 3.1.9.7). The effect size was estimated using the mean and SD of salivary NO₂⁻ at BL and Day 90 and the calculation assessed the probability of a type-II error when testing for a statistically significant difference in salivary NO₂⁻ levels between BL and Day 90 using a Wilcoxon signed-rank test. This calculation estimated the study power to be 0.99 for this statistical test (Calculation 3-1).

Equation 3-1: Post-hoc power calculation for Study 1.

Options:	A.R.E. method		
Analysis:	Post hoc: Compute achieved power		
Input:	Tails	=	One
	Parent distribution	=	Laplace
	Effect size dz	=	0.7006255
	α err prob	=	0.05
	Total sample size	=	36
Output:	Noncentrality parameter δ	=	4.1079286
	Critical t	=	1.6918079
	Df	=	33.3774677
	Power (1-β error probability)	=	0.9912934

3.3 Results

3.3.1 Patient Demographics

BL demographic characteristics of the full cohort of (Johnston *et al.*, 2020) are summarised in Table 3-1. In summary, 45% of patients had generalised stage 4 grade C periodontitis, 42% had generalised stage 3 grade B periodontitis and 13% had generalised stage 3 grade C periodontitis (Papapanou *et al.*, 2018). Statistically significant improvements were observed following treatment for all investigated clinical indicators of periodontitis (Table 3-2). No significant changes were found in any of the recorded BP measurements following treatment (Supplementary Figure 3-1). The FMPS was the only clinical parameter that was also determined at day 7 (Figure 3-1 C), decreasing clearly from BL. However, a small but significant increase in FMPS was found from day 7 to day 90.

Table 3-1: Patient demographics at baseline (N=38)

	Mean	Standard Deviation
Age (years)	44.66	8.65
	Percentage	N
Sex		
Female	19	50
Male	19	50
Smoking Status		
Never	39.5	15
Former	31.6	12
Current	28.9	11
BMI Grouping		
Normal	28.9	11
Overweight	31.6	12
Obese	39.5	15
BP Grouping		
Normal	23.7	9
Pre-high	55.3	21
High	21.2	8
Disease Classification		
Generalised Stage 4 Grade C	45.0	17
Generalised Stage 3 Grade B	42.0	16
Generalised Stage 3 Grade C	13.0	5

Variables presented as Mean (SD) or percentage (N). Data previously published in Johnston et al., 2020; 2023 as subgroups. Data shows total amalgamated population. BMI (Body Mass Index), BP (Blood Pressure). BMI Grouping; Normal 18.5-25, Overweight 25-29.9, Obese 30-39.9. BP Grouping; Normal 90/60 mmHg - 120/80 mmHg, Pre-high 120/80 mmHg - 140/90, High > 140/90 mmHg

Table 3-2: Comparison of clinical indicators of disease severity between baseline and day-90 (N=38)

Variable	Baseline	Day-90	Change in variable (%)	P value
CAL (mm²)	4.14 (3.63,4.95)	3.81 -9.42 (3.10, 4.57)	-9.42 (-2.43, -18.42)	<0.001‡
PISA (mm²)	979.56 (487.91, 1994.77)	134.85 (60.44, 289.30)	-83.01 (-74.24, -91.09)	<0.001‡
Sites with plaque (%)	50.96 (25.00, 65.83)	7.50 (4.05, 13.25)	-80.00 (-63.01, -89.17)	<0.001‡
Sites with Bleeding on Probing (%)	39.23 (21.52, 69.31)	7.78 (3.88, 12.08)	-81.29 (-65.68, -87.53)	<0.001†
Total PPD (mm per site)	26.72 (3.19, 4.32)	2.81 (2.40, 3.28)	-24.72 (-17.39, -30.41)	<0.001‡
Pockets ≥ 5mm (%)	26.73 (20.83, 42.83)	11.44 (3.81,19.82)	-56.05 (-47.02, -79.64)	<0.001‡

Presented as median and interquartile ranges. Data previously published in Johnston et al., 2020; 2023 as subgroups. Data shows total amalgamated population. (†Paired samples t-test, ‡Wilcoxon Signed-Rank test). CAL (Clinical Attachment Loss), PISA (Periodontally Inflamed Surface Area), PPD (Periodontal Pocket Depth).

3.3.2 Salivary NO₃⁻ and NO₂⁻ do not Change Following Periodontal Treatment

To investigate the effects of periodontal treatment and subsequent healing on local and salivary NO₃⁻ and NO₂⁻ levels, changes in the concentration of both molecules were evaluated between study timepoints. At BL NO₃⁻ and NO₂⁻ levels were 641 ± 258 μM and 216 ± 188 μM respectively. On Day-90 salivary NO₃⁻ and NO₂⁻ levels were 630 ± 281 μM and 194 ± 299 μM. No significant differences were observed in salivary NO₃⁻ and NO₂⁻ levels between any investigated timepoints (all *p*>0.05, Figure 3-2 A and B), despite significant changes in the FMPS between BL and Day-1 and BL and Day-7 (Figure 3-2 C). To reduce the risk of data

manipulation bias as a consequence of outlier removal, changes in salivary NO_3^- and NO_2^- levels in the complete dataset (N=38 for all timepoints) were also assessed. While a significant difference was detected between groups in the salivary NO_2^- levels (Friedman statistic=9.316, $p=0.03$), post-hoc testing did not reveal any significant differences between timepoints (all $p \geq 0.135$ after correction for multiple testing). There were also no significant associations detected between FMPS and salivary NO_3^- and NO_2^- levels (Supplementary Figure 3-2).

Figure 3-2: Salivary NO_3^- and NO_2^- in patients with periodontitis before, (BL) and 1-, 7- or 90-days post-treatment. (A) Salivary NO_3^- (N=36 at BL, N=37 at Day-1, N=36 at Day-7, N=37 at Day-90), (B) Salivary NO_2^- (N=36 at BL, N=35 at Day-1, N=36 at Day-7, N=36 at Day-90). (C) Changes in plaque levels assessed by full mouth plaque score (N=38). Data are presented with the top of each bar showing the median and the error bars showing the IQR. Each point represents a patient. Differences between timepoints were assessed Friedman's test with Bonferroni corrected post-hoc testing. * $p < 0.05$ ** $p < 0.01$ *** $p < 0.001$ **** $p < 0.00001$

3.3.3 Saliva NO_3^- and NO_2^- are not Associated with Levels of Inflammation in Periodontitis

To investigate if a decrease in inflammation after periodontal treatment is associated with salivary NO_3^- and NO_2^- levels, Spearman-Rho correlations were performed between salivary NO_3^- and NO_2^- levels and PISA scores at BL and Day-90. No significant associations were detected at any timepoint (all $p > 0.09$, Figure 3-3).

Figure 3-3: Correlations between NO_3^- and NO_2^- in the saliva and periodontal inflammation (PISA). PISA and NO_3^- at baseline ($N=36$). PISA and NO_2^- at baseline ($N=36$). PISA and NO_3^- at Day-90 ($N=37$). PISA and NO_2^- at Day-90 ($N=36$). Correlations were assessed by calculating Spearman-Rho. These correlations were not significant.

3.3.4 The Periodontitis-Associated Microbiome Changes Following Treatment

Historically, periodontitis associated bacteria have been collated into complexes, depending on their association with clinical signs of disease (Socransky *et al.*, 1998). When changes in relative abundance with treatment were examined, there were significant reductions in the relative abundance of Socransky’s red complex between BL and all subsequent timepoints (all $p < 0.02$, Figure 3-4 A). Bacteria of Socransky’s orange complex were also found to decrease in relative abundance between BL and Day-1 ($p=0.001$, Figure 3-4 B). Socransky’s yellow complex consists of early colonising streptococci. The yellow complex increased in relative abundance between BL and all subsequent timepoints (all $p < 0.0001$, Figure 3-4 C). Further advancements in sequencing technology have revealed a greater number of bacterial species to be associated with periodontitis (Pérez-Chaparro *et al.*, 2014). When all species currently known to be associated with periodontitis were collated, there were reductions between BL and all subsequent post-treatment timepoints (all $p < 0.013$, Figure 3-4 D).

Figure 3-4: Changes in the relative abundance of disease associated bacterial complexes in the subgingival plaque of patients with periodontitis before, (BL) and 1, 7 or 90 days post-treatment and associations between periodontitis-associated species and salivary NO_3^- and NO_2^- . (A-C) Changes in relative abundance of Socransky's complexes. (D) Changes in relative abundance of all known periodontitis-associated species. $N=38$ at BL and Day 1 and 37 at Day 7 and Day 90. Data are presented with the top of each bar showing the median and the error bars showing the IQR. Data from all 38 individuals from Johnston et al. (2023) were grouped together. Each data point represents a patient in the study. Differences between timepoints were assessed using Friedman's test with Bonferroni corrected post-hoc testing of compositional data standardized by ANCOM-BC. p -values adjusted for multiple testing are shown. * $p < 0.05$ ** $p < 0.01$ *** $p < 0.001$ **** $p < 0.00001$

To test if the presence of periodontitis-associated bacteria within the subgingival biofilm were impacted by the levels of salivary NO_3^- and NO_2^- , Spearman-Rho correlations were performed between these molecules and the relative abundance of disease-associated bacteria and between NO_2^- -producing bacteria and salivary NO_3^- and NO_2^- levels. No significant associations were detected at any timepoint (data not shown).

3.3.5 The NO_2^- -Producing Microbiome Changes Following Treatment

NO_2^- -producing bacteria are generally associated with dental health. Bacterial species of the oral microbiome which are known to be capable of NO_2^- production have been previously described (Rosier *et al.*, 2022). The overall composition of the NO_2^- producing microbiome at each timepoint is shown in Supplementary Figure 3-3. To investigate the impact of periodontal treatment on the NO_2^- -producing microbiome, changes to the summed abundance of all known NO_2^- producing species was assessed (Figure 3-5). NO_2^- -producing bacteria increased in abundance between BL and all subsequent timepoints (all $p < 0.001$).

Figure 3-5: Changes in the relative abundance of NO_2^- -producing bacteria in the subgingival plaque of patients with periodontitis before, (BL) and 1, 7 or 90 days post-treatment. $N=38$ at BL and Day 1 and 37 at Day 7 and Day 90. Data are presented with the top of each bar showing the median and the error bars showing the IQR. Each data point represents a patient in the study. Differences in relative abundance were assessed using Friedman's test with Bonferroni corrected post-hoc testing of compositional data standardized by ANCOM-BC.

To investigate the relationship between the relative abundance of NO_2^- -producing bacteria and the periodontitis-associated microbiome within subgingival plaque, Spearman-Rho correlations were performed between the relative abundances of both groups of bacteria at each timepoint (Figure 3-6, A-D). An initial moderate negative association at BL ($\rho=-0.596$, $p=0.002$) became progressively stronger as the subgingival biofilm reformed ($\rho=-0.673$, $p<0.001$ at Day-1 and $\rho=-0.687$, $p<0.001$ at Day-7). This negative association was strongest at Day-90 ($\rho=-0.792$, $p<0.001$). NO_2^- -producing bacteria have previously demonstrated an inverse relationship with inflammation in experimental gingivitis. To investigate the impact of differing levels of inflammation in periodontitis on the NO_2^- -producing microbiome we calculated Spearman-Rho correlations between NO_2^- -producing bacteria and PISA. No significant associations were detected at any timepoint. There were also no significant correlations between NO_2^- -producing bacteria and salivary NO_3^- or NO_2^- (data not shown).

Figure 3-6 Associations between the NO_2^- -producing microbiome and periodontitis-associated species at (A) BL, (B) Day 1, (C) Day 7, and (D) Day 90. $N=38$ at BL and Day 1 and 37 at Day 7 and Day 90. $N=38$ at BL and Day 1 (B) and 37 at Day 7 and Day 90. The correlation strength and significance were determined by calculating Spearman-Rho of standardization of compositional data with ANCOM-BC.

3.4 Discussion

To our knowledge, this is the first study to quantify salivary NO_3^- and NO_2^- levels *in vivo* during periodontal healing and include multiple post-treatment timepoints. Although salivary NO_3^- and NO_2^- levels remained unchanged, we demonstrate an increase in NO_2^- -producing bacteria in subgingival plaque 1, 7 and 90 days after treatment. Commensurate with Johnston *et al.*, 2023, we show extensive disruptions to the subgingival biofilm by periodontal treatment decreased the relative abundance of periodontitis-associated bacteria at all post-treatment timepoints. The abundance of NO_2^- -producing species and periodontitis-associated species were found to be negatively associated at all timepoints, with this relationship strongest at Day-90.

3.4.1 The Longitudinal Impact of Periodontal Treatment on the Subgingival Plaque Biofilm

This cohort demonstrated significant improvements in all recorded clinical indicators of periodontitis. Johnston *et al.*, 2023 evaluated the cohort as two separate treatment groups (hand versus ultrasonic instrumentation) and found that the treatment outcome was identical. In our current study, both treatment types were therefore grouped, leading to a cohort of 38 individuals, and new measurements and analyses were performed. Firstly, the change in FMPS demonstrates a dramatic decrease in plaque level at Day-7. This indicates successful removal of the supragingival biofilm and suggests a corresponding improvement in the quantity of dysbiotic subgingival biofilm during treatment. There was a modest increase in FMPS at day 90; however, plaque levels were still far lower than pre-treatment. This means the relative abundance data collected from Day-1 onwards is likely to come from a much smaller quantity of biofilm compared to BL. There was a marked decrease in the oral inflammatory load, as quantified by PISA. This will have further altered the environment of the periodontal pocket, shifting conditions away from those which suit the development of the inflammation-tolerant periodontitis-associated microbiome (Mira, Simon-Soro and Curtis, 2017; Rosier, Marsh and Mira, 2018).

Following treatment and subsequent healing, the subgingival microbiota seen in untreated periodontitis changes to resemble the composition seen in periodontal health (Shi *et al.*, 2015; Chen *et al.*, 2018; Johnston *et al.*, 2021). The formation of this stable community takes time (Li *et al.*, 2023) and recovery of the periodontal tissues post-treatment takes around 12 weeks

(Darcey and Ashley, 2011). We demonstrate changes in the NO₂⁻-producing species, as well as their relationship with the periodontitis-associated microbiota and salivary NO₂⁻ and NO₃⁻, at multiple timepoints during healing.

3.4.2 The Longitudinal Impact of Periodontal Treatment on the NO₂⁻-Producing Microbiome

The increase in NO₂⁻-producing bacteria between BL and Day-90 is in agreement with the results of our recent multicentre study (Rosier *et al.*, 2024). This study revealed the relative abundance of NO₂⁻-producing bacteria was consistently lower in periodontitis compared with periodontal health, in five different cohorts of patients with periodontitis (Rosier *et al.*, 2024). It can thus be concluded that the cluster of NO₂⁻-producing bacteria is a marker of periodontal health that increases after periodontal treatment. The participants of our current study are the second independently recruited cohort of periodontitis patients from Scotland to show a significant increase in NO₂⁻-producing bacteria 90 days post-treatment (Johnston *et al.*, 2021; Rosier *et al.*, 2024). We show a significant increase in NO₂⁻-producing bacteria at Day-1 and Day-7 post-treatment when biofilm reformation is incomplete. Importantly, we show that at all time points there is a significant negative correlation between NO₂⁻-producing species and periodontitis-associated species, which was strongest at Day-90. It should thus be explored if stimulating NO₂⁻-producing bacteria with pre- or probiotic treatments could improve periodontal treatment outcomes and/or delay redevelopment of periodontal inflammation after treatment.

Due to mechanical disruptions within the periodontal pocket, levels of inflammation within the oral cavity are high immediately post-treatment (Morozumi *et al.*, 2018; Johnston *et al.*, 2020). Increased levels of inflammation in experimental gingivitis studies are associated with decreases in levels of *Rothia* (Corrêa *et al.*, 2019; Huang *et al.*, 2021) and *Neisseria* (Joshi *et al.*, 2014). Additionally, representatives of these genera can further reduce NO₂⁻ to NO, which is an antimicrobial molecule. The negative correlation between NO₂⁻-producing bacteria and periodontitis-associated bacteria in our study could in part result from NO production that can kill sensitive bacteria, such as anaerobes associated with periodontitis (Rosier *et al.*, 2022).

Changes in the relative abundance of NO₂⁻-producing bacteria in this cohort at the species level have been previously published (Johnston *et al.*, 2023). Not all species capable of NO₂⁻

production increased in abundance following treatment. At BL, *Fusobacterium nucleatum*, a member of Socransky's orange complex, was the most abundant NO₂⁻-producing species. Interestingly, *F. nucleatum* is periodontitis-associated, which is in contrast with most NO₂⁻-producing species, and has been found to decrease in the presence of NO₃⁻ (Mazurel *et al.*, 2023). The contribution of *F. nucleatum* and other individual NO₂⁻-producing species to NO₂⁻ and NO availability should be tested in future studies. Notably, *F. nucleatum* decreased at all post-treatment timepoints relative to BL (Johnston *et al.*, 2023). This meant that *R. dentocariosa*, which increased in abundance relative to BL at Day-7 and Day-90, was the most abundant NO₂⁻-producing species at all subsequent timepoints. *R. mucilaginosa* also increased in relative abundance at all post-treatment timepoints. Supporting the growth of these species is likely to be of interest in the reduction of residual periodontal inflammation. Both *R. dentocariosa* and *R. mucilaginosa* have previously been proposed as probiotic bacteria, capable of increasing oral NO₃⁻ reduction capacity and supporting oral health (Rosier, Moya-Gonzalvez, *et al.*, 2020). The administration of supplementary NO₃⁻ is a suitable strategy to increase the abundance of these, and other NO₂⁻-producing bacteria within the biofilm (Velmurugan *et al.*, 2016; Vanhatalo *et al.*, 2018; Burleigh *et al.*, 2019; Rosier, Moya-Gonzalvez, *et al.*, 2020; Jockel-Schneider *et al.*, 2021; Rosier *et al.*, 2021), while decreasing the abundance of periodontal pathogens (Vanhatalo *et al.*, 2018; Burleigh *et al.*, 2019; Rosier, Buetas, *et al.*, 2020; Rosier, Moya-Gonzalvez, *et al.*, 2020; Mazurel *et al.*, 2023).

3.4.3 The Longitudinal Impact of Periodontal Treatment on Groups of Bacteria Associated with Periodontal Health and Disease

An increase was observed in Socransky's yellow complex at Day-1, Day-7 and Day-90, compared to BL. Some yellow complex members are capable of NO₂⁻ production (Rosier *et al.*, 2022) and *streptococci* increase in abundance at the genus level on the dorsal surface of the tongue following NO₃⁻ supplementation (Burleigh *et al.*, 2019). While no individual sequences assigned to specific *Streptococcal* species changed in abundance, there was an increase in unclassified *streptococci* between BL and all subsequent timepoints. *Streptococcal* species have a relatively similar 16S rRNA gene (Gao *et al.*, 2014), limiting the number of species which could be classified using Illumina sequencing of part of the 16S rRNA gene. Future studies should determine what species of *Streptococcus* increase using full 16S rRNA gene sequencing or metagenomic approaches. It is feasible that some of these unclassified *streptococci* were capable of NO₂⁻ production. To better understand the nuances within the NO₂⁻

-producing microbiome, future studies should consider the use of higher-resolution microbiome sequencing where feasible, especially at earlier timepoints during biofilm reformation.

3.4.4 Periodontal Treatment Does not Alter Levels of NO₃⁻ and NO₂⁻ in the Saliva

Despite the cohort all suffering from periodontitis, salivary NO₃⁻ and NO₂⁻ levels were similar to those seen among these dentally healthy individuals, in the absence of NO₃⁻ supplementation (Burleigh *et al.*, 2018, 2023). This is in agreement with our previous study, where no significant differences in BL levels of salivary and plasma NO₃⁻ and NO₂⁻ levels were found between health and periodontitis, but differences between the salivary NO₃⁻ reduction capacity were found when incubating saliva with 8 mM NO₃⁻ (a concentration found in saliva after vegetable intake) (Rosier *et al.*, 2024). Moreover, NO₃⁻ reduction capacity was revealed to have improved post-treatment. It could thus mean that differences in the levels of NO₂⁻-producing microbiota found in our study after treatment would result in differences in NO₃⁻ after dietary NO₃⁻ intake. Alternatively, the decrease in plaque levels after treatment could have resulted a higher relative abundance of NO₂⁻-producing bacteria, but not quantity. Finally, it should be noted that while BL levels of NO₃⁻, NO₂⁻ and NO can be comparable between periodontitis and health, the source of these molecules could shift. For example, iNOS expression has been found to be higher in periodontitis (Lappin *et al.*, 2000), while the NO₃⁻-reduction capacity has been found to be higher in health, with both pathways leading to NO production. Future studies should test how the balance between host and microbiota NO production could shift between health and disease.

The use of conventional adjunctive antimicrobial therapies, such as chlorhexidine mouthwashes, could be reconsidered. While these products reduce the overall oral microbial load, they also disturb the commensal oral microbiome (Brookes *et al.*, 2020; Bescos *et al.*, 2020). The effects of conventional antimicrobial therapies on BP control are becoming apparent (Bondonno *et al.*, 2015; Joshipura *et al.*, 2020) and their impacts on the actions of the NO₂⁻-producing oral cavity and subsequent long-term effects on recovery from periodontitis should be investigated.

Periodontitis-associated species and NO₂⁻-producing bacteria were inversely associated with one another at all timepoints. The association was weakest at BL but became progressively

stronger as healing took place and was strongest at Day-90 when levels of periodontal inflammation were lowest. Previously, negative associations have only been reported between NO_3^- -reducing bacteria and periodontal pathogens 90 days after treatment (Rosier *et al.*, 2024).

The negative association between NO_2^- -producing species and periodontitis-associated species at all timepoints may indicate NO_2^- produced by health-associated bacteria opposes the growth of disease-associated bacteria. Some bacterial species found in dental plaque are capable of further reduction of NO_2^- to form NO (Schreiber *et al.*, 2010). Upon reaction with oxygen intermediates NO forms oxidative and nitrosative species. These cause oxidative damage to bacterial cells, including DNA alterations and disturbances to cell membranes and functional proteins (Jones *et al.*, 2010). Furthermore, NO acts as a biofilm dispersal signal (Rosier, Marsh and Mira, 2018), reducing the mass of biofilm accumulation in *in-vitro* models of periodontitis (Mazurel *et al.*, 2023). However, despite the apparent role of NO_2^- -producing species in the support of periodontal health (Jockel-Schneider *et al.*, 2016; 2021, Rosier *et al.*, 2022;2024) and generation of NO, no negative associations were detected between these bacteria and the oral inflammatory load or salivary NO_3^- or NO_2^- levels. It is feasible that the study was underpowered to detect these associations or that behavioural changes to increase salivary NO_3^- or NO_2^- levels (i.e., the consumption of dietary NO_3^-) are needed to initially support the growth and activity of NO_2^- -producing species.

Previous work suggest increases in NO_3^- bioavailability would further enhance the growth of health-associated NO_2^- -producing species and oppose the development of the periodontitis-associated microbiota. Increasing levels of salivary NO_3^- are associated with reductions in periodontitis relevant dysbiosis within the oral microbiome (Chen, Marsh and Al-Hebshi, 2022). *Prevotella* (Vanhatalo *et al.*, 2018; Burleigh *et al.*, 2019) and *Fusobacterium* (Vanhatalo *et al.*, 2021) decrease in the salivary microbiome following NO_3^- supplementation *in-vivo* and concentrations of 5mM NO_3^- decrease the abundance of *Porphyromonas gingivalis* and other periodontitis-associated in an *in vitro* periodontal plaque biofilm model (Mazurel *et al.*, 2023). While side effects such as gastrointestinal disturbances and issues with supplement palatability are reported in a small number of studies (Zoughaib *et al.*, 2024), the consumption of prebiotic NO_3^- , derived from plant-based sources, appears to present an opportunity to safely alter the oral microenvironment (Bowles *et al.*, 2024) and support periodontal health. Therefore, future studies should consider the acceptability of increased consumption of NO_3^- , derived from whole

food or dietary supplements, to investigate possible beneficial changes in the subgingival microbiome during biofilm reformation following treatment of periodontitis.

3.4.5 A Role for Oral NO₂⁻ Production in the Link Between Periodontitis and Cardiovascular Disease

A recent systematic review found links between reduced BP in the months following completion of periodontal treatment in five out of the twelve studies included. The mechanism responsible for longer-term reductions in BP in some cohorts following periodontal treatment remains to be fully elucidated (Muñoz Aguilera *et al.*, 2020). In our study, we may not have found an effect of periodontal treatment on BP as this was an otherwise healthy population, and simple rapid screening hypertension measurements in a dental setting are likely subject to inaccuracies.

Impaired oral NO₂⁻ production and the resulting decrease in systemic NO availability is another factor which may link cardiovascular disease and periodontitis (Rosier *et al.*, 2024). Previous studies show dietary NO₃⁻ supplementation works effectively to reduce BP (Bahadoran *et al.*, 2017; Li *et al.*, 2020). Current research suggests these protective effects would be impaired among hypertensive cohorts with untreated periodontitis and that the recovery in NO₂⁻ production capacity could also have protective effects for hypertension (Rosier *et al.*, 2024). Future research should investigate the effect of NO₃⁻ intake on BP in patients with periodontitis before and after periodontal treatment.

3.4.6 Strengths and Limitations

We used a species-level analysis, which was obtained by Illumina sequencing of part of the 16S rRNA gene, to group species based on their function (NO₂⁻ production) or association with periodontitis. To further improve the resolution of the oral microbiome, full-length sequencing of the 16s rRNA gene or metagenomic approaches should be considered, to increase certainty of the exact species implicated in community-wide microbiome interactions. For instance, this will be useful in determining the role of streptococci in NO₂⁻ production during the early stages of periodontal healing.

Additionally, 16s rRNA sequencing identifies changes in the relative abundance of types of bacteria but does not identify changes in gene expression (Paster *et al.*, 2006). The same species

may fill different functional niches in health compared to disease, so a multi-omics approach, including metatranscriptomics, would have enabled a better understanding of changes in bacterial functions (Kuboniwa *et al.*, 2012).

At BL, the volume of biofilm collected would have been far larger compared to all other timepoints. Changes in relative abundance after treatment may be affected by a decrease in the number of bacterial cells sequenced. To confirm changes in the microbiome, future studies may wish to consider the use of qPCR to establish changes in the quantity of NO₂⁻-producing bacteria at healing sites.

Different areas of the oral cavity house different biofilms (Xu *et al.*, 2015). The subgingival pocket is of most interest in periodontitis, but is a different environment compared to the dorsal surface of the tongue, where the largest quantity of NO₂⁻ producing bacteria are found and where the most effective NO₂⁻ production takes place. However, it is known that species from one habitat can correlate with species from another habitat (for example, *P. gingivalis* levels in subgingival plaque correlate with its levels in saliva) (Jiang *et al.*, 2021), indicating that changes in subgingival plaque will affect other communities to some extent. Nevertheless, the effect of periodontitis and periodontal treatment across multiple oral habitats should be evaluated.

Few studies investigate changes to salivary NO₃⁻ and NO₂⁻ levels. This study effectively assesses these changes and how they relate to local inflammation and the oral microbiome. By including only individuals, who had not recently received antibiotics, we can be confident changes were likely caused by mechanical disruption, not pharmacological intervention or systemic disease. In addition, the exclusion criteria were assigned to limit the impact of the patients' systemic health. This is important as periodontitis is associated with other inflammatory conditions, including cardiovascular disease and diabetes mellitus (Herrera *et al.*, 2023). However, the absence of a formal diabetes diagnosis does not guarantee that all patients were normoglycemic and over half of the cohort were overweight or obese, a factor associated with elevated Haemoglobin A1c (HbA1c) levels, a measure of glycaemic control over the preceding 3 months (Sarnings *et al.*, 2022). Recent studies also demonstrate significant association between periodontitis and HbA1c levels, even in non-diabetic populations, so future studies should consider screening all patients for abnormal HbA1c levels (Zhao *et al.*,

2023). This would both reduce the risk of confounding and identify periodontitis patients who would benefit from medical care (Abdul Aziz *et al.*, 2022).

The study was originally powered to detect a significant difference in serum CRP following periodontal treatment, meaning the sample size was similar to that of other studies examining changes in the oral environment after treatment for periodontitis (Belstrøm *et al.*, 2018; Johnston *et al.*, 2021). While a post-hoc power calculation estimated that the study achieved sufficient power to detect a statistically significant difference in salivary NO₂⁻ levels between BL and Day-90, it is feasible the sample size was still insufficient to detect associations between the composition of the oral microbiome and salivary NO₃⁻ levels. As a result of this, and to enable generalisation of results to other groups of patients receiving treatment, future studies should be specifically designed to test for these changes.

3.5 Conclusions

Our data demonstrate successful treatment of periodontitis results in increases in the relative abundance of NO₂⁻-producing bacteria at Day-1, Day-7 and Day-90 post-treatment, which was accompanied by a decrease in known clusters of periodontitis-associated bacteria. In addition, disease-associated species and NO₂⁻ producing species were negatively associated with each other at all timepoints, with this relationship strongest following healing of the periodontal tissues at Day-90. The role of these NO₂⁻ producing bacteria in oral and systemic health is becoming more apparent and NO₃⁻ has previously demonstrated efficacy as an adjunctive aid in the reduction of reversible gingival inflammation. Such adjuncts may ultimately offer much needed realistic alternatives to systemic and local antimicrobial. Future studies should consider the use of supplementary dietary NO₃⁻ as an adjunctive aid in the treatment of periodontitis, enabling improvements in clinical indicators of disease and reducing the re-establishment of a disease associated, inflamophilic microbiome.

3.6 Supplementary Tables and Figures

3.6.1 Assignment of Bacterial Species to Group

Supplementary Table 3-1: Red Complex Species (from Socransky et al., 1998)

Species	
<i>Porphyromonas gingivalis</i>	Found
<i>Tannerella forsythia</i>	Found
<i>Treponema denticola</i>	Found

Supplementary Table 3-2: Orange Complex Species (from Socransky et al., 1998)

Species	
<i>Prevotella intermedia</i>	Found
<i>Fusobacterium nucleatum</i>	Found
<i>Fusobacterium periodonticum</i>	Found
<i>Prevotella nigrescens</i>	Found
<i>Parvimonas micra</i>	Not found
<i>Campylobacter rectus</i>	Not found
<i>Campylobacter gracilis</i>	Found
<i>Campylobacter showae</i>	Not found
<i>Eubacterium nodatum</i>	Not found
<i>Streptococcus constellatus</i>	Not found

Supplementary Table 3-3: Yellow Complex Species (from Socransky et al., 1998)

Species	
<i>Streptococcus_NA</i>	Found
<i>Streptococcus cristatus</i>	Found
<i>Streptococcus anginosus</i>	Found
<i>Streptococcus gordonii</i>	Not found
<i>Streptococcus mutans</i>	Not found
<i>Streptococcus oralis</i>	Not found
<i>Streptococcus parasanguinis</i>	Found
<i>Streptococcus sobrinus</i>	Not found
<i>Streptococcus salivarius</i>	Not found
<i>Streptococcus sinensis</i>	Not found
<i>Streptococcus massiliensis</i>	Not found
<i>Streptococcus intermedius</i>	Not found
<i>Streptococcus sanguis</i>	Not found
<i>Streptococcus mitis</i>	Not found

Supplementary Table 3-4: Periodontitis-Associated Species (from Socransky et al., 1998 and Pérez-Chaparro et al., 2014)

Species	
<i>Acinetobacter baumannii</i>	Not found
<i>Aggregatibacter actinomycetemcomitans</i>	Not found
<i>Alloprevotella tannerae</i>	Found
<i>Anaeroglobus geminatus</i>	Found
<i>Campylobacter gracilis</i>	Found
<i>Campylobacter rectus</i>	Not found
<i>Campylobacter showae</i>	Not found
<i>Dialister pneumosintes</i>	Not found
<i>Enterococcus faecalis</i>	Not found
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	Not found
<i>Eubacterium brachy</i>	Not found
<i>Eubacterium nodatum</i>	Not found
<i>Eubacterium saphenum</i>	Not found
<i>Filifactor alocis</i>	Found
<i>Fretibacterium fastidiosum</i>	Not found
<i>Fusobacterium nucleatum</i>	Found
<i>Fusobacterium nucleatum subsp. animalis</i>	Not found
<i>Fusobacterium nucleatum subsp. nucleatum</i>	Not found
<i>Fusobacterium nucleatum subsp. polymorphum</i>	Not found
<i>Fusobacterium nucleatum subsp. vicentii</i>	Not found
<i>Fusobacterium periodonticum</i>	Found
<i>Mogibacterium timidum</i>	Found
<i>Parvimonas micra</i>	Not found
<i>Peptostreptococcus stomatis</i>	Found
<i>Porphyromonas endodontalis</i>	Found
<i>Porphyromonas gingivalis</i>	Found
<i>Prevotella denticola</i>	Found
<i>Prevotella intermedia</i>	Found
<i>Prevotella nigrescens</i>	Found

<i>Selenomonas sputigena</i>	Found
<i>Tannerella forsythia</i>	Found
<i>Treponema denticola</i>	Found
<i>Treponema lecithinolyticum</i>	Found
<i>Treponema medium</i>	Found
<i>Treponema vincentii</i>	Found

Supplementary Table 3-5: Nitrite-Producing Species (from Rosier et al., 2022)

Species	
<i>Actinomyces georgiae</i>	Not found
<i>Actinomyces graevenitzi</i>	Found
<i>Actinomyces hongkongensis</i>	Not found
<i>Actinomyces johnsonii</i>	Not found
<i>Actinomyces lingnae</i>	Not found
<i>Actinomyces massiliensis</i>	Found
<i>Actinomyces naeslundii</i>	Found
<i>Actinomyces odontolyticus</i>	Found
<i>Actinomyces oris</i>	Found
<i>Actinomyces viscosus</i>	Not found
<i>Capnocytophaga gingivalis</i>	Found
<i>Capnocytophaga ochracea</i>	Found
<i>Capnocytophaga sputigena</i>	Found
<i>Corynebacterium durum</i>	Found
<i>Corynebacterium matruchotii</i>	Found
<i>Cutibacterium acnes</i>	Not found
<i>Eikenella _corrodens</i>	Found
<i>Fusobacterium nucleatum</i>	Found
<i>Granulicatella adiacens</i>	Not found
<i>Haemophilus parainfluenzae</i>	Found
<i>Haemophilus segnis</i>	Not found
<i>Kingella denitrificans</i>	Not found
<i>Neisseria elongate</i>	Not found
<i>Neisseria flavescens</i>	Not found
<i>Neisseria macacae</i>	Not found
<i>Neisseria mucosa</i>	Not found
<i>Neisseria oralis</i>	Found
<i>Neisseria sicca</i>	Not found
<i>Neisseria subflava</i>	Not found
<i>Paraburkholderia fungorum</i>	Not found

<i>Prevotella melaninogenica</i>	Found
<i>Propionibacterium acnes</i>	Not found
<i>Pseudopropionibacterium propionicum</i>	Found
<i>Rothia aerea</i>	Not found
<i>Rothia dentocariosa</i>	Found
<i>Rothia mucilaginosa</i>	Found
<i>Schaalia odontolytica</i>	Not found
<i>Selenomonas artemidis</i>	Found
<i>Selenomonas flueggei</i>	Not found
<i>Selenomonas noxia</i>	Not found
<i>Streptococcus australis</i>	Not found
<i>Streptococcus infantis</i>	Not found
<i>Streptococcus mitis</i>	Not found
<i>Streptococcus mutans</i>	Not found
<i>Streptococcus oralis</i>	Not found
<i>Streptococcus parasanguinis</i>	Found
<i>Streptococcus salivarius</i>	Not found
<i>Streptococcus sanguinis</i>	Not found
<i>Veillonella atypica</i>	Found
<i>Veillonella dispar</i>	Found
<i>Veillonella parvula</i>	Found
<i>Veillonella tobetsuensis</i>	Found

3.6.2 Participant Blood Pressure at Each Study Timepoint

Supplementary Figure 3-1: *Supplementary Figure 1: BP of patients with periodontitis before, (BL) and 1, 7, or 90-days post-treatment. (A) SBP, (B) DBP, (C) MAP. N=38 at each timepoint. Each point represents a patient. Error bars show mean \pm SD. Differences in BP were assessed using repeated measures ANOVA with Bonferroni corrected post-hoc testing. Data from Johnston et al., 2020.*

3.6.3 Associations between Salivary NO_3^- and NO_2^- and Full Mouth Plaque Score

Supplementary Figure 3-2: Correlations between NO_3^- and NO_2^- and full mouth plaque score (%) at baseline (BL), 7 or 90 days post-treatment. NO_2^- - BL (N=36), Day-7 (N=36), Day-90 (N=36). NO_3^- - BL (N=36), Day-7 (N=36), Day-90 (N=37). The correlation strength and significance were determined by calculating Spearman-Rho of standardization of compositional data with ANCOM-BC. These correlations were not significant.

3.6.4 Relative Abundance of Known NO₂⁻-Producing Species at Each Timepoint

Supplementary Figure 3-3: Mean percentage relative abundance of known NO₂⁻-producing species at each treatment timepoint. The top 15 most abundant species at baseline are shown, with all other species grouped as 'other'.

4. Chapter 4 Eight Weeks of High-Intensity Interval Training Alters the Tongue Microbiome and Impacts NO₃⁻ and NO₂⁻ Levels in Previously Sedentary Men.

Key Points

- Eight weeks of thrice weekly High-Intensity Interval Training (HIIT), increases the concentration of NO₂⁻ in the saliva at rest, altering the oral microenvironment.
- Plasma NO₃⁻ levels increased following HIIT, while NO₂⁻ levels in the plasma and muscle decreased, indicating exercise training impacts on systemic cycling and storage of NO.
- None of the significant changes in NO₃⁻ and NO₂⁻ persisted following 12 weeks of detraining.
- The relative abundance of NO₂⁻-producing *Rothia* and *Prevotella* increased while *Neisseria* and *Veillonella* decreased, alongside changes in the relative abundance of 4 other bacteria at the genus level, post-training. Post-detraining, 9 genera changed in relative abundance relative to post-training. This included increases in the relative abundance of *Neisseria* and *Veillonella* and a decrease in *Rothia*.
- At the species level, the relative abundance of 9 bacteria increased following training, 5 of which have NO₂⁻-producing capacity, including *R. mucilaginosa* and *Streptococcus salivarius*. Following detraining, 6 NO₂⁻-producing species, remained elevated in abundance relative to baseline.

Role of Annabel Simpson in This Study

- Statistical analysis and interpretation of changes in NO₃⁻ and NO₂⁻ levels
- Interpretation of the statistical analysis of the microbiome dataset
- Construction of all tables and figures

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Burleigh, M. HIIT Training in Previously Inactive Males Enhances Oral Nitrate and Nitrite
Levels Without Increasing Dental Caries Risk. *Book of Abstracts, 24th Annual Congress of
the European College of Sport Science, 4th–7th July 2023, Paris – France.*

4.1 Introduction

Impaired NO availability is associated with oxidative stress, inflammation, and endothelial dysfunction (Levine, Punihale and Levine, 2012) and is a consequence of ageing, with effects especially apparent in sedentary individuals (Shannon *et al.*, 2022). The generation of NO can occur endogenously, through the enzymatic breakdown of the amino acid L-arginine by Nitric Oxide Synthase (NOS) enzymes (Bryan and Loscalzo, 2011) and exogenously by the reduction of dietary NO_3^- into NO_2^- by oral NO_2^- -producing bacteria of the enterosalivary NO_3^- - NO_2^- -NO pathway (Rosier *et al.*, 2022).

The enterosalivary pathway is particularly important as mammals lack efficient NO_3^- -reductase enzymes, so rely on bacteria to enhance NO_2^- bioavailability (Lundberg, Weitzberg and Gladwin, 2008). Once formed, NO_2^- is swallowed and converted to NO in the acidic environment of the stomach (Aneman *et al.*, 1996) or absorbed into the circulation (Qin *et al.*, 2012). In the bloodstream, NO_2^- can be reduced to NO through different pathways involving haemoglobin, myoglobin, xanthine oxidoreductase and antioxidants (Lundberg *et al.*, 2008). Multiple sites within the body act as NO_2^- stores, including the blood, heart and liver (Cosby *et al.*, 2003; Bryan *et al.*, 2007; Li *et al.*, 2008; Webb *et al.*, 2008; Carlström *et al.*, 2011). Emerging evidence also suggests circulatory NO_3^- and NO_2^- can be absorbed and stored in skeletal muscle tissues (Wylie *et al.*, 2019; Kadach *et al.*, 2022, 2023).

Most research to date has focused on the benefits of dietary NO_3^- for cardiovascular health and exercise performance (McMahon, Leveritt and Pavey, 2017; Gao *et al.*, 2021; He *et al.*, 2021). It is also known that aerobic exercise can modulate NO_3^- and NO_2^- bioavailability by enhancing endogenous NO synthesis within different cells and tissues, including endothelial (Green *et al.*, 2004), muscle (McConnell *et al.*, 2007) and immune cells (Su, Jen and Chen, 2011). Regardless of duration, length and type, exercise training appears to increase NO_3^- and NO_2^- levels, particularly in the blood (Arefirad *et al.*, 2022). However, data is limited on the impact of exercise on NO_3^- and NO_2^- levels in saliva and skeletal muscle. In rat models, NO_2^- stores in the skeletal muscle are depleted following a period of exercise training, suggesting bioactivation and release of NO_2^- (Majerczak *et al.*, 2024). In human saliva, two studies did not report any increase in these anions after an acute exercise bout (Sone *et al.*, 2019; Thomas *et al.*, 2019), while another study found consistent exercise training significantly increased resting

salivary NO_2^- levels (Amaral *et al.*, 2021). Therefore, the effects of prolonged exercise on NO_3^- and NO_2^- levels in the saliva and muscle in humans remains to be determined.

Despite the awareness of the impact of other lifestyle factors (Chapple *et al.*, 2017; Angarita-Díaz *et al.*, 2022; Cicchinelli *et al.*, 2023), little information exists regarding the effects of exercise on oral health. Reaching definitive conclusions following interpretation of the data that does exist is complicated by the variety of methods used to quantify exercise training and oral health status. However, cross-sectional data from the general population indicates that increased physical activity levels are associated with a decreased risk of dental caries (Sanchez *et al.*, 2020), tooth loss (Inui *et al.*, 2016; Sanchez *et al.*, 2020) and periodontal disease (Cao *et al.*, 2023). In contrast, elite athletes demonstrate poor oral hygiene and high dental disease risk (Needleman *et al.*, 2016; Gallagher *et al.*, 2019). However, conclusions regarding a causal relationship between physical activity and oral health cannot be drawn from cross-sectional studies alone due to confounding variables, such as dental care access and diet (Pourat, Choi and Chen, 2018; White *et al.*, 2020; Watson *et al.*, 2022).

Exercise training is known to influence the gut microbiome composition (Mailing *et al.*, 2019). Initial studies also suggest that athlete groups have an altered oral microbiome composition compared to the general population (Minty *et al.*, 2018; Kalabiska *et al.*, 2023) and that a relationship exists between exogenous NO_2^- production and maximal aerobic exercise capacity (Thomas *et al.*, 2019). However, while sequencing the full length of the 16S rRNA gene allows more accurate comparison of the microbiome (Callahan, McMurdie and Holmes, 2017), to date, only short-read 16S rRNA sequencing has been used (Minty *et al.*, 2018; Kalabiska *et al.*, 2023). In addition, competitive sports training will be accompanied by numerous behavioural changes, so limited conclusions can be drawn from cross-sectional work. Therefore, the impact of exercise training on the oral microbiome, in the absence of confounding variables, has not yet been investigated.

Global health advice is to meet the minimum recommended aerobic exercise guidelines (World Health Organisation, 2020). Therefore, it is prudent to know how exercise training at this intensity impacts the oral cavity and its resident bacteria. The aim of this study was to address gaps in the literature by examining the effects of eight-weeks of HIIT, followed by a twelve-week detraining period, on the composition of the microbiome of the tongue dorsum in healthy

individuals using long-read sequencing. We also investigated the effect of exercise and detraining on NO_3^- and NO_2^- bioavailability in blood, saliva, and skeletal muscle.

4.2 Methods

4.2.1 Ethical Approval

Participants gave written, informed consent prior to enrolment. The ethics documentation provided information regarding all potential risks of all study procedures. All procedures were approved by the local Ethics Committee (ICS Maugeri 2531 CE – 11/02/2021) and conformed to the Declaration of Helsinki.

4.2.2 Participants

Eleven untrained males were recruited. Participants were excluded if they had any history of cardiovascular, neurological, and/or metabolic disease, altered BP, abnormal electrocardiogram (ECG) results, or if they had taken any medication continuously within 12 months. Participants using mouthwash when performing oral hygiene were excluded. Participants were also excluded if they took part in competitive sports events, followed a structured aerobic training plan prior to enrolment or if their $\dot{V}\text{O}_{2\text{peak}}$, defined as their maximal rate of oxygen consumption during a cycle incremental cardiopulmonary exercise (CPX) test, exceeded $45 \text{ ml} \cdot \text{min}^{-1} \cdot \text{kg}^{-1}$, previously assessed as a suitable cut-off to classify individuals as being untrained (De Pauw et al., 2013).

4.2.3 Experimental Design

Eleven participants were recruited from the local community of the area surrounding the University of Pavia. The study recruitment pathway is shown in Figure 5-1A and a schematic of the study protocol is shown in Figure 5-1B. Individuals underwent an 8-week program of HIIT, followed by a 12-week detraining period during which they returned to pre-study levels of physical activity. Measurements were taken at baseline, after training, and after detraining. At each time point, participants visited the laboratory three times, separated by 24–48h. During the first visit, blood, saliva and microbiome samples were collected. On the second visit, a *vastus lateralis* muscle biopsy was performed. Participants were instructed to abstain from strenuous activity for at least 24 hours prior to sample collection (48 hours for the biopsy trial). Prior to oral sampling, participants were instructed to arrive having fasted for 12 hours and to

have abstained from tooth-brushing and interdental cleaning for 24 hours. During the third visit, the CPX test was performed.

A

B

Figure 4-1: (A) A diagram showing A schematic overview of the study design. Created using biorender.com

4.2.4 Incremental Exercise Test

Participants performed a CPX test to voluntary exhaustion on an electronically braked cycle ergometer (LC-6, Monark, Sweden). External power output during step-incremental cycling was increased 10-15 W every minute, depending on the individual's fitness level. Participants were instructed to maintain a constant cadence at their preferred value (between 70 and 85 revolutions per minute). Exhaustion was defined as when participants could no longer maintain their chosen pedalling frequency despite verbal encouragement. During tests, pulmonary

ventilation ($\dot{V}E$), O₂ consumption ($\dot{V}O_2$), and CO₂ output ($\dot{V}CO_2$) were continuously assessed breath-by-breath via a metabolic cart (Vyntus CPX, Vyaire Medical GmbH, Germany). Respiratory exchange ratio (RER) was calculated as $\dot{V}CO_2/\dot{V}O_2$. Gas exchange threshold (GET) was determined by two independent investigators by using the modified “V-slope” method (Beaver, Wasserman and Whipp, 1986). Heart rate (HR) was recorded using an ECG (Vyntus ECG 12-lead, Vyaire Medical GmbH, Germany). Peak power output (W_{peak}) was defined as the highest power output recorded before task failure. Peak values of CPX variables were measured from the highest 20 s mean values before exhaustion.

4.2.5 Training Programme

Training consisted of an 8-week intervention where participants trained independently 3 times per week on a cycle ergometer (Nowa, Diadora, Italy). All sessions comprised a varied number of bouts of HIIT, including shorter (≤ 2 minute) and longer (2-4 minute) intervals at different percentage of power corresponding to gas exchange threshold (W_{GET}), separated by recovering phases lasting 1-4 min. This approach was taken to improve participant’s enjoyment and motivation. Each session lasted between 16 and 36 minutes, amounting to approximately 75 minutes of high-intensity exercise per week. To avoid stagnation, the training stimulus was progressively incremented by increasing the relative exercise intensity and number of repetitions (Granata et al., 2016). During training sessions, participants were monitored using a chest heart rate band (MyZone, England, UK). A session was considered successfully completed when at least 85% of the total exercise time was attained.

4.2.6 Saliva Sampling

Unstimulated samples were collected using a polymer oral swab (Saliva Bio Oral Swab, Salimetrics, Pennsylvania, USA), placed under the tongue for 2 min. Swabs were transferred to collection tubes (Sarstedt, Aktiengesellschaft & Co, Numbrecht, Germany) and centrifuged at 4,000 rpm for 10 min at 4 °C. Samples were separated into two cryovials and stored at -80 °C.

4.2.7 Blood Sampling

Blood samples were collected with patients in a supine position. Venous blood was collected from the antecubital vein into vacutainer tubes containing EDTA (BD vacutainer K2E 7.2 mg,

Plymouth, UK). The vacutainer was centrifuged (Harrier 18/80, Henderson Biomedical, UK) at 4000 rpm for 10 min at 4 °C. Plasma was then separated and frozen at –80 °C.

4.2.8 Tongue Dorsum Sampling

Samples from the dorsal surface of the tongue were collected using a sterile hydraFlock (Puritan HydraFlock Swabs, Puritan Diagnostics LLC, Guilford, Maine, USA), rolled along the posterior surface for one minute with gentle pressure. Tongue dorsum samples were stored in a medium of 150uL of glycerol and 850uL of sterile saline and inverted 10 times prior to freezing at -80°C.

4.2.9 Muscle Sampling

Biopsies were taken from the resting *vastus lateralis* muscle under local anaesthesia (2% lidocaine), using a 130 mm (6”) Weil-Blakesley rongeur (NDB-2, Fehling Instruments, GmbH&Co, Germany). The sample was cleaned of excess blood, fat, and connective tissue in ice-cold biopsy-preserving solution (Doerrier *et al.*, 2018) then rapidly frozen by immersion in liquid nitrogen and stored at -80°C until analysis.

4.2.10 Bacterial 16S rRNA Sequencing

All processing and analysis of the microbiome samples was carried out at the oral microbiome lab of FISABIO, Valencia. DNA was isolated from tongue swabs using the MagNA Pure LC DNA isolation kit (Roche Diagnostics, Mannheim, Germany), following manufacturer’s instructions. SMRT Amplicon sequencing was carried out with a PacBio Sequel II sequencer as previously described (PacBio, California, USA) (Buetas *et al.*, 2024). The DADA2 pipeline in R, was used to construct an exact amplicon sequence variant (ASV) table, which was then compared to the SILVA database.

4.2.11 NO₃⁻ and NO₂⁻ Analysis

Standard curves were constructed by injecting 10 µL solutions of NO₃⁻ and NO₂⁻ (0 µM, 1.9 µM, 3.9 µM, 7.8 µM, 15.6 µM, 31.2 µM, 62.5 µM, 125 µM and 250 µM) into a HPLC system (ENO-30, Eicom, San Diego, USA). Plasma was mixed with an equal volume of methanol and centrifuged (15 minutes at 10,000g. Saliva was diluted by a factor of 10 with carrier solution (containing 10% methanol, 0.15M NaCl/NH₄Cl, and 0.5 g/L 4Na-EDTA). After preparing plasma and saliva samples, 10 µL of each specimen was injected into a high-

performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) system (ENO-30, EICOM, USA). Muscle samples were kept frozen and pulverized at liquid nitrogen (N₂) temperature in a stainless-steel tissue pulveriser (Biospec Products Inc., Bartlesville, OK, USA). The frozen muscle powder was then transferred using a liquid N₂-cooled spatula to a pre-weighed microcentrifuge tube containing 50 µL of ice-methanol with 0.5% of Triton X-100 to help disrupt the cell membranes as previously described (Troutman *et al.*, 2018). After vortexing, the muscle tube was centrifuged for 5 min at 10,000 g and 4 °C. Then, it was placed in ice for 30 min and centrifuged again for 20 min at 10,000 g and 4 °C before injecting 10 µL of supernatant into the HPLC system.

4.2.12 Statistical Analysis

Data was analysed and visualised in GraphPad Prism (Version 10.0.0) and R. Repeated measures one-way ANOVA, with Geisser and Greenhouse correction applied, were used to assess differences in physiological parameters, and NO₃⁻ and NO₂⁻ concentrations. To calculate changes in summed NO₂⁻-producing bacteria between timepoints a non-parametric Friedman's test was used. Where appropriate, these were followed by post-hoc Tukey multiple comparison tests or Wilcoxon signed-rank tests to detect significant differences between timepoints.

For microbial composition analysis, R programming language was used (R Core Team, 2016). To determine differences in microbial diversity, alpha diversity matrices were calculated using the minimum number of reads annotated at the species level in a sample (4900 reads/sample) and compared using Repeated Measures ANOVA and post-hoc testing. Rarefaction curves were calculated using Vegan library in R (Oksanen *et al.*, 2022). Adonis tests (Permutational Multivariate Analysis of Variance Using Distance Matrices) and constrained correspondence analysis (CCA) were used to assess differences in beta diversity (Oksanen *et al.*, 2017). Statistical differences between groups at the genus, species and ASV level were calculated using Analysis of Compositions of Microbiomes with Bias Correction (ANCOM-BC) analysis (Lin and Peddada, 2020) and *p*-values were corrected for multiple testing using the false discovery rate method. Taxons were filtered by abundance (sequence included in the analysis if the average abundance > 0.15% at either of timepoint) and prevalence (sequences were included if the abundance value closest to zero, multiplied by four was present in 70% of samples) when compared between groups.

For association heatmaps, pairwise associations were computed between bacterial sequences and other parameters based on a multivariant approach described by González *et al.*, (2012), which was implemented in the 'mixOmics' R package (Le Cao *et al.*, 2016; Rohart *et al.*, 2017; Johnston *et al.*, 2021). In short, associations between bacterial sequences and other parameters were obtained based on their projection onto a correlation circle plot (Johnston *et al.*, 2021) derived from a principal component analysis. In the association heatmaps, only negative associations below -0.4 and positive associations above 0.4 are shown. To complement the association heatmaps, correlations between genera and species were determined with Spearman's rho, along with associated adjusted *p*-value using the *cor.test* function of stats library of R. To avoid false positive results, only the associations confirmed by Spearman rho correlations were discussed.

A post-hoc power calculation to was carried out in G*power (Version 3.1.9.7). The effect size was estimated by calculating η^2 using the Sum of Squares and Total Sum of Squares from the repeated measures ANOVA used to test for significant differences in salivary NO₂⁻ between timepoints. The post-hoc power calculation estimated the probability of a type-II error when testing for a statistically significant difference in the mean level of salivary NO₂⁻ between timepoints using a repeated measures ANOVA. This calculation estimated the study power to be 0.95 (Calculation 4-1).

Equation 4-1: Post-hoc power calculation for Study 2

Input:	Effect size f	=	0.5865885
	α err prob	=	0.05
	Total sample size	=	11
	Number of groups	=	1
	Number of measurements	=	3
	Corr among rep measures	=	0.5333
	Nonsphericity correction ε	=	0.7
Output:	Noncentrality parameter λ	=	17.0310439
	Critical F	=	4.1545575
	Numerator df	=	1.4000000
	Denominator df	=	14.0000000
	Power (1-β err prob)	=	0.9509076

4.3 Results

4.3.1 Physiological Characteristics of the Cohort

Baseline demographic characteristics of the cohort at baseline are shown in Table 4.1.

Table 4-1: Baseline demographic characteristics of the cohort.

Parameter	
Age (y/o)	25 ± 5
Body Mass (kg)	64 ± 11.2
Height (cm)	171 ± 6
BMI	22.1 ± 3.4

Data shown as mean ± SD. BMI (Body Mass Index).

Significant changes were seen in markers of exercise training status between study timepoints. Repeated measures and one-way ANOVA analysis both related to $\dot{V}O_{2\text{peak}}$ and W_{peak} reported a significant effect of time ($F=20.00$ and $F=30.27$ respectively; both $p<0.001$). HIIT significantly improved $\dot{V}O_{2\text{peak}}$ (from 2.25 ± 0.42 to 2.53 ± 0.52 $\text{l}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$; $p<0.001$) and W_{peak} (from 201 ± 43 to 237 ± 45 W; $p<0.001$). $\dot{V}O_{2\text{peak}}$ and W_{peak} were significantly reduced after detraining and not different compared to baseline (2.26 ± 0.55 $\text{l}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$ and 203 ± 42 W, respectively; both $p>0.933$).

4.3.2 Changes to Microbiome Composition

Sequencing of 33 samples yielded a total of 2189 ASVs, with an average of 24194 reads per sample (ranging from 10047 to 101589 reads) following filtering and trimming. These ASVs were classified into 64 genera and 145 species. Rarefaction curves suggested taxonomic diversity was fully covered, with 4,900 reads per sample (Figure 4-2 A).

Streptococcus, followed by *Prevotella* and *Veillonella* were the most abundant genera at all timepoints (Supplementary Figure 4-1 A). The third generation, full-length 16S rRNA sequencing allowed for robust species-level taxonomic assignment. At the species level, the tongue microbiome at baseline was predominated by an unclassified *Streptococcus* species, *P. melanginogenica*, *P. salivariae*, *Capnocytophagia gingivalis* and *Streptococcus oralis*. Following training, *P. melanginogenica* was the most abundant species, followed by *Streptococcus parasanguinis*, *S. oralis*, *Neisseria subflava* and *S. salivarius*. Following detraining, *P.*

melaninogenica remained the most abundant species, followed by *S. parasanguinis*, *N. subflava*, an unclassified *Veillonella* species and *S. oralis*. The most abundant species at each timepoint are shown in Figure 4-2 B.

No changes in alpha diversity were observed at the genus (Supplementary Figure 4-1 B and C) or species (Supplementary Figure 4-2 A and B) level at any timepoint, regardless of the method of evaluation. However, at the ASV level, the Chao1 index decreased following training ($p=0.04$) and increased between training and detraining (Figure 4-2 C). Altering training status did not significantly alter microbiome beta diversity, as identified using CCA analysis at the genus (Supplementary Figure 4-1 D), species (Supplementary Figure 4-2 C) and ASV level (Figure 4-2 D, all $p>0.08$).

Figure 4-2: Assessing the impact of HIIT on markers of microbiome diversity. Baseline (BL), after training (TR) and after detraining (DTR). $N=11$ at all timepoints. (A) Rarefaction curves for observed species at baseline. (B) Comparing the most abundant bacteria at the species level between timepoints. Bacteria of relative abundance $>1\%$ at each timepoint are shown, with all remaining species categorised as ‘other’. (C) Comparing Shannon and Chao1 indexes at baseline and after training and detraining at the ASV level rarefied to 4900 reads. (D)

Canonical Correspondence Analysis (CCA) comparing the composition of the microbiome at baseline (navy), post-training (purple) and post-detraining (light blue) at the ASV level.

4.3.3 Genus Level Changes

ANCOM-BC analysis was used to detect differences in individual sequence abundance. To ensure the investigated genera and species were those which contributed most to compositional alterations, a further abundance filter (average abundance > 0.15% at either timepoint included in the analysis) was applied. At the genus level, 8 genera significantly changed between baseline and training, including changes to dynamics within the NO₂⁻ producing microbiome, with increases in *Rothia* and *Prevotella* and decreases in *Neisseria* and *Capnocytophaga* (all $p < 0.05$, Figure 4-3 A). Between training and detraining, 9 genera significantly changed in abundance (all $p < 0.04$, Figure 4-3 B). We observed changes in abundance for 19 genera between baseline and detraining (all $p < 0.05$, Supplementary Figure 4-3 A).

4.3.4 Species Level Changes

At the species level, 9 bacteria increased significantly between baseline and training (all $p < 0.03$, Figure 4-3 C). Five of these species, *R. mucilaginosus*, *S. salivarius*, *S. parasanguinis*, *P. salivae* and *P. melanginogenica*, are known to possess NO₂⁻ producing capacity (Rosier *et al.*, 2022). We found 17 species changed in abundance between training and detraining (all $p < 0.05$, Figure 4-3 D). Furthermore, 25 species differed in abundance between baseline and detraining (all $p < 0.05$, Supplementary Figure 4-3 3B).

4.3.5 ASV Level Changes

Between baseline and training, there was an increase in an ASV assigned to halitosis-associated *Solobacterium moorei* (Barrak *et al.*, 2020) ($p = 0.02$, Supplementary Figure 4-3 C). Following detraining (Supplementary Figure 4-3D), this ASV remained elevated compared to baseline ($p = 0.01$, Supplementary Figure 4-3E).

Figure 4-3: Assessing the impact of HIIT on individual bacteria at the genus and species level. Log₂ fold change of all significant genera following (A) HIIT training and (B) detraining. Log₂ fold change of all significant species following (C) HIIT training and (D) detraining. Baseline (BL), after training (TR) and after detraining (DTR). N=11 at all timepoints. Bacteria with an average abundance of > 0.15% during at least one sampling timepoint are shown. Positive values indicate organisms which increased significantly following HIIT training and negative values indicate organisms which decreased significantly following HIIT training. ANCOM-BC was used to identify sequences which significantly changed in abundance between timepoints.

4.3.6 Changes to the Relative Abundance of all Known NO₂⁻-Producing Bacteria

We collated all known NO₂⁻ producing species as previously described to evaluate the impact of exercise on the relative abundance of these bacteria. No significant differences between timepoints were detected (F=5.636, *p*=0.06, Supplementary Figure 4-4).

4.3.7 Changes in NO_3^- and NO_2^-

Salivary NO_3^- concentration did not differ between any of the study timepoints ($F=2.077$, $p=0.17$, Figure 4-4 A). Plasma NO_3^- concentration was different between timepoints ($F=6.686$, $p=0.03$, Figure 4-4 B). Following the HIIT intervention, plasma NO_3^- increased from baseline ($p=0.03$). After detraining, plasma NO_3^- decreased from the post-training timepoint ($p=0.03$), with no significant difference detected compared to baseline levels ($p=0.55$), Figure 4B. There were no significant changes in muscle NO_3^- ($F=0.069$, $p=0.90$, Figure 4-4 C).

Significant differences in NO_2^- concentration were detected in the saliva ($F=11.43$, $p=0.002$, Figure 4D). Post-HIIT, salivary NO_2^- increased significantly relative to baseline ($p=0.02$). After detraining, salivary NO_2^- decreased from the post-training timepoint ($p=0.009$). Salivary NO_2^- then returned to baseline levels following detraining ($p=0.10$), Figure 4-4 D). In the plasma, NO_2^- levels differed significantly between timepoints ($F=7.853$, $p=0.02$, Figure 4-4 E). Following the HIIT intervention, plasma NO_2^- decreased significantly ($p=0.03$). After training, plasma NO_2^- increased relative to post-training ($p=0.008$), returning to baseline levels ($p=0.10$), Figure 4E. Muscle NO_2^- storage was also impacted by the training intervention ($F=11.53$, $p<0.001$, Figure 4-4 F). Following the course of HIIT, muscle NO_2^- decreased relative to baseline ($p=0.002$), before decreasing following the detraining period ($p=0.005$). No significant differences in muscle NO_2^- levels were detected between baseline and detraining ($p=0.95$).

Figure 4-4: Graphs showing changes in NO₃⁻ and NO₂⁻ concentration between study timepoints. Baseline (BL), after training (TR) and after detraining (DTR). N=11 at all timepoints. (A-C) Changes in NO₃⁻ and (D-F) changes in NO₂⁻ as assessed using repeated measures ANOVA followed by Tukey's multiple comparison test. * $p < 0.05$ ** $p < 0.01$ *** $p < 0.001$. Data is presented as the mean \pm SD. Each data point represents a patient in the study.

4.3.8 NO₃⁻ and NO₂⁻ Levels are Associated with the Oral Microbiome

To determine how changes to NO₃⁻ and NO₂⁻ related to exercise-induced alterations to the oral microbiome, associations between NO₃⁻ and NO₂⁻ and the abundance of specific bacteria were assessed. Following correction for multiple testing, no significant correlations were found between NO₃⁻ and NO₂⁻ and the oral microbiome at the genus or species level at any timepoint (all $p > 0.06$, Supplementary Figures 4-5 and 4-6).

At baseline, an ASV assigned to an unclassified species of *Granulicatella* was positively correlated with plasma NO₂⁻ following correction for multiple testing (0.83, $p = 0.04$,

Supplementary Figure 4-7 A). No significant correlations were observed after training (all $p > 0.05$, Supplementary Figure 4-7 B) while 15 correlations following detraining remained significant (all $p < 0.04$, Supplementary Figure 4-7 C).

4.4 Discussion

To our knowledge, this is the first study showing that completing an 8-week programme of HIIT, which meets WHO guidelines for minimal aerobic exercise levels, alters the composition of the microbiome of the tongue dorsum, predominantly increasing the abundance of oral NO₂⁻-producing species. Following a return to habitual activity levels, the relative abundance of several NO₂⁻-producing species remained elevated relative to baseline. We also provide novel data showing how HIIT impacts NO₃⁻ and NO₂⁻ bioavailability in blood, saliva, and muscle and demonstrate that, following a return to baseline activity levels, NO₃⁻ and NO₂⁻ bioavailability appear to return to baseline levels.

4.4.1 HIIT Alters the Abundance of Specific Bacteria on the Tongue Dorsum

As far as we are aware, this is the first study to show that exercise training can modify the abundance of bacteria colonising the tongue. We observed a decrease in the Chao1 alpha diversity index at the ASV level following training. This suggests a reduction in less prevalent bacterial sequences, that does not significantly affect the abundance of more dominant members of the microbiome (Reese and Dunn, 2018). Beta diversity did not change with exercise training status, indicating changes in the oral microenvironment did not destabilise the overall composition of the tongue microbiome. Despite this, individual genera and species differed in abundance between timepoints, with potential implications for dental and systemic health and NO metabolism.

8-weeks of HIIT induced changes at the genus-level in our cohort, with an increase in *Rothia* and *Prevotella*, a decrease in *Neisseria*, and no change to *Veillonella*. These data are supported by a previous study which reported that the relative abundance of *Rothia* was higher and *Neisseria* lower in elite rugby players compared to inactive individuals (Minty *et al.*, 2018). Both *Rothia* and *Neisseria* include facultative anaerobic representatives and grow in the presence of O₂ (Sato-Suzuki *et al.*, 2020) and *Rothia* demonstrates rapid growth under aerobic conditions (Rosier, Moya-Gonzalvez, *et al.*, 2020). Increased O₂ demands during HIIT lead to an increase in the respiratory rate, which can significantly alter the oral environment and impact

the microbial population towards aerobic bacterial species. Previous studies also suggest oral *Rothia* species are sensitive to other changes in substrate availability, with a rapid increase in the relative abundance of *Rothia* previously been demonstrated 4 hours after the administration of a suitable substrate (i.e. a NO₃⁻-rich beetroot supplement) (Rosier *et al.*, 2021).

These microbial changes were associated with an increase in salivary NO₂⁻ levels, suggesting higher abundance and/or bioactivity of NO₂⁻-producing bacteria. Exercise-induced NO synthesis could induce some microbial changes in the oral cavity. It is well-known that exercise stimulates NO synthesis in endothelial and muscle cells (Kapil *et al.*, 2020; Kumar, Coggan and Ferreira, 2022). Then, NO is rapidly oxidised to NO₂⁻ and NO₃⁻, with NO₃⁻ being a more stable and abundant molecule in plasma (Cosby *et al.*, 2003). Some of this NO₃⁻ could be absorbed by the salivary glands and excreted in the oral cavity with saliva, where it can stimulate the growth and activity of NO₃⁻-reducing bacteria, consequently increasing NO₂⁻ bioavailability. Supporting this hypothesis, we observed a significant increase in plasma NO₃⁻ and salivary NO₂⁻ after the training period. However, further research employing NO₃⁻ and NO₂⁻ endogenous tracers is needed to confirm this.

Another potential mechanism by which exercise can modify the oral microbiome is through an increase in lactate synthesis. High-intensity exercise stimulates anaerobic respiration in skeletal muscle, leading to an increase in lactate levels (Torma *et al.*, 2019). This lactate is released into the circulation and a proportion passively diffuses into saliva (Santos *et al.*, 2006; Oliveira *et al.*, 2015). When exercise ends, blood lactate levels gradually decrease as the lactate is removed by oxidation (Hatta, 1990), with a return to baseline observed after approximately an hour (Chatel *et al.*, 2016). Both *Rothia* and *Neisseria* can use lactate as a carbon source, so may benefit from elevated salivary lactate during and after exercise (Hoshino and Araya, 1980; Rosier, Moya-Gonzalvez, *et al.*, 2020). As *Rothia* and *Neisseria* contain representatives with a similar metabolism (i.e., lactate using and denitrifying strains), they may compete for NO₃⁻ and lactate under nutrient-limited conditions (Ghoul and Mitri, 2016; Rosier, Moya-Gonzalvez, *et al.*, 2020). Following detraining, we saw an inverse in the abundances of both genera, indicating a return to post-study activity levels did not support a sustained increase in *Rothia*.

Over half the species which increased in abundance with HIIT have previously demonstrated NO₂⁻-producing capacity (Rosier *et al.*, 2022). Of these species, *R. mucilaginosus* is a confirmed NO₃⁻-reducing species. *S. parasanguinus*, *S. salivarius*, *P. salivae* and *P. melanginogenica* are

likely to contribute to NO_3^- reduction but this has yet to be confirmed as NO_2^- can also be produced by other pathways (e.g., the oxidation of NO or ammonia). When *R. mucilaginosa* is added to *in vitro* oral communities alongside NO_3^- , lactate levels are depleted as a consequence of denitrification and NO_2^- reduction to ammonium (Rosier, Moya-Gonzalvez, *et al.*, 2020), a possible contributing mechanism in regulating salivary pH and reducing oral acidification, reducing the risk of dental caries and erosion. This species may have benefitted from the increases in salivary lactate which are known to occur during and after exercise (Santos *et al.*, 2006; Oliveira *et al.*, 2015). Recent evidence has shown that *V. atypica*, isolated from elite-level runners, is capable of using lactate in the gut (Scheiman *et al.*, 2019). Increasing abundance of these bacteria in the gut resulted in greater exercise performance in mice (Scheiman *et al.*, 2019). Furthermore, *V. atypica* are also present in the oral cavity where they can enhance NO_2^- production (Rosier *et al.*, 2022). While our results indicate oral bacteria capable of lactate metabolism and NO_2^- production may benefit from the environmental conditions seen during exercise training and have a role in the removal of lactate from the saliva, further research is needed to better understand the effects of exercise on the oral microbiome.

In our study, salivary NO_2^- increased following HIIT, along with increases in NO_2^- -producing *R. mucilaginosa*. Another NO_2^- producing bacteria which notably increased was *S. salivarius* which has been proposed as a probiotic for oral health (Masdea *et al.*, 2012; Kaci *et al.*, 2014) and which enhances the systemic response to NO_3^- supplementation (Burleigh *et al.*, 2023). Besides exercise, diet is another important factor that can alter the oral microbiome composition and the abundance of NO_2^- -producing bacteria. From this perspective, recent studies have shown that dietary NO_3^- consumption in form of concentrated beetroot juice increased the abundance of *R. mucilaginosa* and reduced the abundance of *P. melanginogenica*, which was accompanied by an increase in plasma and salivary NO_3^- and NO_2^- (Vanhatalo *et al.*, 2018; Burleigh *et al.*, 2019). The provision of supplementary NO_3^- of a similar dose also demonstrates a significant increase in skeletal muscle levels of NO_3^- and NO_2^- (Piknova *et al.*, 2015; Wylie *et al.*, 2019; Kadach *et al.*, 2022, 2023). Our results indicate that exercise dependant changes occurred in the relative abundance of *R. mucilaginosa*, salivary NO_2^- and plasma NO_3^- , and that these changes were reversed after the detraining period. However, we did not observe any reduction in the relative abundance of *P. melanginogenica*, alongside no significant increase in saliva NO_3^- , plasma NO_2^- or muscle NO_3^- and NO_2^- after exercise, which differs with previous beetroot juice studies (Vanhatalo *et al.*, 2018; Burleigh *et al.*, 2019; Wylie

et al., 2019). This suggests that, while exercise training may modulate the composition of the oral microbiome and NO metabolites at different levels, even with microbiome changes which indicate the presence of an oral microbiome more capable of NO₂⁻ production, the exogenous enterosalivary pathway (diet) was not the main source of NO₂⁻ generation in these participants.

Following detraining, several species which increased following HIIT, including *R. mucilaginosa*, *P. melanginogenica* and *S. salivarius* remained elevated relative to baseline, which may demonstrate prolonged changes in the tongue's microbiome and NO₃⁻ reducing capacity. This could also indicate that these microbial changes are not exercise-dependent, and other factors like diet can have an impact on them.

Anaerobic periodontitis-associated *Alloprevotella* (Pérez-Chaparro *et al.*, 2014) also decreased post-HIIT and at the detraining timepoint, we observed an increase in periodontitis-associated *Eubacterium nodatum*, alongside a decrease in *F. periodonticum*. Following periodontal treatment, increases are seen in the abundance of NO₃⁻-reducing bacteria and in oral NO₃⁻-reducing capacity (ONRC) (Rosier *et al.*, 2024). This finding may further explain lower levels of periodontal disease observed in recreationally active individuals (Ferreira *et al.*, 2019). This observation is currently attributed to greater numbers of 'healthy behaviours' in active individuals (Al-Zahrani, Borawski and Bissada, 2005) and to the immunomodulatory effects of exercise (Staufenbiel *et al.*, 2023).

4.4.2 HIIT Alters NO₃⁻ and NO₂⁻ Levels in Saliva, Plasma and Muscle

A previous study demonstrated an association between individuals with greater aerobic fitness and oral NO₂⁻ production capacity, linking the enterosalivary pathway with training status (Thomas *et al.*, 2019). The same authors found a single exercise bout did not alter salivary NO₃⁻ or NO₂⁻. Following the results of Thomas *et al.*, (2019) and our study, it may be suggested that a sustained period of aerobic exercise training is necessary to alter salivary NO₂⁻ levels. Our finding of increased salivary NO₂⁻ following consistent HIIT is supported by another study by Amaral *et al.*, (2021) who showed an increase in salivary NO₂⁻, following prolonged exercise training. However, the extent to which these changes are due to increased bacterial activity and/or abundance, as well as increased efficiency of the endogenous NOS pathway requires further investigation.

Plasma NO_3^- is higher in trained individuals (Arefirad *et al.*, 2022) and elevated plasma NO_2^- is associated with improved exercise capacity (Rassaf *et al.*, 2007). Increased endogenous NO synthesis with consistent training is proposed as the mechanism behind this finding, as intensive exercise training increases NOS expression (Rudnick *et al.*, 2004; McConell *et al.*, 2007). NO is unstable, so rapidly oxidised by oxyheme-containing proteins such as oxyhemoglobin, with NO_3^- being the ultimate, stable endpoint of this pathway (Cosby *et al.*, 2003). Circulatory NO_2^- appears to exert vasodilatory effects both through its conversion to NO and through independent mechanisms during hypoxia (Pinder *et al.*, 2009). In our protocol, we exposed participants to thrice weekly HIIT sessions which likely caused a reduction in NO_2^- reserves in the plasma.

The exercise training protocol also appears to have impacted on NO_2^- storage within the muscle, resulting in a decrease in muscle NO_2^- once the HIIT period was complete. Recent studies suggest skeletal muscle can act as a reservoir of NO_3^- and NO_2^- (Piknova *et al.*, 2015; Wylie *et al.*, 2019; Kadach *et al.*, 2022, 2023). A recent study in rats revealed eight weeks of endurance training depleted stored NO_2^- , with no corresponding changes to stored NO_3^- , NOS activity or NO_2^- reductase levels (Majerczak *et al.*, 2024). This mirrors our findings in humans and, when taken together suggests that long-term exercise training results in a decrease in NO_2^- stores in skeletal muscle. A possible explanation for these findings was that NO_2^- stored in the muscle was used as a source of NO during intensive training, when the physiological acid-base balance would be disturbed (Majerczak *et al.*, 2008), favouring NO production from NO_2^- reduction (Piknova *et al.*, 2022). We suggest incorporating isotopic techniques in future studies to provide a more detailed investigation of NO_3^- and NO_2^- metabolism.

4.4.3 Strengths and Weaknesses

This is the first study to use long-read sequencing to investigate changes to the oral microbiome with exercise training, providing the highest level of resolution of the microbial community at the species level to date. However, some other weaknesses should be highlighted.

Firstly, this study used a sample of 11 participants, all of whom were young, systemically healthy males, resident in Italy, where this study took place. The decision to recruit an exclusively male cohort was made during the initial planning of the study, which was designed to examine if HIIT evoked epigenetic muscle memory (Pilotto *et al.*, 2024). This makes

generalisation of the results difficult, especially as demographic differences have been observed in previous investigations into the NO_3^- - NO_2^- - NO reduction pathway (Kapil *et al.*, 2018). Despite the small sample size, we were able to observe significant changes in the oral microbiome and $\text{NO}_2^-/\text{NO}_3^-$ levels indicating the powerful effect of exercise training on these physiological parameters. Additionally, a post-hoc power calculation estimated the study power was sufficient to detect a difference in salivary NO_2^- levels between timepoints. However, it is also feasible that, as in the previous study, the sample size was insufficient to detect changes in some of the other parameters, such as microbiome diversity at the species and genus level and salivary NO_3^- levels.

The microbiota from the tongue dorsum was sampled because, despite previously discussed experimental flaws, this site has previously been assessed as the site where the colonies of bacterial with the greatest NO_3^- reduction capacity have been found (Doel *et al.*, 2005). Dental caries and periodontal disease affect the teeth and periodontium respectively (Kilian *et al.*, 2016) future studies should confirm the absence of dental disease through examination and investigate microbiome changes in multiple niches of the mouth.

High levels of inter-individual variation are observed in the oral microbiome (Franzosa *et al.*, 2015; Caselli *et al.*, 2020). This means some of the observed changes could be due to natural fluctuations in the composition of the bacterial community (Liddle *et al.*, 2019). However, a strength of our work is that the repeated measures design enabled intra-participant comparison, using the participants' baseline results as a control. Training studies involve a change from a sedentary lifestyle to regular sustained aerobic exercise. This can be overwhelming for participants, resulting in poor compliance and high attrition rates (Perri *et al.*, 2002). By following our entire cohort to completion, we can be more confident that the observed effects were due to the exercise training stimulus and not as a result of interindividual variation (Poortinga, 2007). In addition, while the participants' diet was standardised in the three days immediately prior to sampling, we cannot discount the influence of changes in habitual diet prior to this on both physiological NO_3^- and NO_2^- levels and on the oral microbiome.

While individual NO_3^- reducing species and NO_2^- levels changed in the saliva, we cannot confirm if the behaviour of the NO_3^- reducing microbiome also changed. The inclusion of an ONRC test would have enabled us to track changes in oral NO_3^- -reducing capacity as aerobic

fitness increased. Future studies should test the ONRC, to confirm if this improves alongside aerobic fitness level.

Despite increasing aerobic activity levels, the HIIT sessions occupied a minority of participants' time. To accurately reflect prevailing oral conditions, samples were collected at rest. In the future, salivary samples should also be collected during training sessions to confirm the impact of inter-activity environmental changes on the oral microbiome. This could enable the identification of optimal points during an exercise training programme when additional preventative strategies could be implemented to best mitigate oral disease risk.

4.5 Conclusion

Completion of 8 weeks of HIIT, which met WHO guidelines for minimal aerobic exercise levels, followed by a 12-week detraining period altered NO_3^- and NO_2^- levels in saliva, plasma and muscle and altered the abundance of multiple genera and species of the microbiome of the tongue dorsum. The species-level changes following HIIT, including increases in *R. mucilaginosa*, *S. salivarius*, *S. parasanguinis*, *P. salivae* and *P. melanginogenica*, were indicative of a microbiome capable of efficient oral NO_2^- production among active members of the population. This may have implications for the maintenance of oral and systemic health due to the role of these bacteria in the generation of bioactive NO from dietary NO_3^- sources.

4.6 Supplementary Tables and Figures

4.6.1 Genus Level Changes Following Training and Detraining

Supplementary Figure 4-1: Assessing the impact of HIIT on markers of microbiome diversity at the genus level. Baseline (BL), after training (TR) and after detraining (DTR). $N=11$ at all timepoints. **A** - Comparing the most abundant bacteria at the genus level between timepoints. Bacteria of relative abundance $>1\%$ at each timepoint are shown, with all remaining genera categorised as 'other'. **B** - Comparing Shannon and **C** - Chao1 indexes at baseline and after training and detraining. **D** - Canonical Correspondence Analysis (CCA) comparing the composition of the microbiome at baseline (green), post-training (blue) and post-detraining (red) at the genus level.

4.6.2 Species Level Changes Following Training and Detraining

Supplementary Figure 4-2: Assessing the impact of HIIT on markers of microbiome diversity at the species level. Baseline (BL), after training (TR) and after detraining (DTR). $N=11$ at all timepoints. Comparing (A) Shannon and (B) Chao1 indexes at baseline and after training and detraining. (C) Canonical Correspondence Analysis (CCA) comparing the composition of the microbiome at baseline (green), post-training (blue) and post-detraining (red) at the species level.

4.6.3 Significant Differences in Individual Bacteria at the Genus, Species and ASV Level Following HIIT and Detraining

Supplementary Figure 4-3: Assessing the impact of HIIT on individual bacteria at the genus, species and ASV level. Log_2 fold change between baseline and detraining for (A) all significant genera and (B) all significant species. Log_2 fold change of all significant ASVs between (C) baseline and training, (D) detraining and training and (E) baseline and detraining. Bacteria with an average abundance of $> 0.15\%$ during at least one sampling timepoint are shown. Positive values indicate organisms which increased significantly following HIIT training and negative values indicate organisms which decreased significantly following HIIT training.

4.6.4 Changes in NO₂⁻-Producing Bacteria Following HIIT and Detraining

Supplementary Figure 4-4: Changes in the relative abundance of all known NO₂⁻-producing species on the dorsal surface of the tongue following training and detraining. Results of Friedman's test of compositional data standardized by ANCOM-BC2 with post-hoc Wilcoxon signed-rank tests is shown. Data are presented with the top of each bar showing the median and the error bars showing the IQR. The error bar extends to the maximum value. Baseline (BL), after training (TR) and after detraining (DTR). N=11 at all timepoints. Each data point represents a patient in the study.

4.6.5 Associations Between NO_3^- and NO_2^- Levels and the Oral Microbiome at the Genus Level

Supplementary Figure 4-5: Heatmap with associations between bacterial genus and the NO_3^- and NO_2^- levels at baseline. This heatmap shows the association between genus abundances after ANCOM-BC transformation and other parameters, which were obtained based on their projection onto a correlation circle plot derived from a principal component analysis. Only negative associations below -0.4 and positive associations above 0.4 between genera are shown. To complement the association heatmaps, correlations between genus and other parameters were determined with Spearman's rho and marked with asterisks on the heatmap (* p -unadjusted < 0.05, ** p -unadjusted < 0.01). Only associations confirmed by Spearman's rho correlations were discussed. This heatmap shows the results at baseline, as no associations supported by significant Spearman's rho correlations were detected at any other timepoint.

4.6.6 Associations Between NO_3^- and NO_2^- Levels and the Oral Microbiome at the Species Level

Supplementary Figure 4-6: Heatmaps with associations between bacterial species and the NO_3^- and NO_2^- levels at A - baseline, B - after training and C - after detraining. This heatmap shows the association between species abundances after ANCOM-BC transformation and other parameters, which were obtained based on their projection onto a correlation circle plot derived from a principal component analysis. Only negative associations below -0.4 and positive associations above 0.4 between species are shown. To complement the association heatmaps, correlations between species and other parameters were determined with Spearman's rho and marked with asterisks on the heatmap (*p-unadjusted < 0.05, **p-unadjusted < 0.01). Only associations confirmed by Spearman's rho correlations were discussed.

4.6.7 Associations Between NO_3^- and NO_2^- Levels and the Oral Microbiome at the ASV Level

Supplementary Figure 4-7: Heatmaps with associations between bacterial ASVs and the NO_3^- and NO_2^- levels at A - baseline, B - after training and C - after detraining. This heatmap shows the association between species abundances after ANCOM-BC transformation and other parameters, which were obtained based on their projection onto a correlation circle plot derived from a principal component analysis. Only negative associations below -0.4 and positive associations above 0.4 between ASVs are shown. To complement the association heatmaps, correlations between species and other parameters were determined with Spearman's rho and marked with asterisks on the heatmap (**p*-adjusted < 0.05, ***p*-adjusted < 0.01). Only associations confirmed by Spearman's rho correlations were discussed.

5. Chapter 5 Competitive Athletes Demonstrate an Increased Relative Abundance of Health-Associated Oral Bacteria When Compared to Controls, a Pilot Study.

Key Points

- A higher concentration of NO_3^- and NO_2^- in the saliva were observed when trained individuals are compared with untrained controls, suggesting exercise training alters the oral microenvironment.
- Significantly higher levels of plasma NO_2^- were observed when trained individuals are compared with untrained controls, indicating increased systemic NO bioavailability.
- The beta diversity of the tongue dorsum microbiome differs significantly when trained individuals are compared with untrained controls.
- Trained individuals had a greater abundance of health-associated *R. mucilaginosa* and unclassified *Gemella* species on the tongue dorsum compared with untrained individuals.
- *R. mucilaginosa* and unclassified *Gemella* species have a strong positive correlation with $\dot{V}\text{O}_{2\text{max}}$ and the time spent exercising, suggesting these species benefit from regular intensive exercise training.
- Training for competitive sports is not associated with any differences in the microbiome of the supragingival dental plaque.

Role of Annabel Simpson in This Study

- Study design
- Participant recruitment
- Exercise testing and clinical sample collection
- Quantification of NO_3^- and NO_2^- levels in saliva and plasma
- Isolation of bacterial DNA from tongue swab samples
- Statistical analysis and interpretation of all clinical and physiological data
- Interpretation of the statistical analysis of the microbiome dataset
- Construction of all tables and figures

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5.1 Background

Individuals who meet minimum recommended levels of physical activity are generally reported to have good oral health (Medapati and Pachava, 2022). However, it is likely these individuals also perform regular oral hygiene and consume a healthy diet (Virtanen *et al.*, 2019; Baskaradoss *et al.*, 2022). These behaviours reduce the risk of imbalance in the oral microbial ecosystem and subsequent development of dental pathologies, including dental caries and periodontal diseases, with prevalence of these conditions among active members of the general population (Inui *et al.*, 2016; Ferreira *et al.*, 2019; Huttunen *et al.*, 2023; Popa *et al.*, 2023).

In contrast, dental disease prevalence is high among elite-level sportspeople (Needleman *et al.*, 2013, 2016; Gallagher *et al.*, 2018; Kragt *et al.*, 2019). The elevated risk has been attributed to lifestyle factors, such as the frequent consumption of simple carbohydrates and suboptimal dental hygiene practices (Minty *et al.*, 2018; Gallagher *et al.*, 2019), as well as physiological factors related to intense and/or long-duration exercise, including elevated salivary lactate levels (Santos *et al.*, 2006; Oliveira *et al.*, 2015) and dehydration (Armstrong, 2021). These factors can decrease the salivary flow rate and pH which may disrupt the oral microbiome (Bescos *et al.*, 2020).

Exercise training induces other physiological adaptations throughout the body (Gibala, Bostad and McCarthy, 2019; Mishica *et al.*, 2023), including increased NOS expression (Green *et al.*, 2004; Su, Jen and Chen, 2011), leading to increased NO bioavailability (Arefirad *et al.*, 2022). This has potential benefits for health as the physiological roles of NO include modulation of vasodilation (Hezel and Weitzberg, 2015), support of oral homeostasis (Rosier *et al.*, 2022) and assisting exercise performance (Gao *et al.*, 2021).

Nitric oxide generation can also occur through the enterosalivary NO_3^- - NO_2^- -NO pathway (Liu *et al.*, 2023). Dietary NO_3^- , derived mainly from plant-based sources, enters the circulation (Lundberg, Weitzberg and Gladwin, 2008) with almost 100% bioavailability (Bartholomew and Hill, 1984). Around 25% of this NO_3^- is then actively secreted into the saliva (Qin *et al.*, 2012) where a proportion is reduced to NO_2^- by commensal NO_2^- -producing bacteria. Specific bacteria, including *R. mucilaginosa*, demonstrate superior NO_2^- -producing capacity compared to other species (Rosier, Moya-Gonzalvez, *et al.*, 2020). Swallowed NO_2^- is either converted to NO in the acidic environment of the stomach (Aneman *et al.*, 1996) or resorbed into the

circulation (Qin *et al.*, 2012). Circulatory NO_2^- can be stored in various tissues, including the blood, heart and liver (Cosby *et al.*, 2003; Bryan *et al.*, 2007; Li *et al.*, 2008; Webb *et al.*, 2008; Carlström *et al.*, 2011) or reduced to NO as required via multiple pathways involving haemoglobin, myoglobin and xanthine oxidoreductase (Lundberg *et al.*, 2008).

Alterations to the NO_2^- -producing microbiome are found when trained groups are compared to untrained controls. *Rothia* was found to be increased in abundance among professional rugby players, alongside an increase in the relative abundance of the genus *Streptococcus* and in caries-associated *Streptococcus mutans* (Gross *et al.*, 2012) and *Streptococcus sobrinus* (Korona-Glowniak *et al.*, 2022) and lactic acid generating *Streptococcus thermophilus* (Oehmcke *et al.*, 2010) at the species level (Minty *et al.*, 2018). *Veillonella*, another genus with NO_2^- -producing capability, was also found in increased abundance among competitive water polo players (Kalabiska *et al.*, 2023). Despite these microbiome changes and the increases in salivary NO_2^- following periods of exercise training (Amaral *et al.*, 2021), only one study has investigated links between oral NO_2^- production capacity and aerobic fitness. Thomas *et al.*, (2019) found a positive association between $\dot{V}\text{O}_{2\text{peak}}$ and oral NO_2^- generation capacity among trained participants, suggesting adaptations in microbiome behaviour in response to regular exercise training.

Previous studies comparing athletes and untrained controls analysed the salivary microbiome (Minty *et al.*, 2018; Kalabiska *et al.*, 2023), providing only an overview of bacterial cells shed from various oral sites (Shaw *et al.*, 2017). In addition, the use of short-read 16s rRNA sequencing limited accurate species-level analysis of microbiome differences (Callahan, McMurdie and Holmes, 2017). This means that further research is needed to determine to what extent aerobic exercise training impacts on the oral microbiome and environment, to determine if these changes alter NO bioavailability, complementing the adaptations already seen in NOS-mediated NO generation or alter dental disease risk.

The aim of this study was to compare the composition of the microbiome of the tongue dorsum and supragingival plaque between individuals who trained for competitive sports and those who failed to meet WHO physical activity guidelines, using PacBio long-read 16S rRNA sequencing. In addition, the effect of long-term differences in activity level on NO_3^- and NO_2^- bioavailability in blood and saliva, on salivary pH and on oral NO_2^- production capacity were also investigated.

5.2 Methods

5.2.1 Ethical Approval

The study was approved by the School of Health and Life Sciences Research Ethics Committee at the University of the West of Scotland (submission number 14970). All procedures were carried out in accordance with the World Medical Association Declaration of Helsinki. All participants gave written informed consent.

5.2.2 Participants

Ten trained and 10 untrained individuals were recruited from the local community via advertisement on social media. Figure 5-1B describes the recruitment of participants and reasons for their exclusion from the final analysis. Inclusion criteria for the trained group were as follows: completion of moderate-vigorous aerobic exercise training which totalled ≥ 6 hours per week for ≥ 6 months prior to enrolment, placing participants in Tier 3 of the Participant Classification Framework proposed by McKay *et al.*, (2021), and completion of exercise training specifically aimed at improving performance in a competitive sporting event for ≥ 6 months. Untrained participants carried out < 1 hour of organized aerobic exercise per week in the 6 weeks leading up to study participation. All participants reported good systemic and oral health, did not smoke or take regular medication, and had not been given antibiotic therapy or used antimicrobial mouthwash within three months of enrolment.

5.2.3 Experimental Design

The study recruitment pathway is shown in Figure 5-1A and a schematic of the study visits is shown in Figure 5-1B. Participants attended the laboratory twice, with at least 72 hours between visits. In the first visit, anthropometric measurements were recorded and an incremental exercise test to exhaustion was completed. Prior to the second lab visit, participants were instructed to refrain from carrying out tooth brushing or any other form of oral hygiene, as well as consuming caffeine or alcohol, for at least 12 hours. They were asked to begin fasting 3 hours before attending the lab. Compliance with fasting instructions was checked verbally. An hour prior to sampling participants were advised to drink 500ml of water. After this, participants did not consume any further liquids until sampling was complete. Samples of

saliva, plasma, dental plaque, and a swab from the tongue dorsum were collected. Plaque and gingivitis indices were collected and an oral NO₂⁻ production capacity test carried out.

Food diaries were filled out in the week prior to sample collection (Appendix 1) and training diaries (Appendix 2) were filled out for the week prior exercise testing.

A

B

Figure 5-1: Shows a schematic of the study's recruitment (A) and data collection procedures (B). Created in Biorender.com.

5.2.4 Incremental Exercise Test

Participants warmed up at a self-selected pace for 10 minutes, then completed a graded exercise test to exhaustion on a motorised treadmill (Woodway, Waukesha, Wisconsin, USA). The incline was set to 1%. The belt speed was increased by 1 km/h each minute until 16 km/h was reached, the incline was then increased by 1% per minute until exhaustion. Heart rate was recorded by telemetry (Polar Electro, Oy, Finland). Expired gas was measured via indirect calorimetry (Jaeger/Vyntus, Vyair Medical, IL, US) and analysed for respiratory variables to enable the calculation of $\dot{V}O_{2max}$. The end criteria for the $\dot{V}O_{2max}$ were the achievement of at least one of the following; a plateau in oxygen uptake (<150 ml/min or <2.1 ml/kg/min) with an increase in work rate, a heart rate within 10 beats \cdot min $^{-1}$ of the age-adjusted theoretical maximum heart rate (220 -age), a respiratory exchange ratio greater than 1.15 or an RPE score >18 .

5.2.5 Saliva Sampling

The resting salivary flow rate was measured using the passive drool technique (Navazesh, Kumar, 2008). In brief, participants sat upright for 5 minutes while refraining from swallowing. Saliva was allowed to drip into a collection container without any external stimulation or active movement. The saliva was then weighed and centrifuged for 10 minutes at 13500 rpm prior to freezing at -80°C .

5.2.6 Blood Pressure and Mean Arterial Pressure

Systolic blood pressure and DBP were measured in triplicate using an automated cuff (Orman M6, Intelli-Sense. Hoofdorp, Netherlands) after the participant had remained supine for at least 30 minutes. The values were then averaged. If measurements $>120/80$ were recorded, the patient was left for 5 minutes, and the blood pressure re-recorded. Mean arterial pressure was then calculated using the equation $\text{MAP} = 2(\text{DPB} + \text{SBP})/3$.

5.2.7 Plaque Sampling

Supragingival plaque samples were collected from the mesiobuccal of tooth 16 and 26 using a sterile curette. Samples were immediately transferred to a sterile Eppendorf containing 500ul of sterile phosphate-buffered saline. Plaque biofilm cells were harvested via non-refrigerated centrifuge (13,500 RPM for 10 minutes) and excess supernatant discarded prior to freezing. Samples from the tongue dorsum were collected using a sterile hydraflock (Puritan HydraFlock

Swabs, Puritan Diagnostics LLC, Guilford, Maine, USA), rolled along the posterior surface for one minute. Tongue dorsum samples were stored in 150 μ L of glycerol and 850 μ L of sterile saline.

5.2.8 Plaque and Gingival Bleeding Indices

Plaque and signs of gingival inflammation (bleeding or swelling) were assessed visually and using a sterile CPITN C probe, moved around the gingival margin (Perfection Plus, Southampton, England). The upper and lower 8s were excluded from analysis. Each tooth was split into four sites (mesial, distal, lingual and buccal). The presence of any dental plaque or bleeding from the gingival margin was recorded at each site and the percentage of total sites with plaque or bleeding were then calculated.

5.2.9 Blood Sampling

A venepuncture needle was inserted into the antecubital vein of the arm. Venous blood was collected into vacutainer tubes containing EDTA (BD vacutainer K2E 7.2 mg, Plymouth, U.K.) and centrifuged at 4000rpm for 10 minutes. The plasma was transferred to an Eppendorf prior to freezing.

5.2.10 Oral NO₂⁻ Production Test

Participants rinsed their mouth with a solution of 80 μ mol sodium NO₃⁻ dissolved in 10mL of ultrapure water, reflection the 10-fold higher salivary NO₃⁻ observed following a NO₃⁻ rich meal. The solution was held in the participants mouth for five minutes before being spat into a clean container. The reduced solution was spun at 13,500 RPM for 5 minutes and stored prior to absolute NO₂⁻ determination.

5.2.11 NO₂⁻ analysis

A solution of 2.5ml acetic acid, 0.5ml of deionised water and 25mg sodium iodide was placed into a glass purge vessel heated to 50°C and connected to a NO analyser (Sievers NOA 280i, Analytix, UK). A standardisation curve was constructed by injecting 100 μ L of NO₂⁻ solution to achieve a maximum concentration of 3000 μ M. Samples were thawed at 37°C in a water bath and 100 μ L of thawed sample was injected into the purge vessel. Saliva and oral NO₂⁻ production test samples were diluted with deionised water at a ratio of 1:100 prior to injection. The NO₂⁻ content of each sample was calculated using the area under the standard curve (AUC).

In addition to absolute quantification, the salivary NO_2^- levels were normalised by dividing the absolute concentration by the salivary flow rate.

5.2.12 NO_3^- Analysis

Vanadium reagent (24mg of vanadium tri-chloride and 3ml of 1M hydrochloric acid) was added to the purge vessel and heated to 90°C . A standard curve was created by injecting $50\mu\text{L}$ NO_3^- solution at concentrations up to $100\mu\text{M}$ into the purge vessel. Plasma samples were de-proteinised by adding and vortexing $100\mu\text{l}$ of sample alongside $200\mu\text{l}$ of solutions of ZnSO_4 and NaOH (both in deionised water at a 1:1 ratio), prior to centrifuging for 5 minutes at 4000 RMP. Saliva and samples were diluted with deionised water at a ratio of 1:100 prior to injection. $50\mu\text{L}$ of sample was injected into the purge vessel and the NO_3^- content was calculated as described above. In addition to absolute quantification, the salivary NO_3^- levels were normalised by dividing the absolute concentration by the salivary flow rate.

5.2.13 pH Analysis

Salivary pH was measured in duplicate using a circular electrode pH-meter (1140 Mettler Toledo, Greisensee, Switzerland). The pH value was recorded after an unchanged pH value was observed for a period of at least 7 seconds. The pH meter was calibrated before analysis and after every 10 samples using buffers with known pH (4.01 and 7.00). The electrode was rinsed with $18\ \Omega$ deionised water between samples.

5.2.14 Dietary Analysis

Total dietary NO_3^- consumption was calculated as the sum of all NO_3^- rich substances consumed during each meal, according to the weight recorded by the participants, multiplied by their estimated average NO_3^- content (Hord *et al.*, 2009; Martin-Leon *et al.*, 2021).

5.2.15 DNA isolation

DNA isolation was carried out according to manufacturer's instructions using the MasterPure Complete DNA and RNA Purification Kit (Epicentre Biotechnologies, Madison, WI, USA). An additional treatment step with 20mg/mL lysozyme was included for all samples (Sigma-Aldrich, St-Louis, MO, USA). The DNA concentration of each sample was checked using the Qubit 1 \times dsDNA HS Assay Kit and a Qubit 3 Fluorometer (both Thermo Scientific, Waltham, Massachusetts, USA), according to manufacturer's instructions. Samples were frozen prior to

sequencing. DNA isolation of the tongue dorsum samples was carried out at the University of the West of Scotland. DNA isolation of the supragingival plaque samples was carried out at the oral microbiome lab of FISABIO, Valencia.

5.2.16 Bacterial 16S rRNA Sequencing

The analysis of the microbiome samples was carried out at the oral microbiome lab of FISABIO, Valencia. SMRT Amplicon sequencing of the 16s rRNA gene was carried out with a PacBio Sequel II sequencer according to manufacturer's instructions (PacBio, California, USA). The DADA2 pipeline in R was used to construct an exact amplicon sequence variant (ASV) table, to be compared to the SILVA database.

5.2.17 Statistical Analysis

Data was analysed in GraphPad PRISM and R. Physiological and exercise data was tested for normality using the Shapiro-Wilk test and by visual examination of box plots. Non-parametric tests were used where appropriate. Differences between groups were analysed using independent samples t-tests, Wilcoxon tests or Fisher's exact tests. Parametric data is displayed as mean \pm SD and non-parametric data is displayed as median (IQR).

For microbial composition analysis, R programming language was used (R Core Team, 2016). Rarefaction curves were calculated using Vegan library (Oksanen *et al.*, 2022). To determine differences in microbial diversity, alpha diversity matrices were calculated using the minimum number of reads annotated at the species level in a sample (4900 reads/sample). Adonis tests (Permutational Multivariate Analysis of Variance Using Distance Matrices) and constrained correspondence analysis (CCA) were used to assess differences in beta diversity (Oksanen *et al.*, 2017). Statistical differences between groups at the genus and species level were calculated using Wilcoxon tests on the relative abundance values following the application of an Analysis of Compositions of Microbiomes with Bias Correction (ANCOM-BC2) filter (Lin and Peddada, 2020). *P*-values were corrected for multiple testing using the false discovery rate method. Taxons were filtered by abundance (sequence included in the analysis if the average abundance $> 0.15\%$) and prevalence (sequences were included if the abundance value closest to zero, multiplied by four was present in 70% of samples) when compared between groups.

Association heatmaps were constructed by computing pairwise associations between bacterial sequences and other parameters based on a multivariate approach described by González *et al.*,

(2012), using the 'mixOmics' R package (Le Cao *et al.*, 2016; Rohart *et al.*, 2017; Johnston *et al.*, 2021). In brief, associations were obtained between bacterial sequences and other parameters by the projection of variables onto a correlation circle plot (Johnston *et al.*, 2021) derived from a principal component analysis. Only negative associations below -0.4 and positive associations above 0.4 are shown on the heatmaps. To compliment these associations, Spearman's rho correlations between bacterial sequences and other parameters were determined, alongside associated adjusted *p*-value using the *cor.test* function of stats library of R. Only the associations confirmed by Spearman rho correlations were discussed to avoid false positive results.

A post-hoc power calculation to was carried out in G*power (Version 3.1.9.7). The effect size was estimated using the mean and SD of salivary NO₂⁻ in the trained and untrained groups. The post-hoc power calculation estimated the probability of a type-II error when testing for a statistically significant difference in salivary NO₂⁻ levels between groups using a Wilcoxon test. This calculation estimated the study power to be 0.88 (Calculation 5-1).

Equation 5-1: Post-hoc power calculation for Study 3

Options:	Lehmann 3 moments method		
Analysis:	Post hoc: Compute achieved power		
Input:	Tail(s)	=	One
	Parent distribution	=	Laplace
	Effect size d	=	1.06268
	α err prob	=	0.05
	Sample size group 1	=	10
	Sample size group 2	=	10
Output:	Noncentrality parameter δ	=	2.9102690
	Critical t	=	1.7011309
	Df	=	28.0000000
	Power (1-β err prob)	=	0.8837535

5.3 Results

5.3.1 Baseline Characteristics

Table 5-1 shows the demographic characteristics of the subjects. The control group were significantly heavier compared to the trained group (body mass, *p*<0.02 and BMI *p*<0.002) and

had significantly higher DBP ($p < 0.0003$). No other significant differences were detected. Table 5-2 shows the dental characteristics of the participants. No significant differences were found between groups, except in salivary flow rate which was lower in the trained group ($p < 0.04$).

Table 5-1: Demographic characteristics of the participants.

Parameter	Trained N=10	Untrained N=10	p-value
Demographic Characteristics			
Female (n)	3	4	
Age (y/o)	30 ± 10	31 ± 7	0.75 [∅]
Body Mass (kg)	63.4 ± 9.6	81.8 ± 20.4	0.02 [∅]
Height (cm)	172 ± 9	172 ± 9	0.10 [∅]
BMI	21.3 (19.7 - 22.9)	25.0 (23.7 - 31.1)	0.003 [∅]
SBP (mm Hg)	116 ± 8	122 ± 13	0.4 [⊗]
DBP (mm Hg)	69 ± 7	83 ± 11	0.0003 [⊗]
MAP (mm Hg)	101 ± 7	109 ± 12	0.09 [⊗]

Data shown as mean ± SD or median (IQR). [∅]Unpaired t-test, [⊗]Fisher's exact test

[⊗]Wilcoxon test. BMI (Body Mass Index), SBP (Systolic Blood Pressure), (DBP) Diastolic Blood Pressure, MAP (Mean Arterial Blood Pressure).

Table 5-2: Dental characteristics of the participants. Data shown as mean \pm SD. [⊗]Unpaired t-test, [⊕]Fisher's exact test [⊗]Wilcoxon test.

Parameter	Trained N=10	Untrained N=10	p-value
Seen Dentist Within 12 Months (%)	60	40	0.66 [⊕]
Interdental Cleaning Aids Used (%)	40	70	>0.99 [⊕]
Plaque Index (%)	61.7 \pm 22.6	67.7 \pm 24.7	0.58 [⊗]
Gingival Index (%)	4.3 \pm 4.2	3.5 \pm 5.1	0.60 [⊗]
Salivary Flow Rate (ml/min)	0.3 \pm 0.2	0.6 \pm 0.4	0.04 [⊗]
Estimated Weekly NO ₃ ⁻ Consumption (mg/kg)	176.7 \pm 91.9	187.6 \pm 98.8	0.81 [⊗]

Data shown as mean \pm SD or median (IQR). Plaque and gingival index measured after abstaining from oral hygiene for at least 12 hours. [⊗]Unpaired t-test, [⊕]Fisher's exact test [⊗]Wilcoxon test.

5.3.2 Participant Training Status

The trained group engaged in significantly more cumulative weekly exercise training (median 484, IQR 382-787 minutes per week) compared to the untrained group (median 12, IQR 0-60 minutes per week). This disparity yielded a statistically significant between-group difference (Wilcoxon rank-sum test, $W=0$, $p<0.0001$), Figure 5-2 A.

The trained group also demonstrated a higher $\dot{V}O_{2max}$ (61.4 ± 8.8 mL/kg/min) compared to the untrained group (38.6 ± 7.8 mL/kg/min). A statistically significant difference of 22.7 mL/kg/min was observed between the groups ($t=6.127$, $p<0.001$, 95% CI 15.0 - 30.5 mL/kg/min), Figure 5-1 B.

Figure 5-2: Comparison of training status and aerobic fitness between trained (TR) and untrained (UTR) participants. (A) Time spent carrying out exercise training in the week before testing[⊗]. (B) Relative $\dot{V}O_{2max}$ [⊗]. Each point represents a participant in the study. $N=10$ for each group. [⊗]Wilcoxon test with data shown as median with IQR, [⊗]Unpaired t-test with data shown as mean \pm SD. **** $p < 0.0001$

5.3.4 Physiological Levels of NO_3^- and NO_2^- , Salivary pH and Oral NO_2^- -Production

No significant difference in plasma NO_3^- concentration was found between groups (Wilcoxon rank-sum test, $W=26$, $p < 0.13$, Figure 5-3 A). Plasma NO_2^- concentration was significantly higher in the trained group ($t=3.439$, $p=0.003$, 95% CI 52.7 - 220.0 nM, Figure 5-3 B).

Significantly higher levels of both salivary NO_3^- (Wilcoxon rank-sum test, $W=12$, $p < 0.02$, Figure 5-3 C) and NO_2^- ($t=2.377$, $p=0.03$, 95% CI 6.27 - 109.6 μ M, Figure 5-3 D) were observed in the trained group. Following correction for the salivary flow rate, these results remained unchanged (Wilcoxon rank-sum test, $W=9$, $p=0.002$ for NO_3^- and unpaired t-test, $t=3.21$, $p=0.005$).

In contrast, no significant differences were detected in the resting salivary pH ($t=0.3128$, $p=0.76$, 95% CI -0.32 - 0.24, Figure 5-3 E) or NO_2^- produced following the administration of a NO_3^- -rich mouth rise ($t=1.597$, $p=0.13$, 95% CI -17.53 - 126.8 μ M, Figure 5-3 F).

Figure 5-3: Differences in the saliva and plasma and differences in weekly NO_3^- consumption between trained (TR) and untrained (UTR) participants. (A) Plasma NO_3^- , (B) Plasma NO_2^- , (C) Salivary NO_3^- , (D) Salivary NO_2^- , (E) Resting salivary pH, (F) NO_2^- produced following administration of a NO_3^- mouth rinse. Each point represents a participant in the study. $N=10$ for each group for salivary values, $N=9$ for the untrained group for plasma values. [⊗]Wilcoxon test with data shown as median with IQR, [⊘]Unpaired t -test with data shown as mean \pm SD. * $p<0.05$, ** $p<0.01$.

5.3.5 Microbiome Results

Sequencing of the 20 samples collected from the tongue dorsum samples yielded a total of 479050 ASVs, with an average of 11182 reads per sample (ranging from 5544 to 18648 reads) following filtering and trimming. These ASVs were classified into 30 genera and 52 species. The samples of supragingival dental plaque collected from the mesiobuccal sites of teeth 16 and 26 were combined for analysis. Sequencing yielded a total of 568023 ASVs, with an average of 14984 reads per sample (ranging from 8319 to 25783 reads) following filtering and trimming. These ASVs were classified into 42 genera and 87 species. Rarefaction curves suggested taxonomic diversity was fully covered, with 4900 reads per sample (Figure 5-4 A and Supplementary Figure 5-1 A).

To evaluate differences in alpha diversity, the dpb (Figure 5-4 B), Shannon (Figure 5-4 C), and Chao1 (Figure 5-4 D) indices were calculated. No significant differences were found between groups in the microbiome of the tongue dorsum (all $p > 0.09$) or supragingival dental plaque (all $p > 0.53$). Significant differences were detected between samples collected from different oral sites. A significantly lower dpb was detected between the tongue and plaque samples collected from trained individuals ($p = 0.04$), indicating the microbiome within the plaque was more homogeneous compared to that of the tongue dorsum. The Shannon index was higher in the supragingival plaque of both groups, indicating decreased domination of the bacterial community by high-abundance species. ($p < 0.04$). The Chao1 index was also significantly higher in the dental plaque ($p < 0.01$), suggesting a higher number of low abundance species in the supragingival plaque.

To investigate if participation in regular exercise training altered the community structure of at either of the sampled sites, beta diversity analysis was conducted to assess dissimilarity in the microbiome composition between the trained and untrained groups using CCA and PERMANOVA.

A significant difference was found between the bacterial community of the tongue dorsum between the trained and untrained groups using CCA and PERMANOVA ($p \leq 0.046$, Figure 5-4 E). No difference was detected in the beta diversity of the supragingival plaque samples ($p \geq 0.57$, Figure 5-4 F). CCA and PERMANOVA were also used to compare microbiome composition between oral sites. The microbiome composition of samples collected from the tongue dorsum and supragingival plaque were significantly different (both $p < 0.001$, Figure 5-

4 G). The most abundance species on the tongue dorsum and dental plaque are shown in Figure 5-4 H and I.

At the genus level, similar differences in alpha diversity and beta were observed. Differences were seen between sites for the dpb (all $p > 0.013$, Supplementary Figure 5-1 B), Shannon (all $p < 0.014$, Supplementary Figure 5-1C), and Chao1 (all $p < 0.03$, Supplementary Figure 5-1 D) indices (all $p < 0.014$). A difference in beta diversity of the tongue dorsum microbiome was detected between the trained and untrained groups (CCA $p = 0.033$, adonis $p = 0.014$, Supplementary Figure 5-1 E), while no difference was detected in the supragingival plaque (CCA $p = 0.86$, adonis $p = 0.88$, Supplementary Figure 5-1 F). At the genus level, the composition of the tongue dorsum and supragingival plaque were also found to be significantly different (both $p < 0.001$, Supplementary Figure 5-1 G).

Streptococcus, followed by *Prevotella* and *Veillonella* were the most abundant genera in both groups on the dorsal surface of the tongue (Supplementary Figure 5-1 H). *Veillonella*, followed by *Capnocytophaga* and *Fusobacterium* predominated in the supragingival plaque (Supplementary Figure 5-1 I). *P. melanginogenica* was the most abundant species on the tongue dorsum in both groups. The next most abundant species in the trained group were unassigned species of *Streptococcus*, *S. parasanguinis*, unassigned *Veillonella* species and *R. mucilaginosa*. In the untrained group, the next most abundant species found on the tongue dorsum were unassigned *Veillonella* species, *V. atypica*, unassigned *Prevotella* species, unassigned *Alloprevotella* species and *H. parainfluenzae* (Figure 5-4 H). In the supragingival plaque, the two most abundant species were *F. nucleatum* and *V. parvula*, followed by *Capnocytophaga granulosa*, *H. parainfluenzae* and *Prevotella loescheii* in the trained group and *C. matruchotii*, *N. subflava* and *C. ochracea* in the untrained group (Figure 5-4 I).

H

I

Figure 5-4: Assessing the impact of long-term intensive aerobic exercise training on the diversity and composition of the oral microbiome. (A) Rarefaction curves for observed species. Differences in (B) dbp index, (C) Shannon index and (D) Chao1 index between trained (TR) and untrained (UTR) participants[⊗] and between the microbiome of the tongue and subgingival plaque in participants of the same training status[∧]. Data shown as median with IQR. Differences in beta-diversity as assessed using canonical correspondence analyses (CCA). € the tongue microbiome of trained and untrained participants, (F) the subgingival plaque microbiome and (G) the combined differences in beta-diversity between microbiome samples of different groups. Overall composition of H - the tongue dorsum microbiome and (I) the supragingival plaque in the trained and untrained groups. All species with relative abundance >1% are shown, with the remaining species described as 'other'. [⊗]Wilcoxon test [∧]Wilcoxon signed-rank test. * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$.

5.3.6 Individual Genus and Species-Level Differences

Wilcoxon tests of ANCOM-BC transformed relative abundance data were used to detect differences in individual sequence abundance. To ensure the investigated genera and species were those which contributed most to the compositional differences seen in the oral microbiome in active individuals, a further abundance filter (the inclusion of only genera and species where the lowest abundance was at least ten times the lowest abundance above zero in >60% of samples) was applied.

Following correction for multiple testing, no significant differences were detected at the genus level in the microbiome of the tongue dorsum (all $p > 0.07$) or in the supragingival plaque (all $p > 0.98$).

Species-level differences were detected in the microbiome of the tongue dorsum between the trained and untrained groups. Following correction for multiple testing, unclassified sequences assigned to the genus *Gemella* (*Gemella_NA*) and *R. mucilaginosa* remained significantly increased in the trained group (both $p < 0.04$, Figure 5-5). In the supra-gingival plaque, no significant differences were detected between groups following correction for multiple testing (all $p > 0.91$).

No significant between-group difference was observed in the summed relative abundance of NO₂⁻-producing species on the tongue dorsum or in the supragingival plaque (all $p > 0.80$, data not shown).

Figure 5-5: Shows significant species-level differences between trained (TR) and untrained (UTR) groups. (A) Relative abundance of *R. mucilaginosa* (B) Relative abundance of *Gemella_NA* $N=10$ for each group. Data shown as median with IQR. Each point represents a participant in the study. Groups compared using a Wilcoxon test, carried out on the ANCOMBC-2 transformed relative abundance values. * $p < 0.05$.

5.3.7 Associations Between the Oral Microbiome and Regular Exercise Training

An apparent relationship was detected between the microbiome of the tongue dorsum and regular exercise training. To further investigate this, associations between the abundance of oral bacteria at the genus and species level, physiological concentrations of NO₃⁻ and NO₂⁻, $\dot{V}O_{2max}$ and the volume of training carried out were assessed by calculating Spearman's correlation coefficients.

Multiple significant associations between $\dot{V}O_{2max}$ and training volume and the tongue dorsum microbiome were detected. At the genus level, *Gemella* ($\rho=0.73$, $p=0.02$), *Porphyromonas* ($\rho=0.68$, $p=0.03$), *Rothia* ($\rho=0.65$, $p=0.03$) and *Streptococcus* ($\rho=0.62$, $p=0.03$) were all positively associated with the $\dot{V}O_{2max}$ (Figure 5-6 A). At the species level, positive associations

were detected between the $\dot{V}O_{2\max}$ and the relative abundance of *Gemella_NA* ($\rho=0.79$, $p=0.002$), *R. mucilaginosa* ($\rho=0.68$, $p=0.02$), unclassified *Porphyromonas* species ($\rho=0.62$, $p=0.03$), *S. salivarius* ($\rho=0.60$, $p=0.03$), *S. parasanguinis* ($\rho=0.60$, $p=0.04$), unclassified *Granulicatella* species ($\rho=0.59$, $p=0.04$) and unclassified *Streptococcus* species ($\rho=0.57$, $p=0.04$), as shown in Figure 5-6 B. An increased volume of exercise training was also positively associated with the relative abundance of *Gemella_NA* ($\rho=0.66$, $p=0.02$), *R. mucilaginosa* ($\rho=0.63$, $p=0.03$), unclassified *Granulicatella* species ($\rho=0.60$, $p=0.04$), *S. salivarius* ($\rho=0.57$, $p=0.04$) and *S. parasanguinis* ($\rho=0.55$, $p=0.04$).

Three positive associations were detected between bacterial species found on the tongue dorsum and plasma NO_2^- . These were between *Gemella_NA* ($\rho=0.69$, $p=0.001$), *S. salivarius* ($\rho=0.67$, $p=0.03$) and *S. parasanguinis* ($\rho=0.67$, $p=0.05$). Significant associations were also detected between salivary NO_2^- and the genus *Peptostreptococcus* ($\rho=-0.57$, $p=0.05$) and salivary NO_2^- and the species *Peptostreptococcus stomatitis* ($\rho=-0.62$, $p=0.03$).

No significant associations were found with the supragingival plaque microbiome (all $p>0.09$ at the genus level, Supplementary Figure 5.2A and $p>0.06$ at the species level, Supplementary Figure 5.2B).

The genus *Rothia* has been associated with participation in exercise training in previous studies (Minty *et al.*, 2018, Simpson *et al.*, 2024), while *Gemella_NA* and *R. mucilaginosa* were both increased in abundance in the tongue microbiome of the trained group. The strong positive association between $\dot{V}O_{2\max}$ and the relative abundance of each of these bacterial sequences is shown in Figure 5-6 C-E.

A

B

Figure 5-6: Shows associations between the composition of the tongue dorsum microbiome, NO_3^- and NO_2^- levels and the aerobic training status of all participants. Heatmaps with associations between markers of exercise training status, NO_3^- and NO_2^- levels, salivary pH and oral NO_2^- production levels and bacterial abundance at the genus (A) and species (B) These heatmaps show the association between bacterial abundances after ANCOM-BC transformation and other parameters, which were obtained based on their projection onto a correlation circle plot derived from a principal component analysis. Only negative associations below -0.4 and positive associations above 0.4 between species are shown. To complement the association heatmaps, correlations between species and other parameters were determined with Spearman's rho and marked with asterisks on the heatmap (* *p*-adjusted <0.05, ** *p*-adjusted <0.01). Scatterplots showing the $\dot{V}\text{O}_{2\text{max}}$ and ANCOM-BC2 transformed relative abundance of (C) *Rothia*, (D) *R.mucilaginosa* and € *Gemella*_NA.

5.4 Discussion

In our exploratory study, we are the first to use long-read 16S rRNA sequencing to examine differences in the oral microbiome of highly trained individuals compared to inactive controls at the species level. We did not detect differences between groups in the supragingival dental plaque microbiome, which suggests no link between consistent exercise training and the dental disease-associated microbiome at this site. Our data did suggest that the composition of the tongue microbiome of individuals who were engaged in consistent intensive exercise training for at least 6 months was significantly different to that of untrained individuals. This was accompanied by a higher relative abundance of NO_3^- -reducing *R. mucilaginosa* and unclassified sequences, assigned to the health-associated genus *Gemella*, among trained individuals. Furthermore, NO_3^- and NO_2^- bioavailability was significantly higher in the saliva of trained individuals, as were NO_2^- levels in the plasma. Despite this, no changes were detected in salivary pH or oral NO_2^- -production capacity. While our findings suggest differences in the oral microenvironment and microbiome composition between highly trained individuals compared to inactive controls, it is unclear if this relates only to exercise training or if these differences result from other host behaviours. Importantly, these results should be confirmed in future studies which include larger populations.

5.4.1 Salivary and Plasma NO₃⁻ and NO₂⁻ are Higher in Trained Participants.

Plasma NO₂⁻ was significantly higher in our trained group than in the untrained group. This finding was not unexpected as previous studies associate elevated plasma NO₂⁻ with improved exercise performance (Rassaf *et al.*, 2007) and demonstrate that regular aerobic exercise increases NO metabolite levels (Arefirad *et al.*, 2022). This will be partially due to elevated NOS expression, which in turn increases endogenous NO synthesis (Rudnick *et al.*, 2004; McConell *et al.*, 2007). This is relevant for sports performance as NO aids in regulation of blood flow (Bryan *et al.*, 2008; Kapil *et al.*, 2020) and muscle contraction (Kumar, Coggan and Ferreira, 2022) and increasing NO₂⁻ via NO₃⁻ supplementation has been shown to improve performance (Senefeld *et al.*, 2020).

We are only aware of two studies assessing the impact of chronic exercise training on NO₃⁻ and/or NO₂⁻ levels in saliva. In agreement with our results, salivary NO₂⁻ was found to increase following 10 weeks of combined aerobic and resistance exercise (Amaral *et al.*, 2021) and after 8 weeks of high-intensity interval training when compared to baseline levels in the previous chapter. The elevated salivary NO₃⁻ in the trained group can be contrasted with the previous thesis chapter, where salivary NO₃⁻ was unchanged following periods of training and detraining in previously sedentary males. It is feasible that a higher volume of regular exercise is required to influence levels of salivary NO₃⁻ compared to NO₂⁻ as the maximum time these individuals spent training was 75 minutes per week, which was far exceeded by all members of the trained group in this study. These increases in NO₃⁻ and NO₂⁻ levels in the saliva are also likely to impact the oral microbiome, potentially benefitting NO₃⁻-reducing species like *R. mucilaginosa*, which reduces both NO₃⁻ and NO₂⁻ (Rosier, Moya-Gonzalvez, *et al.*, 2020; Moran *et al.*, 2024). However, while no significant difference was detected in weekly NO₃⁻ consumption, this measurement was an estimate only and relied on the participants to accurately assess and record food intake. While it was requested that the participants weigh foods to enable precise nitrate quantification where possible, most did not prepare all their own meals as part of their habitual diet. This makes making an under- or over-estimation of NO₃⁻ consumption a possibility, which may have impacted on NO₃⁻ and NO₂⁻ levels.

Several studies have investigated changes in NO metabolites in saliva following an acute exercise bout. While Thomas *et al.*, (2019) found no impacts on either ion, another study detected an increase in salivary NO₂⁻ (Souza *et al.*, 2019) and another suggested the completion of exercise prevented a decrease in salivary NO₃⁻ compared an equivalent time period of rest

(Sone *et al.*, 2019). These post-exercise changes to levels of NO metabolites in the saliva are also likely to impact on the oral microbiome.

5.4.2 Volume of Exercise Training is Not Associated with Oral NO₂⁻ Production Capacity or Salivary pH

The saliva samples were collected while participants were at rest, and we detected no pH differences between groups. The salivary pH is sometimes reported to decrease post-exercise (Thomas *et al.*, 2019), albeit not in all studies (Ligtenberg *et al.*, 2015). These pH changes, alongside the dehydration and increases in salivary lactate attributed to exercise training may contribute to the increased risk of dental diseases seen in elite-athlete cohorts (Schulze and Busse, 2024). While athlete groups are advised to consume a balanced diet rich in high-quality proteins, vitamins and minerals, which are associated with oral health in the general population (Najeeb *et al.*, 2016; Gondivkar *et al.*, 2019) they are also advised to use carbohydrate-rich substances to support performance, which will impact on the oral environment and may increase dental disease risk (Valenzuela *et al.*, 2021).

We also did not see elevated oral NO₂⁻ production capacity in trained participants, in contrast with the positive association between NO₂⁻ production and $\dot{V}O_{2\text{peak}}$ detected by Thomas *et al.*, (2019). The conflicting results may be explained by differences in study design. Thomas *et al.*, (2019) administered their NO₃⁻ mouth rinse immediately after the completion of a maximal exercise test, during which the salivary lactate levels were elevated relative to rest (Santos *et al.*, 2006; Oliveira *et al.*, 2015; Thomas *et al.*, 2019). Certain NO₂⁻-producing species, including *R. mucilaginosa* can utilise lactate as a carbon source while carrying out NO₃⁻ reduction (Hoshino and Araya, 1980; Rosier, Moya-Gonzalvez, et al., 2020). Therefore, these species may only display elevated NO₂⁻ production capacity immediately post-exercise. As a higher relative abundance of *R. mucilaginosa* was found on the tongue dorsum of the trained group, it is plausible that individuals who regularly engage in intensive aerobic exercise will display a greater oral NO₂⁻ production capacity only when salivary lactate levels are increased, explaining the lack of a significant difference in the results of the oral NO₂⁻ production capacity test carried out in this study. Additionally, oral bacteria can carry out all stages of denitrification and dissimilatory nitrite reduction (reviewed by Rosier *et al.*, 2022) it is also feasible that a portion of the generated NO₂⁻ was more efficiently metabolised further by the oral microbiome

of the athletes, to form NO or NH₄⁺, substances undetected by the analysis methods of this study.

Higher salivary NO₃⁻ levels and greater oral NO₃⁻ reduction capacity have previously been associated with reduced dental caries experience (Doel *et al.*, 2004), and dietary NO₃⁻ supplementation demonstrates protective effects against salivary acidification following carbohydrate consumption (Burleigh *et al.*, 2020; Rosier *et al.*, 2021). These results suggest an increase in salivary NO₃⁻, may have protective effects against the development of dental caries and erosion. However, while a between-group difference in salivary NO₃⁻ was observed between the trained and untrained individuals, this was of a smaller magnitude compared to that observed following a dietary intervention (see Burleigh *et al.*, 2018, 2020; Vanhatalo *et al.*, 2018). Thus, the impact of the changes to salivary NO metabolites associated with exercise training on salivary buffering requires further investigation.

5.4.3 Exercise Training Significantly Alters the Oral Microbiome

There were no significant differences in the summed relative abundance of NO₂⁻-producing microbiome (i.e., species that can produce NO₂⁻ in the presence of NO₃⁻) or of confirmed NO₃⁻-reducing species (i.e., species that have been confirmed to reduce NO₃⁻ by physiological measurements of NO₃⁻) (Rosier *et al.*, 2022). While an increase in NO₃⁻ and NO₂⁻ bioavailability in saliva was observed in the trained individuals, NO₂⁻-producing bacteria must still compete for their required substrate (e.g., lactate). This suggests that the successful growth of one species, such as *R. mucilaginosa* may inhibit the growth of others and may explain why no differences were observed when bacteria were analysed collectively. In a previous exploratory study, *Rothia* increased 4 hours after NO₃⁻-rich beetroot supplement intake (Rosier *et al.*, 2021), indicating that the fluctuations in species of this genus are dynamic and can happen quickly after substrate administration.

Diversity analysis demonstrated a significant difference in microbiome composition of the tongue dorsum microbiome between the trained and untrained groups. Two previous studies demonstrate similar findings in saliva (Minty *et al.*, 2018; Kalabiska *et al.*, 2023). This suggests the environmental alterations induced by regular intensive exercise training are sufficient to induce changes in oral microbiome composition or that other behaviours carried out by athletes influence the composition of the oral microbiome. Conversely, in the previous chapter, the

completion of 75 minutes of high-intensity interval training per week for eight weeks did not change the overall composition of the tongue dorsum biofilm, relative to remaining sedentary. This suggests that high volumes of intensive exercise training are necessary to modulate the overall composition of the oral microbiome. Alternatively, the microbiome composition may have been affected by between-group differences in the BMI (Wu *et al.*, 2018; Ma *et al.*, 2023) or diet (Angarita-Díaz *et al.*, 2022; Cato *et al.*, 2023). However, the correlation between *R. mucilaginosa* and unclassified *Gemella* species and $\dot{V}O_{2\max}$ in our study indicates that the relationship between exercise training and the tongue microbiota warrants further investigation in larger study populations.

We found no evidence that the completion of a high volume of exercise training increased the relative abundance of bacterial species associated with disease within the supragingival plaque, where an increased abundance of caries-associated species is most likely to be clinically relevant. These findings can be contrasted with the clinical (Needleman *et al.*, 2016; Gallagher *et al.*, 2018; Minty *et al.*, 2018; Kragt *et al.*, 2019) and microbiological findings (Minty *et al.*, 2018) of previous studies of elite-level athletes and suggest that training to compete at the sub-elite level does not result in changes to the supragingival plaque microbiome that could influence dental caries risk. However, due to our small study population, it is possible that the interindividual variation was not large enough to be detected, meaning this result should be confirmed in future studies. Additionally, all individuals indicated they habitually brushed their teeth at least twice per day, contrasting with the tongue microbiota which could have more time to accumulate, being affected by weekly habits. In future studies, individuals could be informed to abstain from oral hygiene for a short period to see if exercise should affect the accumulated plaque community.

The relative abundance of two taxa at the species level were found to be higher on the tongue dorsum of the trained group compared to the untrained controls. These were unclassified *Gemella* species and *R. mucilaginosa*. *Gemella* are core members of the health-associated human oral microbiome (Dewhirst., 2010; Torres-Morales *et al.*, 2023). Furthermore, *Gemella* is periodontal-health associated (Feres *et al.*, 2021) and some *Gemella* species are capable of inhibiting the growth of periodontitis-associated bacteria (e.g., *P. gingivalis*) *in-vitro* (Miyoshi *et al.*, 2021). *R. mucilaginosa* demonstrates effective NO_3^- -reducing capacity and has been proposed as a probiotic species to increase NO availability to improve host health (Rosier, Moya-Gonzalvez, *et al.*, 2020). It was also one of five NO_2^- -producing bacteria seen to increase

in relative abundance following consistent exercise training in the previous chapter. At the genus level, *Rothia* was also found to be increased in abundance in the saliva of professional rugby players (Minty *et al.*, 2018). These results suggest that regular exercise training may result in environmental conditions amenable to the growth of *Rothia* species, especially *R. mucilaginosa*, the human *Rothia* species that is most abundant on the tongue (i.e., tongue tropism) (Wilbert, Welch and Borisy, 2020), and that this species may be a marker of aerobic fitness. It should be noted that *R. mucilaginosa* is a commensal species associated with the absence of halitosis when detected on the tongue (Carda-Diéguez *et al.*, 2022) and periodontal health when detected in subgingival plaque (Feres *et al.*, 2021). An increase in this bacterium is thus clearly beneficial for the human host.

5.4.4 Correlations Between Markers of Exercise Training and the Oral Microbiome

Strong correlations were detected between individual bacteria resident on the tongue dorsum, the volume of exercise training carried out per week and aerobic fitness levels. This suggests that regular exercise training alters the oral microenvironment, resulting in conditions more amenable to health-associated species, particularly those involved in NO_2^- production.

The completion of regular aerobic exercise training, at a variety of intensities, increases $\dot{V}\text{O}_{2\text{max}}$ (Scribbans *et al.*, 2016). Oral conditions will be altered each time an individual exercises, including increases in salivary lactate levels (Santos *et al.*, 2006; Oliveira *et al.*, 2015; Thomas *et al.*, 2019). As previously mentioned, some NO_3^- -reducing species, including *R. mucilaginosa* are capable of using lactate as an electron donor while during NO_2^- generation (Rosier, Buetas *et al.*, 2020). It is plausible that the combination of increased NO_3^- and NO_2^- availability in the saliva of trained individuals, combined with regular spikes in salivary lactate during intensive exercise, grants certain NO_2^- -producing bacteria a survival advantage.

Associations were also detected between health-associated bacteria and plasma NO_2^- . Species positively associated with exercise training included *R. mucilaginosa* and *Streptococcus salivarius*, a species which has previously demonstrated the ability to increase NO_2^- bioavailability when administered as a probiotic (Burleigh *et al.*, 2023). While *R. mucilaginosa* was the only confirmed NO_3^- -reducing bacterium that was significantly higher in the trained group, these exploratory findings suggest that regular exercise may also benefit other NO_2^- -producing species under different conditions, which should be tested in future studies.

No significant associations were detected between the composition of the plaque microbiome and any of the investigated variables. While it is feasible that the study was underpowered to detect these associations, the impact of oral hygiene habits should also be considered. This means the tongue microbiome will have been left undisturbed for longer than that of the supragingival plaque. As a result, the bacteria resident on the tongue will have been exposed to salivary NO_3^- and NO_2^- for a longer period and may have been resident in their host during multiple intensive exercise bouts. This may have supported the undisturbed growth of health-associated NO_2^- -producing species which would have been removed from supragingival areas when performing tooth brushing.

5.4.5 Strengths and Weaknesses

This study used long-read PacBio 16s rRNA sequencing to conduct precise species-level identification of bacteria, providing data of a higher resolution compared to previously published studies (Minty *et al.*, 2018; Kalabiska *et al.*, 2023). We also collected samples from environmental niches relevant to oral NO_2^- production and dental disease development to assess the impact of long-term exercise training on the microbiome of these sites.

However, the study design has some weaknesses which should be noted. It was designed as a pilot, recruiting only 10 participants to each group. While the post-hoc power calculation estimates a power of 0.88 when assessing differences in salivary NO_2^- levels there were high levels of variability in physiological NO_3^- and NO_2^- levels, dietary NO_3^- , oral NO_2^- production capacity and in the composition of the oral microbiome. This may have obscured significant findings, which could be detected with a larger sample size. Furthermore, the oral hygiene practices of the two groups appear to differ, but are not statistically significant, again indicating that future studies of a similar design would benefit from a larger sample size. This makes it challenging to draw robust conclusions regarding the impact of exercise on the oral microbiome.

While all the trained group demonstrated a high $\dot{V}\text{O}_{2\text{max}}$, they also reported a wide range of time spent exercising in the week prior to participation. This may have implications for both their NO_3^- and NO_2^- levels and for their oral microbiome composition. In contrast, the untrained group were largely inactive for the duration of this period, meaning the lifestyle difference

between groups was still considerable. In addition, the results of the previous chapter appear to support the finding of this study, with the completion of regular exercise training associated with both changes in physiological NO_3^- and NO_2^- levels and an increased relative abundance of health-associated oral bacteria. However, future studies may wish to consider the impact of specific training programmes, to assess if specific disciplines or sports may be more beneficial or detrimental to oral health. Differences in energy expenditure between groups made finding control participants of a similar mass to trained participants difficult. All other recruitment criteria ensured no differences between groups likely to alter NO bioavailability (Bailey *et al.*, 2016; Brookes *et al.*, 2020; Bescos *et al.*, 2020; Lundberg and Weitzberg, 2022). In addition, all participants were instructed to arrive in a euhydrated state and attended the lab at approximately the same time in the morning. However, it was not possible to account for all factors which may influence salivary flow rates (Iorgulescu, 2009). Despite the wide variation in salivary flow rate, following normalisation, the intergroup differences between NO_3^- and NO_2^- levels remained unchanged. Finally, while inflammation at the gingival margin was quantified, the ethical approval and risk assessment for this study were such that no comprehensive periodontal examination was carried out. Furthermore, no radiographic examination was included. As a result, it is feasible that undetected periodontitis or interproximal carious lesions were present in some participants.

5.5 Conclusion

To our knowledge, we are the first study to examine differences in the oral microbiome between highly trained and untrained individuals at the species level using long-read 16s rRNA sequencing. While the results should be interpreted cautiously due to the small sample size and unavoidable confounding factors, we demonstrate differences in the microbiome of the tongue dorsum among individuals who carry out a high volume of intensive exercise training, compared to healthy inactive controls. Exercise training appears to benefit health-associated species within the microbiome of the tongue dorsum, as an increased relative abundance of unclassified *Gemella* species and of *R. mucilaginosa*, which are both health-associated, were seen in the trained group. We also demonstrate that consistent intensive exercise training alters the oral microenvironment, with increased salivary NO_3^- and NO_2^- levels compared to untrained controls, which may further support the development of a health-associated oral microbiome. The increased relative abundance of *R. mucilaginosa* in this, and previous studies, appears to indicate this NO_3^- reducing-species could act as a marker of aerobic fitness.

5.6 Supplementary Figures and Tables

5.6.1 Genus Level Microbiome Results

Supplementary Figure 5-1: Assessing the impact of long-term intensive aerobic exercise training on the diversity and composition of the oral microbiome at the genus level. (A) Rarefaction curves for observed genera. Differences in (B) dbp index, (C) Shannon index and (D) Chao1 index between trained (TR) and untrained (UTR) participants[⊗] and between the microbiome of the tongue and subgingival plaque in participants of the same training status[⊘]. Data shown as median with IQR. Differences in beta-diversity as assessed using canonical correspondence analyses (CCA). (E) the tongue microbiome of trained and untrained participants, (F) the subgingival plaque microbiome and (G) the combined differences in beta-diversity between microbiome samples of different groups. Overall composition of (H) the tongue dorsum microbiome and (I) the supragingival plaque in the trained and untrained

groups. All genera with relative abundance >1% are shown, with the remaining genera described as 'other'. [⊗]Wilcoxon test [∩]Wilcoxon signed-rank test. * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$.

A

Supplementary Figure 5-2: Shows associations between the composition of the supragingival plaque microbiome, NO_3^- and NO_2^- levels and the aerobic training status of all participants. Heatmaps with associations between markers of exercise training status, NO_3^- and NO_2^- levels, salivary pH and oral NO_2^- production levels and bacterial abundance at the genus (A) and species (B) levels. These heatmaps show the association between bacterial abundances after ANCOM-BC transformation and other parameters, which were obtained based on their projection onto a correlation circle plot derived from a principal component analysis. Only negative associations below -0.4 and positive associations above 0.4 between species are shown. To complement the association heatmaps, correlations between species and other parameters were determined with Spearman's rho and marked with asterisks on the heatmap (* p-unadjusted < 0.05, ** p-unadjusted < 0.01. No associations remained significant following correction for multiple testing).

6. Chapter 6 Reflections on Dental Disease Prevention in Competitive Endurance Sports: A Pilot Mixed-Methods Analysis

Key Points

- There is significant room for improvement in the level of knowledge possessed by athletes, their coaches and dental healthcare professionals (DHPs) regarding dental disease prevention in the competitive sports environment
- Self-reported measures of athlete oral hygiene habits indicate room for improvement.
- DHPs did not consider participation in competitive sports to increase dental disease risk.
- Few coaches had considered their role in dental disease prevention, but most felt they had a role supporting athlete health and wellbeing.

Role of Annabel Simpson in This Study

- Study design
- Initial questionnaire design
- Piloting and revision of initial questionnaire
- Participant recruitment
- All statistical analyses and interpretation of the quantitative data set
- All thematic analysis of the qualitative data set
- Construction of all tables and figures

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6.1 Background

An absence of dental disease is an integral part of health and well-being (Spanemberg *et al.*, 2019). Common dental diseases can be prevented with a mixture of strategies, implemented by the patient and dental team (Peres *et al.*, 2019). Among the general population, the absence of dental disease is linked to general health (Hakeem, Bernabé and Sabbah, 2019; Kotronia *et al.*, 2021) and the completion of physical activity appears associated with self-reported measures of oral health (Sanchez *et al.*, 2020).

Elite level athletes carry out high levels of exercise training and are generally considered to be at a decreased risk of developing most medical conditions compared to less active members of the general population (Runacres, Mackintosh and McNarry, 2021). Despite this, studies of elite-level athletes consistently demonstrate high dental disease prevalence (recently reviewed by Schulze and Busse, 2024). Between 6–18% of athletes report a negative impact of dental disease on performance and 20–28% report negative impacts on their quality of life (Schulze and Busse, 2024). Historic reports also implicate dental infections in poor performances by athletes at the Olympic Games (Forrest, 1969), while contemporary evidence estimates severe dental infection to be present in 3% to 8% of elite-level athletes (Needleman *et al.*, 2016; Gallagher *et al.*, 2019).

Dental disease prevalence among sub-elite athletes is less clear. While caries prevalence was higher among endurance athletes compared to controls (Merle *et al.*, 2022), these results were not replicated when competitive swimmers were compared to controls who swam recreationally (D’Ercole *et al.*, 2016). A greater prevalence of dental erosion has also been reported in competitive triathletes compared to untrained controls (Frese *et al.*, 2015), but not in competitive youth athletes (Merle *et al.*, 2022). Other studies using dental examinations to determine oral health substantiate these findings, reporting a reduced number of decayed, missing and filled teeth among active individuals compared to their inactive counterparts (Huttunen *et al.*, 2023) and a reduction in the prevalence of periodontitis, as assessed by multiple diagnostic parameters (Ferreira *et al.*, 2019). These findings suggest differences in the behaviour of elite-level athletes may alter their risk of developing dental disease.

Dietary guidelines in sports with high energy requirements recommend athletes follow carbohydrate supplementation protocols (Thomas, Erdman and Burke, 2016). These protocols

are athlete and activity-specific and may require the use of sugar mouth rinses or inter-activity consumption of cariogenic sugars (Thomas, Erdman and Burke, 2016). When used regularly, sugar ingestion may overwhelm salivary buffering mechanisms and provide an energy source for caries-associated bacteria which, in turn, increases the risk of dental caries and erosion (Rosier, Marsh and Mira, 2018). Athlete cohorts report that they perform regular oral hygiene (Gallagher *et al.*, 2019). However, professional rugby players have higher levels of plaque and gingival inflammation compared to inactive individuals acting as a control group (Minty *et al.*, 2018). A separate study reported elevated gingival inflammation compared to a population-wide survey (Gallagher *et al.*, 2019). These behaviours are accompanied by other physiological impacts of exercise training which affect the oral cavity, including systemic dehydration, decreased salivary flow and immunosuppression (Mulic *et al.*, 2012; Ntovas *et al.*, 2022). Furthermore, elite athletes frequently travel to races and training camps (Schwellnus *et al.*, 2016) which may disrupt attendance at dental appointments and oral hygiene, enabling disease progression.

Resources have previously been published to support dental disease prevention in competitive sports. These target athletes (Eastman Dental Institute, 2017; World Dental Federation, 2019a; World Dental Federation, 2019b), sports organisations (World Dental Federation, 2019c) and athletes' dental and medical teams (World Dental Federation, 2019d). As dental health is primarily the responsibility of the individual patient, these resources focus on encouraging behaviours which support oral health. This includes the performance of oral hygiene using a fluoride-containing dentifrice (Glenny *et al.*, 2023) and reducing the frequency of carbohydrate consumption (Moores, Kelly and Moynihan, 2022). This should be accompanied by behavioural change support and preventative interventions, delivered by DHPs, following evidence-based guidance (Public Health England, 2021; SDCEP, 2024).

Current evidence suggests athletes are amenable to behaviour changes to prevent dental disease, following a targeted intervention delivered by a specialist sports dentist (Gallagher, Ashley and Needleman, 2020). However, most dental care in the UK is provided by DHPs with no special interest in sports dentistry and just over one half of elite-level athletes could recall receiving diet advice from their own dentist (Gallagher *et al.*, 2019). Instead, athletes rely on other members of their support team to provide them with advice. This includes their coach, whom athletes regularly consult for guidance on sports nutrition (Diehl *et al.*, 2012; Torres-McGehee *et al.*, 2012; Solly *et al.*, 2023). While this may provide conflicting advice to that

delivered by the dental team (Schulze and Busse, 2024), coaches could be in an ideal position to encourage dental disease mitigation, for example by suggesting when the use of sports supplements is inappropriate (Needleman *et al.*, 2015, 2018).

Awareness of the existence and contents of the dental education resources available (Eastman Dental Institute, 2017; World Dental Federation, 2019a; World Dental Federation, 2019b; World Dental Federation, 2019c; World Dental Federation, 2019d) to athletes and their support team are not currently known. It is feasible that these are currently underutilised, contributing to the increased prevalence of dental disease among some athlete populations. In addition, the attitudes of non-specialist DHPs and coaches regarding their role in the prevention of dental disease in athletes are unknown.

This study aimed to assess the knowledge, beliefs and attitudes of athletes, coaches, and non-specialist DHPs regarding the prevention of dental disease in individuals who, while not elite-level athletes, train for competitive sports. As preventing dental disease in competitive sports represents a unique challenge a mixed-methods study design was used to collect quantitative and qualitative data from all three study groups, via an online questionnaire.

6.2 Methods

The study questionnaire was developed and administered following a systematic multi-stage process: 1) initial questionnaire development; 2) piloting of the initial questionnaire to assess its content; 3) adjustment of the initial questionnaire; 4) data collection using the finalised questionnaire. Each stage is described in greater detail below.

6.2.1 Initial Questionnaire Development

A self-administered questionnaire was created and hosted on the QuestionPro online platform to address the study aims. The questions were developed following a review of evidence-based guidance relevant to the prevention of dental disease in the general population (Public Health England, 2021), alongside expert advice based on this guidance regarding dental disease prevention in elite-level sports (Needleman *et al.*, 2014).

The initial draft questions were discussed by the researcher, who has experience as an undergraduate dental student and an international-level athlete, with a panel of individuals involved in dental practice (N=1), sports coaching (N=1), sports science (N=2) and

questionnaire design (N=1). All members of this panel were aware of the aims of the research study and, while the individual involved in dental practice was contacted via email, all other panel members attended a face-to-face meeting to assess questionnaire content. A different questionnaire was used for DHPs to account for the professional knowledge of this group (Richards, Filippini and Roberts-Burt, 2014).

The first questionnaire section collected demographic data. The second section used multiple-choice questions (answered using a five-point Likert Scale) and scenario-based questions (with multiple-choice answers given as options, plus an open-box question marked ‘other’) to assess participant knowledge. These questions mapped to 3 domains identified in pre-existing dental literature, as shown in Table 6-1.

Table 6-1: Mapping of questions to assess participant knowledge to domains in existing dental literature

Domain	Number of Questions Referencing Domain in Pilot Questionnaire	
	DHP Questionnaire	Coaches and Athletes Questionnaire
Dental Diseases	4	5
- Dental Caries	2	2
- Periodontal Disease	0	1
- Dental Erosion	2	2
Dental Disease and Sports Performance	3	3
Preventative Dental Care	3	3
Total Questions in Pilot Questionnaire	10	11

The final section consisted of modified Likert Scale questions, checkboxes, and open-ended questions to gather data regarding the respondents' perceived role in maintaining athletes' oral health, their reasons for holding these beliefs and if they were aware of any barriers preventing them from promoting athlete dental health.

6.2.2 Piloting of the Initial Questionnaire

The questionnaire was piloted to convenience samples of DHPs working at Glasgow Dental Hospital on a typical midweek day (N=11) and to coaches (N=11) and athletes (N=10) attending the Scottish Athletics Senior Track Championships. The researcher was present throughout the pilot.

To assess content and clarity, respondents were required to complete the questionnaire and then fill out a feedback form. Their responses were collected for subsequent analysis. Likert scale questions were used to evaluate the questionnaire wording, terminology, and structure. Open-ended questions were included to allow participants to provide additional feedback.

6.2.3 Adjustments to the Initial Questionnaire Following Piloting

All changes made to the study questionnaire following feedback from the pilot participants are shown in Table 6-2.

Table 6-2: Changes made to the pilot questionnaire following feedback

Group	Change
DHPs	<ol style="list-style-type: none">1. 'Dental diseases' changed to 'plaque-induced dental diseases'.2. Addition of a question regarding periodontal-disease prevention in athlete groups.3. Please provide a brief explanation of what you think your role is with regards to providing diet advice for athletes, for general and/or oral health. Have any specific experiences (e.g. personal or CPD courses you have attended) influenced your understanding of your role in the delivery of diet advice? changed to<ol style="list-style-type: none">a. Please provide a brief explanation of what you think your role is with regards to providing diet advice for athletes, for general and/or oral health. Have any specific experiences (e.g. personal or CPD courses you have attended) influenced your understanding of your role in the delivery of diet advice?b. Do you feel you encounter any barriers in your clinical practice that would prevent you from finding out that your patients are involved in elite sport or that might prevent you from delivering advice on disease prevention to this group?
Coaches	<ol style="list-style-type: none">1. Change to neutral terminology throughout the questionnaire.2. Additional open-ended question 'Would anything prevent you from advising your athletes attend the dentist for treatment or advice?'
Athletes	<ol style="list-style-type: none">1. Wording changes to improve clarity.2. Formatting changes to improve clarity.
Multiple Groups	<ol style="list-style-type: none">1. Option given to state having never received CPD materials on the provision of diet advice.2. Statements reassuring participants that a link to athlete oral health guidance would be provided were added throughout the questionnaire.3. Additional open-ended question 'Has your ability to train or compete been impacted on by dental disease, for example, toothache, infections or gum disease?' was added to the athlete questionnaire.

6.2.4 Ethical Approval

Participants confirmed they had read the participant information sheet and gave informed consent prior to starting the online questionnaire. All procedures were approved by the local Ethics Committee (Reference number: 21859 - 19/10/2023) and conformed to the Declaration of Helsinki.

6.2.5 Data Collection

Following piloting, the online questionnaire was distributed (Appendix 3). Social media groups which included athletes, sports coaches and DHPs were contacted with a copy of the study

flyer. In addition, this information was distributed using email to staff at Glasgow Dental Hospital. Response data were collected and stored by the questionnaire tool before being exported for analysis. The questionnaire was open from 23/01/24 until 19/04/24 with periodic reminders to encourage responses.

6.2.6 Inclusion Criteria

Athletes were invited to take part if they were aged >18 and if they took part in organised exercise training to improve competitive performance. Coaches were invited to participate if they were involved in setting training plans for athletes aged >18, aiming to improve their competitive performance. Dental healthcare professionals were invited to take part if they were involved in the provision of preventative care and if they were registered with the General Dental Council.

6.2.7 Quantitative Analysis

Excel (Version 2402) was used to clean the exported data. Once complete, the data was exported into GraphPad Prism (Version 10.1.1) for subsequent analysis. To assess participants knowledge of dental disease prevention in the competitive sports environment, the total number of correct answers to the knowledge portion of the questionnaire from each respondent were computed and an overall percentage score calculated. Correct answers were decided by the research team, after consultation of the relevant preventative guidance and evidence-informed educational materials (Eastman Dental Institute, 2017; Public Health England, 2021). As an additional question was added for the DHP questionnaire post-piloting, only the post-pilot responses for this group were included in the final analysis. These data were tested for normality using Shapiro-Wilk tests and by visual examination of boxplots. The overall scores of athletes and coaches were compared using a Mann-Whitney test. The knowledge scores of the DHPs were not compared with the other groups as different questions were used to reflect the professional training this group had received. For categorical data and Likert scale responses, frequency distributions were calculated. Cross tabulations were constructed, and Fisher's exact tests used to analyse if being a DHP or coach was associated with the responses to each question. For all statistical testing, the alpha level for declaring statistical significance was set at $p \leq 0.05$.

6.2.8 Qualitative Analysis

The qualitative dataset was analysed using reflexive thematic analysis, following the methodology proposed by Braun and Clarke (2019). In accordance with the paradigm of interpretivism, the researcher's background as a dental student and a competitive athlete will have influenced the analysis process (Thanh and Thanh, 2015), so an artfully interpretive approach was adopted (Braun and Clarke, 2024). The researcher first read the dataset in its entirety multiple times and descriptive codes were generated by marking phrases with a similar meaning in an iterative process. This reflexive approach to coding was chosen to allow the codes to evolve throughout the analysis process (Byrne, 2022). Similar codes were then grouped together and used to construct themes by the researcher. To provide an overview of these themes, thematic maps were initially generated. However, to better incorporate the quantitative and qualitative datasets, the discussion section was constructed as a series of theme headings, accompanied by explanatory text.

6.3 Results

6.3.1 Participant Demographics

The responses of 67 athletes, 33 coaches and 33 DHPs were included for analysis. The demographic characteristics of the athletes, coaches and DHPs are shown in Table 6-3 to 6-5.

Forty-five of the athletes competed in endurance running events of distances exceeding 5000m and another 15 competed in middle distance running events (400-1500m). The remaining athletes were triathletes (2), sprinters (1), field athletes (1), competitive footballers (1) or indicated that their primary event was "running" (2). Thirty-two coaches were involved with the sport of athletics.

No athlete or coach respondents were aware of resources aimed at preventing dental disease in competitive sports. In the DHP group, 1 participant was aware of the athlete oral health toolkit produced by the Eastman Dental Institute (2017) and 1 of guidance published by Scottish Rugby.

Table 6-3: Demographic characteristics of the athlete participants (N=67)

Gender	Male		Female		Non-Binary/Intersex	
	40.3% (27)		58.2% (39)		1.5% (1)	
Ethnicity	White			BAME		
	95.5% (64)			3 (4.5%)		
Age	18-24	25-34	35-44	45-54	55-64	>64
	23.9% (16)	37.3% (25)	17.9% (12)	16.4% (11)	3.0% (2)	1.5% (1)
Working With a Coach	Yes			No		
	67.2% (45)			32.8% (22)		
Years Involved in Competitive Sports	1-5	5-10	10-15	15-20	>20	
	19.4% (13)	22.4% (15)	23.9% (16)	17.9% (12)	16.4% (11)	
Highest Level of Competition	Local/county	District	National	International	Olympic/Paralympic	
	22.4% (15)	11.9% (8)	34.3% (23)	29.9% (20)	1.5% (1)	
Hours Trained/Week	<5	5-6	7-8	9-10	11-12	>12
	6.0% (4)	26.3% (16)	17.9% (12)	26.9% (18)	11.9% (8)	13.4% (9)
Registered With Dentist	Yes		No		Don't know	
	86.6% (58)		11.9% (8)		1.5% (1)	
Time Since Last Visit to Dentist	<3 months	3-6 months	6-12 months	1-2 years	>2 years	
	32.8% (22)	17.9% (12)	17.9% (12)	14.9% (10)	16.4% (11)	
Dental Health Impacted on Sports Performance	Yes			No		
	13.4% (9)			86.6% (58)		

Table 6-4: Demographic characteristics of coach participants (N=33 unless stated otherwise)

Gender	Male			Female		
	75.8% (25)			24.2% (8)		
Age	18-24	25-34	35-44	45-54	55-64	>64
	3.0% (1)	9.1% (3)	18.2% (6)	24.2% (8)	36.4% (12)	9.1% (3)
Ethnicity (N=22)	White			BAME		
	95.5% (21)			4.5% (1)		
Competed as an Athlete	Yes			No		
	78.8% (26)			21.2% (7)		
Time Coaching	1-2 years	2-5 years	5-10 years	>10 years		
	6.0% (2)	18.2% (6)	39.4% (13)	36.4% (12)		
Highest Level of Athlete Competition	Local/County	District	National	International	Olympic/Paralympic	
	9.1% (3)	18.2% (6)	18.2% (6)	45.5% (15)	9.1% (3)	

Table 6-5: Demographic characteristics of DHP participants (N=33 unless stated otherwise)

Gender	Male			Female		
	44.1% (15)			52.9% (18)		
Age	18-24	25-34	35-44	45-54	55-64	>64
	0.0% (0)	21.2% (7)	24.2% (8)	27.3% (9)	27.3% (9)	0.0% (0)
Ethnicity (N=21)	White			BAME		
	100.0% (21)			0.0% (0)		
Role in the Dental Team	Dentist			Other		
	97.0% (32)			3.0% (1)		
Time Spent Treating Patients as Part of NHS Contract (%) (N=21)	0-25%	25-50%	50-75%	75-100%	Public Dental Services	
	28.6% (6)	9.5% (2)	19.0% (4)	23.8% (5)	19.1% (4)	
Years Since Qualification	<1	1-5	5-10	10-20	>20	
	(0.0%) 0	18.2% (6)	9.1% (3)	18.2% (6)	54.6% (18)	
Trained for Competitive Sports	Yes			No		
	48.5% (16)			51.5% (17)		
Currently Training for Competitive Sports	Yes			No		
	39.4% (13)			60.6% (20)		
Coaching Qualification	Yes			No		
	21.2% (7)			78.8% (26)		

6.3.2 Respondent Knowledge of Dental Disease Prevention in a Competitive Sports Environment

The questions presented to each group to assess knowledge of dental disease prevention in competitive sports, their correct responses and the percentage of current responses to each question are shown in Tables 6-6 to 6-8.

Table 6-6: Questions to assess athlete respondent knowledge of dental disease prevention in competitive sports (N=67).

Question Number	Question	Correct Answer	Correct Responses (%)
1	If I consume a large volume of sugar in one go, this will impact my dental health more than if I was to consume small volumes of sugar more frequently.	Disagree OR Strongly Disagree	68.7
2	If my gums bleed when I am brushing my teeth, this is a sign I am using too much force and should stop brushing the affected area.	Disagree OR Strongly Disagree	55.2
3	Using sugar-free powders or tablets to deliver electrolytes during sessions where I will sweat heavily will have no impact on my mouth.	Disagree OR Strongly Disagree	49.3
4	Athletes like me are at a higher risk of dental disease compared to inactive members of the population of a similar age.	Agree OR Strongly Agree	25.4
5	My dental health will impact my performance in training and competition.	Agree OR Strongly Agree	71.6
6	I should use a mouthwash which contains fluoride as an ingredient, from a brand such as Listerine or Colgate, at a time other than when I am brushing my teeth.	Agree OR Strongly Agree	40.3
7	I should use a mouthwash which contains antimicrobial ingredients, from a brand such as Corsodyl, at a time other than when I am brushing my teeth.	Disagree OR Strongly Disagree	20.9
8	Sometimes, after working especially hard during training or competition, athletes vomit. If you vomit while doing sport which of the following, would you be most likely to do?	Rinse my mouth with water once vomiting stops and then continue training' OR 'other' if the given answer was appropriate	73.1
9	You have decided you are going to start using carbohydrate drinks or gels during longer training sessions so you can maintain performance for longer. You have bought some sports drinks to use in between hard efforts. Is there anything you would do immediately after having some of the sports drink?	Rinse my mouth with water' OR 'other' if the given answer was appropriate	31.3
10	You are going on a training camp so need to bring your toiletries bag. Would you choose a toothpaste with a minimum concentration of fluoride to take with you?	I should use the standard fluoride toothpaste concentration sold in supermarkets' OR 'My dentist gives me a prescription strength toothpaste, so I use that' OR 'other' if the given answer was appropriate	94.0
11	Would you try to adjust the timing of your dental appointments based on specific markers in your training season, such as the off-season?	'Yes' OR 'other' if the given answer was appropriate	14.9

Table 6-7: Questions to assess coach respondent knowledge of dental disease prevention in competitive sports (N=33).

Question Number	Question	Correct Response	Correct Responses (%)
1	When my athletes consume a large volume of sugar in one go, this impacts on their dental health more that when they consume smaller volumes of sugar more frequently.	Disagree OR Strongly Disagree	57.6
2	If my athletes' gums bleed when they brush their teeth, this is a sign they are using too much force and they should stop brushing this area.	Disagree OR Strongly Disagree	81.3
3	If my athletes use sugar-free powders or tablets to deliver electrolytes when they are doing sessions where they are likely to sweat heavily these will have no impact on the mouth.	Disagree OR Strongly Disagree	33.3
4	Elite athletes are at a higher risk of dental disease compared to inactive members of the population of a similar age.	Agree OR Strongly Agree	18.2
5	The dental health of the athletes I coach will impact their performance.	Agree OR Strongly Agree	72.7
6	I would advise the athletes I coach to use a mouthwash which contains fluoride as an ingredient, from a brand such as Colgate or Listerine, at a time other than when they brush their teeth.	Agree OR Strongly Agree	27.3
7	I would advise athletes I coach to use a mouthwash which contains an active antimicrobial ingredient, such as chlorhexidine, from a brand such as Corsodyl, at a time other than when they brush their teeth.	Disagree OR Strongly Disagree	36.4
8	One of your athletes occasionally vomits during or after training sessions and competitions after working especially hard. Which of the following would you be most likely to advise after the athlete has finished throwing up?	Rinse my mouth with water once vomiting stops and then continue training' OR 'other' if the given answer was appropriate	66.7
9	Your athlete has recently started using high carbohydrate sports drinks to maintain performance during long training sessions. Would you give any advice after taking some of the high-carbohydrate sports drink?	Rinse my mouth with water' OR 'other' if the given answer was appropriate	15.6
10	You are going on a training camp with your athletes, and they will need to bring toiletries bags. Is there a minimum concentration of fluoride toothpaste the athletes should use to brush their teeth?	I should use the standard fluoride toothpaste concentration sold in supermarkets' OR 'My dentist gives me a prescription strength toothpaste, so I use that' OR 'other' if the given answer was appropriate	27.3
11	Would you advise your athletes to adjust the times they attend their dentist due to specific markers in their training calendar such as the off-season?	'Yes' OR 'other' if the given answer was appropriate	9.1

Table 6-8: Questions to assess DHP respondent knowledge of dental disease prevention in competitive sports (N=21).

Question Number	Question	Correct Response	Correct Responses (%)
1	Individuals involved in competitive sport are more at risk of developing dental disease compared to less active members of the population of a similar age?	Agree OR Strongly Agree	51.5
2	If an athlete reports their gums are bleeding when they brush, they are applying too much pressure to this area and should avoid brushing it for a few days to let the gingivae recover.	Disagree OR Strongly Disagree	95.2
3	I give different prevention advice to individuals who I know are involved in competitive sport compared to less active individuals of a similar age	Agree OR Strongly Agree	45.5
4	To avoid dental disease, I would advise athletes I care for to avoid the use of dietary carbohydrate supplementation during training and racing	Disagree OR Strongly Disagree	39.4
5	I would advise athletes to use a mouthwash which contains fluoride at a time other than when they are carrying out tooth brushing and inter-dental hygiene.	Agree OR Strongly Agree	72.7
6	I would advise athletes to use a mouthwash which contains chlorhexidine at a time other than when then are carrying out toothbrushing and flossing.	Disagree OR Strongly Disagree	51.5
7	A patient attends your surgery for a routine appointment. They compete for their local rugby club with matches almost every weekend for the duration of the on-season. Their aim is to sign with a club on a professional basis within the next few years. What would you advise to be used for hydration when the patient is sweating heavily?	‘Electrolytes followed by water’ OR ‘other’ if the given answer was appropriate	9.1
8	A patient attends your surgery for a routine appointment. During history taking, they mention that they are in training for the London marathon aiming to run a qualifying time for the upcoming World Championships and that their coach has advised they use carbohydrate gels during the race to avoid ‘hitting the wall’. What advice, if any, would you give them?	‘Advise they take the supplement with mitigation methods’ OR ‘other’ if the given answer was appropriate	78.8
9	Your patient has recently been selected to compete for Scotland in the Commonwealth Games. He makes sure he wears full headgear and a mouthguard when competing to avoid injuries to his teeth or facial skeleton, and he trains for more than 90 minutes a day, at least 6 times a week, sometimes splitting his training sessions so they take place before and after work. What concentration of fluoride toothpaste would you consider most appropriate for him?	‘I would prescribe him a higher dose’ OR ‘other’ if the given answer was appropriate	18.2
10	After an athlete leaves the dental chair, where does most of the responsibility for their dental health lie?	‘With the athlete’	100
11	One of your patients attends the practice, mentioning she is about to start pre-season training with the football club she has signed to for her first professional contract. Would you decide to adjust the timings of recall appointments for this athlete, who currently has no signs of dental disease?	‘I would’	3

The total number of correct answers from each respondent was computed and used to calculate overall percentage scores for all individuals in each respondent group. The median score for this section of the questionnaire was 36.4% (IQR 27.3-45.6%) for athletes and 36.4% (IQR 27.3-45.6%) for coaches (Figure 6-1A). No significant difference was detected between groups ($p=0.74$, $U=1094$). The median score for DHPs was 45.5% (IQR 36.4-54.6%), as shown in Figure 6-1B.

Figure 6-1: Percentage of correct responses to questions assessing respondent knowledge of dental disease prevention in competitive sports. (A) Athlete and Coaches (B) DHPs. Each point represents an individual respondent. The bars show the median score and the interquartile range. Athlete and coach scores were compared using a Mann-Whitney Test. $N=67$ for athletes, $N=33$ for coaches and $N=21$ for DHPs.

When the proportion of correct responses to each question by athletes and coaches was compared, 94% of athletes correctly responded to question 10 (worded ‘You are going on a training camp so need to bring your toiletries bag. Would you choose a toothpaste with a minimum concentration of fluoride to take with you?’) compared to 27% of coaches (worded ‘You are going on a training camp with your athletes, and they will need to bring toiletries bags. Is there a minimum concentration of fluoride toothpaste the athletes should use to brush their teeth?’). A significant difference was detected in correct responses between groups for this question ($p=0.001$ after correcting for multiple testing).

6.3.3 Sources of Advice Provided to Athletes

Athletes were questioned on the diet advice they could recall receiving from their coach and dental team. Forty-five of the respondents indicated they worked with a coach, so only these individuals were included for analysis.

No athletes could recall having received diet advice relating to dental disease prevention advice from their coach and 42% (28) could recall receiving this advice from their dentist (Figure 6-2A). In contrast, 71% (32) could recall receiving diet advice relating to sports performance from their coach, while only 6% (4) could recall receiving similar advice from the dental team (Figure 6-2B) and only 9% (6) had received diet advice relating to their general health from their dentist compared to the 44% (20) who had received this advice from a coach (Figure 6-2C). A statistically significant difference in the proportion of athletes who could recall receiving advice from either group was detected for all 3 types of diet advice (all $p < 0.0001$).

Figure 6-2: Athlete responses to the question ‘Have you ever been given advice about the following from your dentist or coach?’ (A) Diet advice relating to dental disease prevention, (B) Diet advice relating to sports performance (C) Diet advice relating to their general health. The results of Fisher’s exact tests, used to compare the proportions of athletes who could recall receiving diet advice from each group, compared to the null hypothesis are shown. $N=45$.

6.3.4 Self-reported Oral Hygiene Aid and Carbohydrate Supplementation Use by Athletes

Athletes were asked what oral hygiene aid(s) they used (Table 6-9) and to report on their carbohydrate supplementation usage during activity (Table 6-10) and outside of activity (Table 6-11).

Table 6-9: Self-reported oral hygiene aid use by athlete respondents

Oral Hygiene Aid	Daily	Weekly	Monthly	Annually	Never
Electric Toothbrush	56.1% (37)	1.5% (1)	3.0% (2)	1.5% (1)	37.9% (25)
Manual Toothbrush	56.9% (37)	4.6% (3)	13.9% (9)	7.7% (5)	16.9% (11)
Fluoride Toothpaste (Bought From Supermarket)	97.0% (65)	0.0% (0)	0.0% (0)	0.0% (0)	3.0% (2)
A Toothpaste My Dentist Prescribes	3.1% (2)	0.0% (0)	0.0% (0)	1.5% (1)	95.4% (62)
Fluoride Free Toothpaste	0.0% (0)	0.0% (0)	0.0% (0)	3.0% (2)	97.0% (64)
Fluoride Mouthwash Such as Listerine or Colgate	10.6% (7)	28.8% (19)	7.6% (5)	4.6% (3)	48.5% (32)
Antimicrobial Mouthwash such as Corsodyl	1.5% (1)	4.6% (3)	4.6% (3)	10.6% (7)	78.8% (52)
Dental Floss/Interdental Brushes/Dental Flossettes	28.4% (19)	26.9% (18)	9.0% (6)	7.5% (5)	28.4% (19)
Whitening Products	4.5% (3)	1.5% (1)	11.9% (8)	7.5% (5)	74.6% (50)
Other	1.6% (1)	1.6% (1)	1.6% (1)	0.0% (0)	95.1% (58)

Table 6-10: Self-reported carbohydrate supplementation usage during activity by athlete respondents

Supplement	Daily	Weekly	Monthly	Annually	Never
Sports Drinks	7.5% (5)	22.4% (15)	28.4% (19)	7.5% (5)	34.3% (23)
Sports Gels	6.0% (4)	26.9% (18)	19.4% (13)	11.9% (8)	35.8% (24)
Sugar Mouth Rinses	1.5% (1)	1.5% (1)	0.0% (0)	0.0% (0)	97.0% (65)
Sugar Gummies	1.5% (1)	13.4% (9)	14.9% (10)	3.0% (2)	67.2% (45)
A Sugar-Free Electrolyte Powder/Tablet/Gel	14.9% (10)	16.4% (11)	14.9% (10)	7.5% (5)	46.3% (31)
A Non-Sugar-Free Electrolyte Powder/Tablet/Gel	4.5% (3)	16.4% (11)	11.9% (8)	13.4% (9)	53.7% (36)
Snacks to Increase Sugar Intake	13.4% (9)	44.8% (30)	11.9% (8)	6.0% (4)	23.9% (16)
Other Product	9.7% (6)	9.7% (6)	4.8% (3)	3.2% (2)	72.6% (45)

Table 6-11: Self-reported carbohydrate supplementation usage outside of activity by athlete respondents

Supplement	Daily	Weekly	Monthly	Annually	Never
Sports Drinks	3.0% (2)	6.0% (4)	7.5% (5)	7.0% (6)	74.6% (50)

Sports Gels	1.5% (1)	1.5% (1)	7.5% (5)	1.5% (1)	88.0% (59)
Sugar Mouth Rinses	0.0% (0)	3.0% (2)	0.0% (0)	0.0% (0)	97.0% (65)
Sugar Gummies	0.0% (0)	6.0% (4)	9.0% (6)	1.5% (1)	83.6% (56)
A Sugar-Free Electrolyte Powder/Tablet/Gel	11.9% (8)	7.0% (6)	6.0% (4)	4.5% (3)	68.7% (46)
A Non-Sugar-Free Electrolyte Powder/Tablet/Gel	3.0% (2)	9.1% (6)	7.6% (5)	4.6% (3)	75.8% (50)
Snacks to Increase Sugar Intake	17.9% (12)	32.8% (22)	11.9% (8)	0.0% (0)	37.3% (25)
Other Products	7.7% (5)	9.2% (6)	3.1% (2)	1.5% (1)	78.5% (51)

Factors athletes consider important when making dietary changes.

To understand what might motivate dietary decision making, the athlete respondents were provided with a question, asking if they considered general health, dental health, sports performance, and enjoyment of their food and drink as important when making dietary changes. The athlete responses are shown in Figure 6-3.

Figure 6-3: Athlete responses to the question ‘When you make decisions about dietary changes, do you consider the following to be important?’ (A) General Health, (B) Dental Health, (C) Sports Performance, (D) Enjoyment. N=67.

6.3.5 Coach and DHP Opinions on Their Role in the Delivery of Diet Advice

Coaches and DHPs were asked if they considered themselves to have a role in delivering diet advice relating to the maintenance of general health, sports performance, dental health, and dental health specific to athletes. The proportions of responses to each question by coaches and DHPs were calculated and compared to the null hypothesis, which assumes no difference in the proportions of responses between the two groups.

No significant associations were detected between the responses given by coaches and DHPs relating to the delivery of diet advice to maintain general health (Figure 6-4A, $p=0.12$) or for sports performance (Figure 6-4B, $p=0.61$). A significant association was detected between

coaches and DHPs regarding their perceived role in the delivery of diet advice to prevent dental disease and in the prevention of dental disease specific to athletes (both $p < 0.0001$), with more DHPs stating they believed they had a role in these areas. A greater proportion of DHPs indicated that they strongly agreed or agreed that they had a role in dental disease prevention, both when the patient was not specified as an athlete (Figure 6-4C) and when they were (Figure 6-4D).

Despite some changes in response, no significant associations were detected when groups were asked if they felt they had a role in dental disease prevention and in dental disease prevention specific to athletes ($p = 0.38$ in DHPs and $p = 0.92$ in coaches).

Figure 6-4: DHP and coach responses to the statement ‘I believe I have a role...’ (A) Delivering Diet Advice to Support General Health, (B) Delivering Diet Advice to Support Sports Performance, (C) Delivering Diet Advice to Prevent Dental Disease, (D) Delivering Diet Advice to Prevent Dental Disease in Athletes. Results of Fisher’s exact tests, comparing the proportions of each group to the null hypothesis are displayed. $N = 33$ in both coaches and DHPs.

6.3.6 Coach and DHP Confidence Delivering Diet Advice

Both coaches and DHPs were asked how confident they felt in delivering diet advice to support sports performance and to prevent dental disease. A significant association was detected between groups for responses to both questions. A greater proportion of coaches felt more confident providing diet advice to support sports performance (Figure 6-5A, $p=0.035$) while a greater proportion of DHPs felt confident delivering diet advice for dental disease prevention (Figure 6-5B, $p<0.0001$).

Figure 6-5: DHP and coach responses to the question 'I feel confident delivering...' (A) Diet advice to athletes to improve sports performance, (B) Diet advice to athletes to prevent dental disease. The results of Fisher's exact tests, comparing the proportions of each group compared to the null hypothesis are displayed. $N=33$ in both coaches and DHPs.

6.4 Discussion and Results of Qualitative Thematic Analysis

To our knowledge, this is the first study to reveal a lack of awareness among athletes, coaches and DHPs of the possible increased risk of dental disease in athletes and to show limited awareness of strategies to reduce this risk in the competitive sports environment. To provide context for these quantitative findings, we discuss them below, alongside the results from the thematic analysis. The findings of the thematic analysis are summarised in brief in Table 6-12.

Table 6-12: A summary of the key themes and subthemes found in the thematic analysis for each of the study groups. Illustrative quotes for each theme are also shown.

Athletes				
Theme 1: Missing Sleep and Dropping Out - Dental Disease Impacts Athletes On and Off the Field of Play				
A2 'Had root canal treatment that stopped me training for about a week and hindered me for about a week before the operation'	A32 '...toothache once which was horrendous and prevented me from training until it was fixed'	A42 'Toothache has given me a few consecutive bad night's sleep in the week before a race and I dropped out of the race'	A46 'Unable to run due to an infection'	
Theme 2: Diet and Dental Advice From Multiple Sources (Not the Dentist)				
A30, '...share advice in the group about what gels etc are good and what tastes nice'	A31 '...in my club we work with nutritionist and she gives us advice on what is good to eat and what foods are good for performance'	A41 '...in general I'm quite sceptical of the sports diet industry as I think a lot of it has been influenced by market forces and is over complicated'.	A53 '...chats with coach about fuelling during marathon training blocks and races'	A12 'Elite athletes on social media'.

Coaches

Theme 1: The Role of the Coach in the Provision of Diet Advice

Sub-theme 1: Diet Advice for General Health

C1 'Encourage general self-care of athletes everyday'. C13 would,	C25 '...ensure young athletes eat a good balance of all food groups'	C26 'Can't start a session depleted as quality and quantity will be negatively impacted. Like trying to drive a car with no petrol'	C25 '...encourage good carbohydrates in the form of pasta/bread/rice/bananas etc in advance of and after training sessions'.	C25 '...don't currently recommend energy drinks...water all the way!'
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Sub-theme 2: Diet Advice For Sports Performance

C5 '...fundamental to optimum performance'	C14 'For those competing at Half-marathon and beyond (including hill racing) or in heats, semis, etc. I suggest use of gels and sports drinks during long runs and competition.'	C16 '...would not provide any diet advice for my highest performing athletes as I have no qualifications to do so.'	C24 'I believe only basic general advice on diet should be advised unless the coach has some specific qualification/training in diet/nutrition and oral health. I myself have no nutrition qualifications so only give out basic diet advice that would be easily available to athletes themselves online'	C2 'No formal qualifications in nutrition or diet, so therefore would signpost athletes to good sources of information or nutritionists'.
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Theme 2: Trusted Sources of Information Provide the Best Advice

C10 'We [Their athletics club] have a nutritionist who guides us what is appropriate at different stages of their training throughout the year'.	C18 'Usually direct them to the advice in a book (Pfitzinger) and recommend Eat Slow Run Fast cookbook'.	C14 '...experience of the use of carbohydrate drinks and gels'	C26 '...background in physiology and public health'	
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Theme 3: The Perceived Role (or Lack Thereof) of the Coach in Dental Health.

C32 'Major role as with other health issues. We want our athletes to be able to train and compete to their best. This involves being medically and dentally fit. We also have a duty of care - 'do no harm'. This includes teeth and dental issues.'	C30 'consider providing basic advice regards diet and oral health'.	C13, '...had not considered it before' C22 '...I must confess I've never thought about my role in relation to dental health'.		
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DHPs

Theme 1: Patient Education is Paramount to Achieving Good Oral Health - The Role of the DHP in the Provision of Diet Advice.

DHP32 'Patient education is paramount to achieving good oral health' and	DHP4 'As my patient my role is the same as any other patient to give the most appropriate advice I can'	DHP22 '...[athletes] should have access to the advice that anyone else has access to'.	DHP15 '...Diet advice is a fairly standard concept, it's tailored to patients on a fairly individual basis.'	DHP22, 'Role is to deliver general diet advice re health and oral hygiene'
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Theme 2: If Athletes are at Increased Risk of Dental Disease

Subtheme 1: I Diet Advice Will Mitigate This

<p>DHP27 ‘Often mention acid erosion and tooth wear in high performing athletes’ and ‘Severe periodontal disease can occur in endurance athletes’</p>	<p>DHP29 ‘Having managed dental care of footballers targeted dietary advice and OHI is of paramount importance as diets were high in sugar and oh poor’</p>	<p>DHP32 ‘...non-athletes can have more concerning diets that athletes due to other many factors but these will also include factors that affect many athletes such as timing and frequency of food intakes, frequency and volume of high sugary intakes, frequency...’</p>	<p>DHP12 said that, ‘high carbohydrate supplements are highly cariogenic’</p>	
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Subtheme 2: Oral Hygiene Instruction Will Mitigate This

<p>DHP21 ‘...making sure the timing of OH measures are appropriate so as not to increase damage’</p>	<p>DHP8 ‘...fluoride advice’</p>	<p>DHP9 ‘To provide OHI with regards to toothbrushing with a fluoride toothpaste if they are consuming high amounts of fluids containing sugars, regular dental check-ups to screen for dental disease and provide preventative advice’.</p>		
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Subtheme 3: Enhanced Prevention Will Mitigate This				
DHP13 'provide enhanced prevention if necessary - e.g higher dose fluoride toothpaste'	DHP10 '...if necessary increase fluoride exposure'	DHP12 '...important that we highlight the potential issues with highly cariogenic sporting diets...caveat that not all athletes are high caries risk, but indeed high carbohydrate supplements are highly cariogenic.'		
Theme 3: I Face Barriers When I Treat Athletes				
DHP17 'Certainly NHS time constraints do have an impact on our ability to deliver services'	DHP2 '...there are not a huge number of professional athletes and for most dentists it is a low priority'.	DHP10 'If someone is on a coach led diet - I wouldn't feel confident changing the diet for sports performance...'	DHP25 ' 'I would be much less comfortable advising an elite athlete as their perspective on dental health vs performance within their sporting activity will be entirely different from a member of the public who has sport as a hobby.'	

6.4.1 Thematic Analysis of Athlete Responses

Theme 1: Missing Sleep and Dropping Out - Dental Disease Impacts Athletes On and Off the Field of Play

Fifteen per cent (10) of respondents stated dental disease had prevented them from carrying out their usual training. This can be compared with the 6-18% of athletes who have previously reported a negative impact of oral health on performance (Chantaramanee *et al.*, 2016; Gallagher *et al.*, 2018). Highlighting that an acute exacerbation of dental disease can remove an athlete from the field of play, A57 had spent, '3 days off work/ no training', while A55, 'once missed a session due to toothache'. A46 had been left, 'Unable to run due to an infection' and A32 spoke of having, '...toothache once which was horrendous and prevented me from training until it was fixed'.

In addition to preventing athletes from training, the effects of dental disease on athletes' sleep patterns, and in particular, the impact of sleep disturbances on performance in training and competition were discussed. A2 spoke of, '...a few times in my athlete life which [dental disease] has affected sleep...meaning I didn't get the best out of a session the next day.' At one point they, 'Had root canal treatment that stopped me training for about a week and hindered me for about a week before the operation'. A42 attributed poor race performance to symptomatic dental disease as, 'Toothache has given me a few consecutive bad night's sleep in the week before a race and I dropped out of the race'. Previous studies have reported an impact of disturbed sleep on sports performance (Fullagar *et al.*, 2015; Kirschen, Jones and Hale, 2020) and, taken with the results from this study could be used to incentivise athletes to maintain good oral health to support performance.

Eighty-eight per cent of elite-level athletes felt that awareness of the potential impacts of dental health on performance would motivate adherence to dentist-recommended behaviours (Gallagher, Ashley and Needleman, 2020). The results of this study provide evidence of the negative effects of dental disease at the sub-elite level and could be further used to emphasise the benefits of carrying out preventative behaviours.

Theme 2: Diet and Dental Advice From Multiple Sources (Not the Dentist)

Seventy per cent (47) of athlete respondents reported training for at least 7 hours a week. Previous studies have associated a greater training volume with an increased risk of dental caries (Frese *et al.*, 2015) and worse oral health-related quality of life (Kragt *et al.*, 2019), suggesting behaviours needed to support a higher training load may increase disease risk.

Over half of athlete respondents indicated intra-activity consumption of sports drinks (66%) or gels (64%). These products support performance but their frequent consumption may lead to poor dental health (Schulze and Busse, 2024). These data can also be compared to the higher proportion (86%) of UK-based elite athletes who report sports nutrition product use during exercise (Gallagher *et al.*, 2019). This increased use of sports nutrition products at higher performance levels may be a contributing factor in the higher dental disease prevalence in elite-level cohorts.

The athletes discussed multiple sources they relied on to inform their dietary choices, including the internet, coaches, other athletes, family, and sports nutritionists. Several respondents indicated they critically appraise information from grey-literature sources. A14 said, 'I'd usually start with blogs on reputable sports websites but then find the underlying peer-reviewed articles to assess the claims, where possible'. However, not all respondents felt they could trust published research. While A41 consulted, 'Scientific studies/papers mainly' they also said that, '...in general I'm quite sceptical of the sports diet industry as I think a lot of it has been influenced by market forces and is over complicated'.

As in previous studies, coaches were discussed as valuable sources of advice (Diehl *et al.*, 2012; Torres-McGehee *et al.*, 2012; Solly *et al.*, 2023). A26 would, '...occasionally get recipes from my coach', while A53 has, '...chats with coach about fuelling during marathon training blocks and races'. This could provide opportunities for an adequately informed coach to encourage food-first nutrition and to provide practical tips to mitigate carbohydrate supplement use (Needleman *et al.*, 2015, 2018) .

Several respondents discussed consulting nutritionists that they knew personally for advice. A61 spoke to their, '...partner (and her friend) who specialises in nutrition' while A30 would seek advice within, 'My training group - one of them is a nutritionist so provides us with what supplements etc to take to help with certain things as well as posting healthy meals on his

Instagram’. Only A31 indicated that their club worked alongside a nutritionist stating, ‘...in my club we work with nutritionist and she gives us advice on what is good to eat and what foods are good for performance’.

Finally, several respondents obtained advice from either peer or elite-level athletes. A60 discussed noting, ‘What other running friends eat/drink’ while A30 said that in the club setting they, ‘...share advice in the group about what gels etc are good and what tastes nice’. A11 relied on advice from, ‘My brother, who is a division I athlete in the US’ and reading, ‘Cookbooks from professional runners (Run Fast Eat Slow - Shalane Flanagan)’ and A12 discussed following advice from, ‘Elite athletes on social media’. There was scepticism regarding the usefulness of information provided by individuals on social media who did not have experience in elite-level sports and A64 said they would, ‘...discount it as most running influencers are not very competitive’.

These findings can be contrasted with the athletes’ responses regarding their dental health behaviours. When asked, 27% (18) respondents indicated they would change their oral health behaviours due to pressures from outside sources. Three respondents said advertisements or posts from influencers made them consider using tooth whitening products and 3 stated that they had used a tooth whitening product as a direct result of something they had seen on social media. Only 1 respondent indicated they had changed their oral health behaviours following advice from their dentist.

6.4.2 Dental Health Behaviours of Athlete Respondents

All respondents reported daily use of fluoride-containing toothpaste. Two used a high-fluoride toothpaste, indicating they have been identified as being at increased dental disease risk (Walsh *et al.*, 2010). There was some evidence that targeted oral hygiene instruction would benefit the respondents as only 28% reported daily interdental cleaning, compared to 56% of elite-level athletes (Gallagher *et al.*, 2019).

To ensure the provision of preventative care, athletes should attend regular dental appointments (Needleman *et al.*, 2018). The dental attendance of this cohort was higher than that reported by elite-level athletes. Thirty-three (49%) had not been seen by a dentist for at least 6 months, compared to 60% of the cohort of Gallagher *et al.*, (2019). Out with the UK, dental attendance

among athletes is also low as a recent report found 79% of professional rugby players had not been seen by a dentist for at least 12 months, compared to 33% (22) of this cohort (Minty *et al.*, 2018). At the sub-elite level, 76% of German endurance athletes reported regular dental attendance (Merle, Richter, *et al.*, 2022). These results may suggest elite-level athletes are more likely to miss dental appointments, resulting in the progression of disease.

6.4.3 Coach and DHP Respondent Demographics

The coach respondents demonstrated high levels of attainment and experience. Seventy-three percent (24) reporting at least 1 athlete they had worked with had achieved a national, or higher, level of representation and 76% (25) stated they had at least 5 years of experience as a coach.

While no DHP respondents indicated they had a special interest in sports dentistry, a high proportion had experience participating in competitive sports (40%) or as a coach (20%). Despite this, only 2 were aware of guidance aimed at dental disease prevention in athletes, with 1 of these respondents only aware of dental trauma prevention guidance.

6.4.4 Thematic Analysis of Coach Responses

Theme 1: The Role of the Coach in the Provision of Diet Advice

The coaches indicated they had a role in providing advice, but used language suggesting that athletes would have to approach them first as illustrated by C21 who stated ‘...I only give advice when asked...’. The coaches indicated nuances within the nutrition advice they provided, focusing on both maintaining good general health and on event-specific nutrition to maximise performance (Thomas, Erdman and Burke, 2016).

Sub-theme 1: Diet Advice for General Health

Many coaches believed their primary role in providing dietary advice was to ensure athletes' general health and well-being. C1 felt that they had a responsibility to, ‘Encourage general self-care of athletes everyday’. C13 would, ‘...recommend a normal healthy diet that is balanced’, and C25 gave ‘...advice to ensure young athletes eat a good balance of all food groups’ and C21 wanted their athletes to ‘...keep to a varied balanced diet to ensure demands of activity’.

Several coach respondents emphasised the importance of athletes consuming sufficient food to support exercise and recovery, summarised by C26 who said athletes, ‘Can’t start a session depleted as quality and quantity will be negatively impacted. Like trying to drive a car with no petrol’ and C25 who said that, ‘Recommending carbs advised after a session...to ensure healthy refuelling and avoidance of any energy deficits’. This suggests that, while relative energy deficiency in sport (RED-S) was only mentioned by name by C14, the coaches were aware that inadequate fuelling can significantly impact well-being and performance (Mountjoy *et al.*, 2018). These findings can be contrasted with some previous studies which suggest coaches are unaware of this condition or that they place greater emphasis on performance compared to long-term health (Frideres, Mottinger and Palao, 2016; Wasserfurth *et al.*, 2020).

Coaches did not feel all foods and beverages were of equal merit. Several advocated for the consumption of complex carbohydrates (described as ‘good carbohydrates’ by several respondents). C29 directed athletes towards, ‘...good healthy sources’ of energy while C25 would, ‘...encourage good carbohydrates in the form of pasta/bread/rice/bananas etc in advance of and after training sessions’. These substances will maintain glycogen stores, benefitting performance (Podlogar and Wallis, 2022). In addition, advising the consumption of whole foods where carbohydrate supplements are not required is recommended to support athlete oral health (Needleman *et al.*, 2018).

Dehydration during progressive exercise impacts performance (Carlton and Orr, 2015) and the coaches primarily advocated for the use of water for rehydration. C25 said they, ‘...don’t currently recommend energy drinks...water all the way!...’ and C12 provided advice for athletes on, ‘what drinks they bring to training, (water only, no energy drink or flavoured drinks)’. This coach advice is again in agreement with expert guidance, which suggests beverages containing sugars should be avoided by athletes where possible (Needleman *et al.*, 2018).

Sub-theme 2: Diet Advice For Sports Performance

Several coaches also discussed the importance of diet in ensuring athletes could perform well in training and competition, summarised by C5 who described diet as ‘...fundamental to optimum performance’. This advice should be personalised as C27 stated the provision of diet advice should be ‘...a very individual 'thing' for each athlete and is different for each athlete’.

The coaches were aware of the importance of tailoring nutrition to an individual and their training load (Thomas, Erdman and Burke, 2016). C14 considered athlete age when providing advice, stating, ‘...they should use steady body weight (if mature) to ensure they consume sufficient calories to cover daily living and training/competition...’. The same respondent recommended carbohydrate supplementation for specific scenarios, ‘For those competing at Half-marathon and beyond (including hill racing) or in heats, semis, etc. I suggest use of gels and sports drinks during long runs and competition.’

C6 stated nutrition should be ‘Dependant on duration and intensity of training’ and C24 acknowledged the increased complexity of planning for longer events, saying they ‘...get more specific when getting into race strategy and how many grams of carbs per hour they should aim for in ultra-endurance events.’. C20 stated the exact quantities of carbohydrate needed to fuel different training intensities, with, ‘3-5g per kg easy days 5-7 g intermediate days 7-10g very hard days’. Other respondents indicated they recommend specific meals or snacks. C2 referred to the consumption of ‘...after sessions milkshakes...’ to support recovery, while C8 suggested ‘...a slice of white bread and even some chocolate...’ pre-session to ‘...prepare and get carbs, protein and fat balance right’.

The coach responses suggested awareness of their possible shortcomings when providing diet advice. Some downplayed the complexity of the information they provided. C33 described giving ‘Just basic advice on fuelling post workout’, while C16 said they ‘...provide very basic advice to my athletes such as make sure you eat and hydrate within 10mins of a training session finishing’. This is despite both respondents indicating the provision of advice specific to training load and duration. C16 felt athlete performance level impacted their ability to provide diet advice meaning they, ‘...would not provide any diet advice for my highest performing athletes as I have no qualifications to do so.’, an attitude shared by several DHPs. Several others would direct athletes elsewhere for advice. C24 said ‘I believe only basic general advice on diet should be advised unless the coach has some specific qualification/training in diet/nutrition and oral health. I myself have no nutrition qualifications so only give out basic diet advice that would be easily available to athletes themselves online’. C2 stated that they had ‘No formal qualifications in nutrition or diet, so therefore would signpost athletes to good sources of information or nutritionist...’ this was to avoid possible harm to their athletes as ‘...too often coaches give out advice that is outdated or wrong that can often cause issues’. These responses are supported by previous studies, which demonstrate coaches have some understanding of

nutrition guidelines, alongside significant gaps in their knowledge, which may result in the provision of inaccurate advice to athletes (Cockburn *et al.*, 2014). C25 was concerned that they were in a position where they could inadvertently harm their athletes. They said ‘...I don’t want to go too heavy on diet advice other than a healthy balance etc trying to avoid too much focus on food ...’. Instead C25 coach aimed to ‘...help young athletes develop good relationships with diet’.

Theme 2: Trusted Sources of Information Provide the Best Advice

The coaches indicated they relied on several trusted sources to inform the advice they delivered or to educate their athletes directly. There was some overlap with the sources mentioned by athletes and DHPs.

Sports nutritionists provide specialist, events-specific guidance and were mentioned most often as a group coaches might consult. C20 delivered, ‘...advice about balanced diets, cho for easy/intermediate/hard days... Discussed at length with sports nutritionist’ and C10 stated, ‘We [Their athletics club] have a nutritionist who guides us what is appropriate at different stages of their training throughout the year’.

Elite athletes were noted as a useful source of practical information for athletes. C18 said they would ‘Usually direct them to the advice in a book (Pfitzinger) and recommend Eat Slow Run Fast cookbook’. Both books were written by successful athletes (professional marathon runner and sports physiologist Peter Pfitzinger and coach and former professional marathon runner Shalane Flanagan).

Almost 80% of the coaches had experience of participation in competitive sports. However, only C14 indicated their ‘...experience of the use of carbohydrate drinks and gels’ would influence the advice they provided. There was also evidence coaches relied on experience gained outside of sport, with C26 informed by their, ‘...background in physiology and public health’ and C14 referring to courses they had attended on the prevention of eating disorders and RED-S.

Theme 3: The Perceived Role (or Lack Thereof) of the Coach in Dental Health.

Less than a third of coach respondents felt they had a role in preventing dental disease in athletes, in contrast with the 94% (31) and 82% (27) who felt they had a role delivering diet advice relating to general health and wellbeing or sports performance.

Despite this, some coaches did indicate they had some responsibility for their athletes' dental health. C32 felt they had a, 'Major role as with other health issues. We want our athletes to be able to train and compete to their best. This involves being medically and dentally fit. We also have a duty of care - 'do no harm'. This includes teeth and dental issues.'. A minority of coaches would also provide dental health advice. C21 was aware that occlusion affects postural stability (Maurer *et al.*, 2015; Leroux *et al.*, 2018) and would '...comment on dental health regarding the jaw influencing balance' and C30 they would, 'consider providing basic advice regards diet and oral health'. Coaches like these may benefit from being signposted to educational resources on dental disease prevention, to ensure they can effectively support their athletes.

Other respondents indicated a possible role in dental disease prevention had not occurred to them. C13, '...had not considered it before' and C22 said, '...I must confess I've never thought about my role in relation to dental health'. Encouragingly, no coach indicated opposition to taking on a role in athlete-specific dental disease prevention.

Many responses suggest coaches do not currently consider themselves able to effectively support athlete oral health. In addition, both participant responses and the existing literature suggest coach expertise in the delivery of advice relating to general health, and sports performance is limited (Cockburn *et al.*, 2014). Despite this, it should be noted that several coaches already include recommendations to reduce unnecessary exposure to cariogenic substances as part of their basic "general" health advice.

Directing coaches towards pre-existing educational material (Eastman Dental Institute, 2017; World Dental Federation, 2019a; World Dental Federation, 2019b), developed to be understandable to the layperson, could help strengthen this approach. Although advice provided by coaches would never replace the tailored preventive care offered by DHPs, it may be feasible to integrate coaches into a broader network who support athlete oral health. This network could also include support team members such as nutritionists, upskilled to deliver simple, practical guidance to promote healthy oral habits among athletes.

6.4.5 Thematic Analysis of DHP Responses

Theme 1: Patient Education is Paramount to Achieving Good Oral Health - The Role of the DHP in the Provision of Diet Advice.

Oral health advice helps patients understand dental disease prevention (NICE, 2015). DHP32 said, 'Patient education is paramount to achieving good oral health' while DHP15 said their role, '...comes down to educating the individuals if they demonstrate a lack of knowledge or errors in oral hygiene'. Once this advice was delivered, the DHPs indicated that further responsibility fell upon the patient. DHP5 stated that disease prevention was '...patients responsibility with ownership of care', DHP2 said they must, '...allow them to make their own decisions' and DHP28 said, '...whilst I am responsible for giving advice ultimately the overall responsibility lies with the individual...'. This means both coaches and DHPs feel they have a role delivering diet advice which individual athletes must decide to act upon.

Previous studies show that DHPs appreciate patients following their advice, with poor adherence a source of frustration (Barnes, Bullock and Chestnutt, 2022). DHP13 indicated some athletes did not prioritise their dental health, speaking of, 'Patients refusing to take on board information, for example, those who do ultra-marathons and who don't have the weight to pack a toothbrush and toothpaste for that time so have a week of gels, and no fluoride'. While the performance level of the athlete in question is not known, this contrasts with the results of Gallagher, Ashley and Needleman, (2020) who found elite-level athletes amenable to behavioural change to support their dental health.

Some respondents indicated exercise training status would not alter the care they provided. DHP4 felt, 'As my patient my role is the same as any other patient to give the most appropriate advice I can' and DHP22 said they believed athletes, '...should have access to the advice that anyone else has access to'. Some DHPs indicated they provide generic diet advice, despite sports nutrition guidance recommending an athlete's diet must account for an individual's training load (Thomas, Erdman and Burke, 2016). DHP19 would, '...give the same diet advice regarding frequency of sugar intake to all patients' and DHP5 felt their advice was '...the same for any patient'. This may mean that some athletes do not receive personalised preventative advice. However, other respondents did emphasise the importance of providing individualised

advice, including DHP15 who stated that while, ‘...Diet advice is a fairly standard concept, it’s tailored to patients on a fairly individual basis.’

Although DHPs are expected to deliver general health advice, barriers to providing this advice have previously been reported, including a lack of training, remuneration and time (Henderson, 2015; O’Kane *et al.*, 2024). Contrasting with the coaches, fewer DHPs indicated they provide diet advice for general health. However, DHP22 indicated they felt that their, ‘Role is to deliver general diet advice re health and oral hygiene’ and DHP27 said they ‘Will often mention importance of a balanced diet...’ to patients involved in sports as, from their experience, dental disease, ‘often correlates with other general health issues such as lack of periods’ among these patients.

Theme 2: If Athletes are at Increased Risk of Dental Disease

Previous studies suggest an increased risk of dental disease among elite-level athletes (Needleman *et al.*, 2016; Gallagher *et al.*, 2018; Minty *et al.*, 2018; Kragt *et al.*, 2019). However, many DHPs would not automatically consider an athlete as being at high risk of dental disease without a clinical examination.

Subtheme 1: I Diet Advice Will Mitigate This

Several respondents had experience treating patients involved in elite-level sports, suggesting this experience influenced their practice. DHP31, ‘Particularly noted patients who are professional swimmers likely to be increased caries risk due to high consumption of sugary drinks’ and DHP27 said they, ‘Often mention acid erosion and tooth wear in high performing athletes’ and that, ‘Severe periodontal disease can occur in endurance athletes’. Needleman *et al.*, (2016) recorded poor oral health among football players and DHP29 stated ‘Having managed dental care of footballers targeted dietary advice and OHI is of paramount importance as diets were high in sugar and oh poor’. However, DHP32 believed that, although athletes consume sugar as part of their diet, this did not mean they were at increased risk compared to the general population as, ‘...non-athletes can have more concerning diets than athletes due to other many factors but these will also include factors that affect many athletes such as timing and frequency of food intakes, frequency and volume of high sugary intakes, frequency and method of using oral care products’.

The frequent consumption of carbohydrate supplementation could be implicated in an increased risk of dental disease in athletes (Moynihan and Kelly, 2014). DHP25 expressed apprehension over the, 'high sugar content of gels and sports drinks' and DHP10 felt they must, 'highlight links between hydration drinks/carb gels to dental diseases'. There was a feeling that carbohydrate supplementation could increase the risk of dental caries in particular as DHP33 linked, 'high carbohydrate drinks and risk of dental caries' and DHP12 said that, 'high carbohydrate supplements are highly cariogenic'.

Reducing the time spent exposing the teeth to acidic conditions was also a priority. DHP10 noted a risk of, '...mouth guards reducing saliva buffering and holding sugars against teeth...' and DHP14 discussed the, 'consequences of high frequency intake of high energy products...' leading to, 'increased erosion and decay associated with these products' as a consequence of their low pH (Erdemir *et al.*, 2016).

There was acknowledgement from several DHPs that carbohydrate supplementation might sometimes be unavoidable, but that athletes should aim to minimise its usage. DHP31 said, 'I understand it is difficult however as they are wishing to get maximum performance' while DHP26 suggested athletes find a, 'Balance between the need for energy and the need to reduce frequency and amount of sugar' and DHP21 wanted athletes to consider, 'mitigating the danger of what they are required to consume'. Ensuring athletes and DHPs are aware of inter-exercise mitigation strategies would effectively reduce disease risk where possible.

Subtheme 2: Oral Hygiene Instruction Will Mitigate This

DHPs should also advise patients on oral hygiene, including the use of fluoride dentifrices and proper techniques for toothbrushing and interdental cleaning (SDCEP, 2012, 2024; Public Health England, 2021). DHP29 described this advice as being, 'of paramount importance'. DHP21 advised, '...making sure the timing of OH measures are appropriate so as not to increase damage' and DHP15 would take corrective action if a patient was to, '...demonstrate a lack of knowledge or errors in oral hygiene...'. DHP8 would provide, '...fluoride advice' and DHP9 felt they had a responsibility, 'To provide OHI with regards to toothbrushing with a fluoride toothpaste if they are consuming high amounts of fluids containing sugars, regular dental check-ups to screen for dental disease and provide preventative advice'.

Subtheme 3: Enhanced Prevention Will Mitigate This

Expert guidance recommends the use of high-concentration fluoride toothpaste, of at least 2800 ppm, when carbohydrate supplementation is used regularly and suggests a fluoride mouthwash may also be appropriate (Needleman *et al.*, 2018). DHP13 said that they, ‘provide enhanced prevention if necessary - e.g higher dose fluoride toothpaste’ and DHP10 would, ‘...if necessary increase fluoride exposure’. DHP12 thought it was, ‘...important that we highlight the potential issues with highly cariogenic sporting diets’ but would, ‘caveat that not all athletes are high caries risk, but indeed high carbohydrate supplements are highly cariogenic.’. This may have influenced responses to other parts of the questionnaire, making DHPs unwilling to assume increased dental disease risk in a hypothetical athlete patient compared to the rest of the population.

Theme 3: I Face Barriers When I Treat Athletes

Previous studies highlight common barriers in the provision of preventive dental care to the general population. These include a lack of time, funding shortages, the perception that prevention is not an efficient use of clinical time, and poor patient adherence to preventative advice (Leggett *et al.*, 2024). Many of these barriers were also discussed by the respondents of this study.

Accurate assessment of the lifestyle and dietary factors that influence dental disease risk, followed by tailored advice, requires significant clinical time. DHP23, 24, 29 and 31 all stated, ‘time’ was a barrier to their provision of preventative care. A lack of time when working specifically as an NHS dentist was mentioned by DHP17 who said, ‘Certainly NHS time constraints do have an impact on our ability to deliver services’ and by DHP18 who had concerns over, ‘NHS zero time with patient’.

As athletes comprise a minority of patients, providing specific preventative care to this group was not a priority for respondents. DHP6 said, ‘I don’t ask if people are athletes’ and stated it was, ‘Not routinely within my history to even ask if they’re an athlete’ while DHP2 said, ‘...there are not a huge number of professional athletes and for most dentists it is a low priority’. Responses to this survey also suggest athletes have a role prompting the dental team to ensure they receive tailored preventative advice. DHP15 said, ‘...I’m not going to be asking questions like “are you a professional or aspiring professional athlete” as part of a new patient examination...’ and DHP23 said, ‘Time with patients is very limited. This information [what

carbohydrate supplementation is used] would need to be from the patients'. Pickering *et al.*, (2020) have previously suggested athletes inform the dental team of involvement in contact sports to ensure they receive appropriate advice regarding mouthguard provision.

Several DHPs felt uncomfortable contradicting other members of the athlete support team, with DHP10 stating, 'If someone is on a coach led diet - I wouldn't feel confident changing the diet for sports performance...'. Performance level impacted on how comfortable DHP25 felt delivering advice saying, 'There is a huge difference in giving advice to elite sportspeople and joggers competing in the local park run. I would feel entirely comfortable advising the latter, but the former may well have professional coaches and all the other facilities including dieticians working with them to maximise their sporting abilities. I would be much less comfortable advising an elite athlete as their perspective on dental health vs performance within their sporting activity will be entirely different from a member of the public who has sport as a hobby.'. While other professions provide diet advice, dental health is not their primary focus (Kingsnorth *et al.*, 2021), making the preventative advice from the dental team valuable for all athletes.

Athlete oral health was an unfamiliar topic for the respondents, with DHP3 saying, 'This is not a subject I am familiar with'. DHP33 indicated they felt there was a, 'Lack of CPD and guidance' on this topic, while DHP 2 said, 'I have never attended a formal course in this...'. As a result, the respondents felt they possessed insufficient knowledge on the topic, with DHP30 saying, 'I don't feel I have been well trained or equipped to specifically give oral health advice specifically to athletes.'

Some respondents were unsure what the use of carbohydrate supplementation would entail. DHP3 was interested in, '...learning more about the supplements' and DHP9 wished to know, '...a bit more about what athletes require to perform and train and what these supplements contain'. Raising awareness on the contents and use of carbohydrate supplementation would allow the dental team to advise against their use unless strictly necessary and enable the provision of practical mitigation advice.

DHP25 indicated their participation had prompted them to consider how they could better treat athlete patients saying, 'Since having conversations around this area with colleagues following talking to you, I have done further reading and hopefully now have a bit better understanding

of my role from preventative point of view.’ Other respondents stated they would be unable to prioritise athlete dental health, with DHP2 saying, ‘I think courses would be useful but there are not a huge number of professional athletes and for most dentists it is a low priority’.

Theme 4: Trusted Sources of Information Provide the Best Advice

The DHPs indicated they relied on specific information sources to direct their actions. The DHPs appeared to place great emphasis on how they used their personal experience to inform their practice, as described below.

Some DHPs indicated that their participation in competitive sports provided them with useful information that could be used to direct advice given to athletes. DHP33 had, ‘General personal experience of high carbohydrate drinks and risk of dental caries’ and DHP14 had, ‘Some personal experience of endurance cycling events’ and DHP4 had, ‘...knowledge of athletes diet through personal experience...’ and they would, ‘...use that to help with my advice I offered’. It is also feasible that DHPs who have previously treated athletes become better equipped to treat similar patients. DHP2 said, ‘...most of my knowledge comes from having patients that are professional athletes and trying to help them’. Previous experience with swimmers and footballers meant that DHP31 and DHP29 felt they could highlight dental disease risk factors specific to these groups. Swimmers were, ‘...likely to be increased caries risk due to high consumption of sugary drinks’ while footballers’, ‘...diets were high in sugar and oh poor’. Conversely, DHPs with no experience with competitive sports may be less able to provide targeted dental care to athlete groups.

DHP23’s treatment of athletes was informed by CPD as, ‘Courses have shown high tooth wear and caries so fluoride toothpaste and regular recall is important’. DHPs have a professional obligation to carry out CPD (General Dental Council, 2018) but the demands of clinical practice mean CPD completion must be pragmatic (Brown and Wassif, 2017). DHP2 was reluctant to attend CPD to support the treatment of a small number of patients, saying, ‘I think courses would be useful but there are not a huge number of professional athletes and for most dentists it is a low priority’.

6.4.6 Knowledge Levels of Athletes, Coaches and DHPs

While guidance on preventative care in preventative sports is available (Eastman Dental Institute, 2017; World Dental Federation, 2019a, 2019b, 2019c, 2019d) awareness of these resources was low among all three groups. There was also limited awareness of the increased risk of dental disease in competitive sports.

No significant difference was detected in the knowledge levels of athletes and coaches regarding dental disease prevention in competitive sports. A significant difference was found in the proportion of correct responses to Q10 with coaches unlikely to provide advice regarding the use of fluoride-containing toothpaste to their athletes. The limited role coaches perceived they had in athlete dental health may explain why they would not provide this advice. The coaches did strongly feel they had a role maintaining overall health and supporting performance. Highlighting the impact of poor oral health on both areas may motivate coaches to take a more active role supporting athlete oral health.

DHPs indicated they would not consider athletes as being at an increased risk of dental disease without clinical assessment, possibly culminating in a reluctance to provide enhanced prevention. In addition, a lack of awareness of the contents of carbohydrate supplements and a lack of confidence contradicting the rest of the athlete support team may have impacted on the DHPs' responses. Educating this group to enable them to discourage the use of carbohydrate supplementation where no other alternatives are available would support realistic behavioural change by athletes.

6.4.7 Strengths and Weaknesses

The mixed-methods study design allowed for the collection and analysis of qualitative and quantitative data. The quantitative data allowed the research team to identify gaps in the knowledge while the thematic analysis assessed why respondents reached their conclusions and suggested all 3 groups were unaware of the existence of supporting guidance.

Previous studies report on the actions of dentists working with sports teams (McGovern, Spolarich and Keim, 2015) or on interventions delivered by dentists with an interest in competitive sports (Gallagher, Ashley and Needleman, 2020). The mixture of private and NHS DHPs represents dental team members who athletes, especially at the sub-elite level, might be

more likely to encounter. However, despite not being the only member of the dental team to deliver preventative advice, all but 1 of DHP respondents were dentists.

While encompassing most of the steps required, the questionnaire development did not formally follow the knowledge transfer system framework (Vernhagen *et al.*, 2013). Additionally, no athletes without dental qualifications were involved in the initial questionnaire design and no nutritionists were consulted throughout the study. This may have reduced the effectiveness of the questionnaire and impacted on its implementation, contributing to the non-diverse sample.

An anonymous online questionnaire allows for convenient data collection and may mean respondents are more comfortable providing honest answers. However, a degree of social desirability bias, where the provided responses are more reflective of how the respondent wishes to be perceived, may have been unavoidable (Podsakoff *et al.*, 2003). For example, in club-level athletics in the UK, sports nutritionists are not regularly employed, due to limited resources. Despite this, multiple athlete and coach respondents indicated sports nutritionists supported their decision-making. During the piloting, respondents were keen to elaborate on their views to a greater extent than that offered on the online questionnaire. Following reflection on this, it is likely that other research methods, such as focus groups or one-to-one interviews, may have increased the depth of the qualitative analysis. However, these methods are resource and time intensive and require the involvement of a specially trained researcher, while the online questionnaire enabled rapid data collection in a short time frame. In addition, starting to develop a network to enable co-production could have strengthened future research in this area, as well as supporting this project. This would allow multiple stakeholders to collaborate to design, deliver, and evaluate future projects to support athlete oral health.

While an effort was made to avoid introducing bias via the use of leading questions, the questionnaire contents, particularly those referring to the provision of advice, will inevitably have directed some responses. Patient education in isolation fails to support persistent behaviour change (O'Malley *et al.*, 2016), so oral health promotion instead focuses on behaviour change interventions (O'Malley *et al.*, 2016, Carr and Ebert, 2012). These interventions are guided by behavioural change frameworks, which aim to integrate multiple, often overlapping, behaviour change theories to streamline and guide the development of evidence-based behaviour change interventions. The COM-B model, used by Gallagher,

Ashley and Needleman, 2020, is one example of a behavioural change framework. This model explains that a behaviour is comprised of three interrelated factors – capability, opportunity and motivation. To support a successful oral health behavioural change, an individual must possess the physical skills and knowledge needed to carry out the behaviour. They should also possess any equipment necessary and feel comfortable in their social environment, granting them the opportunity to carry out any necessary tasks. Finally, they must feel motivated to alter their current behaviours to support their oral health (Michie *et al.*, 2011). Several DHPs indicated that they would provide advice or demonstrations to increase athlete capability. However, in addition to this, loss aversion was previously found to be a suitable motivator for an elite athlete cohort (Gallagher, Ashley and Needleman, 2020) and could be capitalised on by the athlete support team to encourage adherence by athletes, with similar advice already provided as part of injury prevention.

Most athlete and coach respondents were involved in individual endurance disciplines. While a recent report suggested athletes involved in individual sports have worse oral health compared to those involved in team sports (de la Parte *et al.*, 2021), further studies may wish to consider individuals involved in team sports, where supplementation and training demands may be different.

Coaches work closely with athletes and see them regularly, so the research team felt there was a rationale for investigating their willingness to deliver preventative advice. Multiple athletes and coaches indicated they consult with sports nutritionists, who may also be a suitable target group to promote athlete oral health.

As convenience sampling was used to recruit respondents it is feasible that athletes who felt their dental health had impacted their sports performance or coaches who felt they had a role in maintaining athlete well-being were more likely to respond. This may have introduced selection bias to the results. Furthermore, a large proportion of DHPs indicated they had competitive sports experience. This may mean the results disproportionately represent DHPs who have a greater interest in sports, so are more likely to be willing to provide targeted care to any athletes they treat in practice. In addition, all three groups were non-ethnically diverse and, while most coach respondents were male, a greater proportion of DHP and athlete respondents were female. While attempts were made to gather demographic information from

sports' governing bodies regarding the demographics of their athlete and coach members, this information could not be obtained due to updates in membership data storage methods. As a result, the generalisability of the results should be interpreted with caution. Finally, while an effort was made to contact a mixture of DHPs using social media, the questionnaire was also shared via email to staff at Glasgow Dental Hospital and School. This email list will include staff who are likely to make an active effort to engage with resources aimed at encouraging prevention of dental diseases via patient behavioural change. As a result, it is feasible that their responses are not representative of the views held by all UK-based DHPs.

6.5 Conclusion

This study reveals that athletes and coaches primarily involved in endurance sports in Scotland have limited knowledge regarding dental disease prevention in the competitive sports environment. Additionally, it reveals that a sample of DHPs, mainly working at a teaching hospital in Glasgow, have limited awareness of the risks of dental disease in competitive sports. Notably, only 2 DHP respondents were aware of resources to support dental disease prevention among athlete groups.

The athletes reported they carried out some behaviours beneficial to their oral health. However, they also indicated regular consumption of carbohydrate supplementation and dental disease had impacted the sports performance of 15% of respondents. Coaches felt their role in preventing dental disease was limited but would provide advice to support general health, well-being, and sports performance. The DHPs indicated they apply the same principles of preventative care to all patients, regardless of exercise training status and that they experienced multiple barriers when treating patients involved in competitive sports. Increasing the awareness of existing educational resources, aimed at athletes and their support teams may represent an effective way to further support dental disease prevention in the competitive sports environment.

7. Chapter 7 General Discussion

7.1 Introduction

This PhD aimed to determine the impact of periodontal treatment and exercise training on NO availability and on the composition of the oral microbiome, using next generation 16S rRNA sequencing. This allowed specific attention to be placed on analysis of changes in the relative abundance of species known to contribute to oral NO₂⁻ production. In addition, a mixed-methods study design was used to assess the knowledge, beliefs and attitudes of athletes and their support teams on oral health support, allowing closer exploration of areas where dental disease prevention could be improved in the competitive sports environment.

Studies 1, 2 and 3 suggest that the successful treatment of periodontitis and the completion of regular aerobic exercise training increases the relative abundance of health-associated bacteria. Of note, these include species known to effectively contribute to NO₂⁻ production, such as *R. mucilaginosa*. In addition, while periodontal treatment did not change salivary NO₃⁻ and NO₂⁻ levels, exercise training appeared to impact physiological NO cycling, altering NO₃⁻ and NO₂⁻ bioavailability in the saliva, plasma and muscle. Finally, Study 4 suggested that further educational interventions could reduce the risk of dental disease development in the competitive sports environment. As a result, this thesis significantly increases understanding of the impact of changes to the oral environment on the NO₂⁻-producing microbiome across multiple oral sites and highlights the possible impacts of exercise training on oral health.

This chapter aims to summarise the key findings from this thesis, explain the significance of these findings and outline future directions for subsequent research. Strengths and limitations of the included studies will also be discussed.

7.2 Summary of Main Findings

7.2.1 Study 1

The aims of Study 1 were 1) to determine the impact of successful treatment of periodontitis on the NO₂⁻-producing microbiome of the subgingival plaque throughout post-treatment biofilm reformation and 2) to determine the impact of successful treatment of periodontitis on salivary NO₃⁻ and NO₂⁻ levels.

Hypothesis 1 - Relative to baseline, the NO₂⁻-producing microbiome would increase in relative abundance once periodontal healing and subgingival biofilm reformation was complete.

Accepted

Hypothesis 2 relating to Aim 1- Relative to baseline, the NO₂⁻-producing microbiome would increase in relative abundance at earlier post-treatment timepoints.

Accepted

Hypothesis 3 relating to Aim 2 - Following successful treatment and completion of periodontal healing, salivary NO₃⁻ and NO₂⁻ levels would be found to increase relative to baseline.

Rejected

7.2.2 Study 2

The aims of Study 2 were to determine the impact of a change from a sedentary lifestyle to carrying out weekly HIIT, sufficient to meet WHO guidelines for minimum aerobic exercise levels, in a group of healthy males, on 1) NO₃⁻ and NO₂⁻ levels in the saliva, plasma, and muscle and 2) the composition of the microbiome of the tongue dorsum.

Hypothesis 1 - Regular HIIT would alter the efficiency of both endogenous and exogenous NO production. As a result, changes in NO₃⁻ and NO₂⁻ levels would be observed in all three of the sampled substances following a period of exercise training. After returning to baseline activity levels, these changes would be reversed.

Accepted for plasma NO₃⁻ and for salivary, plasma and muscle NO₂⁻

Rejected for salivary and muscle NO₃⁻

Hypothesis 2 - Regular HIIT would significantly alter the composition of the tongue dorsum microbiome.

Accepted at the ASV level

Hypothesis 2 - Regular HIIT would significantly increase the relative abundance of known NO₂⁻-producing bacteria of the tongue dorsum microbiome.

Accepted

7.2.3 Study 3

The aims of Study 3 were to determine the impact of long-term aerobic exercise training, aiming to improve performance during competitive sports 1) on NO_3^- and NO_2^- levels in the saliva and plasma in healthy humans, 2) on the tongue dorsum microbiome and 3) on the supragingival plaque microbiome in healthy humans.

Hypothesis 1 - Long-term training to improve performance in competitive sports would be associated with an increase in the efficiency of both endogenous and exogenous NO production. As a result, elevated NO_3^- and NO_2^- levels would be observed in the plasma and saliva of trained participants.

Accepted for salivary NO_3^- and NO_2^- and for plasma NO_2^-

Rejected for plasma NO_3^-

Hypothesis 2 - The consistent completion of regular exercise training would be associated with alterations in the composition of the oral microbiome at both sampled sites.

Accepted for the tongue dorsum microbiome

Rejected for the supragingival plaque microbiome

Hypothesis 3 - The consistent completion of regular exercise training would be associated with an increase in the relative abundance of known NO_2^- -producing bacteria of the tongue dorsum microbiome.

Accepted

Hypothesis 4 - The consistent completion of regular exercise training would be associated with an increase in the relative abundance of disease-associated bacteria in the supragingival plaque.

Rejected

7.2.4 Study 4

The aims of Study 4 were to assess the knowledge, beliefs and attitudes of 1) athletes, 2) coaches and 3) non-specialist DHPs regarding oral health support in individuals who train for competitive sports.

Hypothesis 1 - Neither dental healthcare professionals nor sports coaches would feel equipped to deliver targeted dental disease prevention to individuals who train for competitive sports.

Accepted for coaches (Conditional to the study sample)

Rejected for some DHPs (Conditional to the study sample)

Hypothesis 2 - Both dental healthcare professionals and sports coaches would feel that a lack of knowledge was a significant barrier in the delivery of advice targeting dental disease prevention in individuals who train for competitive sports.

Accepted (Conditional to the study sample)

Hypothesis 3 relating to Aims 1 and 3 - Athletes would have received general preventative dental advice and care from the dental team.

Accepted (Conditional to the study sample)

Hypothesis 4 - Athletes would not have received any sort of preventative dental advice from their coaches.

Accepted (Conditional to the study sample)

7.3 Exercise Training, But Not Periodontal Treatment Impacts on Salivary NO₃⁻ and NO₂⁻ Levels

An emerging body of evidence suggests that increasing oral NO₃⁻ and NO₂⁻ availability could encourage the development of an oral microbiota which is resilient to dysbiosis (Rosier et al., 2022). While the impacts of dietary interventions on the concentration of NO metabolites in saliva had been well explored, the effects of other interventions had not been explored in detail. Salivary NO₃⁻ and NO₂⁻ levels were quantified at all timepoints in Studies 1, 2 and 3 and the average values for these metabolites across all 3 studies are shown in Table 7-1.

Table 7-1: The group mean \pm SD for salivary NO metabolites. The values are displayed for each timepoint or group for Studies 1, 2 and 3. No statistically significant differences were found between baseline and the post-treatment timepoints in Study 1. Statistically significant differences between the ‘trained’ and ‘untrained’ conditions in Studies 2 and 3 are indicated using asterixis. * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$.

Study	Timepoint or Group	Salivary NO ₃ ⁻ (μM)	Salivary NO ₂ ⁻ (μM)
1	Baseline	640.5 \pm 258	215.5 \pm 187.5
	Day-1 Post-Treatment	636.3 \pm 353.5	174.6 \pm 212.7
	Day-7 Post-Treatment	654.1 \pm 356.1	225.9 \pm 247.0
	Day-90 Post-Treatment	629.6 \pm 280.6	161.9 \pm 134.5
2	Baseline	496.5 \pm 433.0	82.5 \pm 60.2*
	Post-Training	604.1 \pm 387.4	169.8 \pm 87.9
	Post-Detraining	505.3 \pm 307.6	81.8 \pm 43.1**
3	Trained	590.9 \pm 556.9	121.8 \pm 69.2
	Untrained	210.7 \pm 154.5**	63.6 \pm 34.8*

No evidence was found of an increase in salivary NO₃⁻ and NO₂⁻ following periodontal treatment. In contrast, the results of Studies 2 and 3 suggest that participating in regular exercise training (for at least 8 weeks) increases oral NO metabolite levels. Salivary NO₂⁻ levels increased following the HIIT intervention in Study 2 and decreased following detraining. Significantly higher levels of salivary NO₃⁻ and NO₂⁻ were then observed in the trained individuals of Study 3. No difference was detected in oral NO₂⁻ production capacity between trained and untrained individuals, suggesting exercise training does not augment oral NO₂⁻ production capacity at rest. However, the conditions under which NO is oxidised to NO₃⁻ and NO₂⁻ in the mouth are unclear, so further research is needed to determine the origin of these metabolites in the saliva of trained individuals.

7.4 Other Impacts of Periodontal Treatment and Exercise Training on the Oral Microenvironment

The periodontal treatment provided in Study 1 dramatically decreased the quantity of dental plaque and reduced the oral inflammatory load. This meant that, while the salivary NO₃⁻ and NO₂⁻ levels remained unchanged, the environment of the periodontal pocket was still altered dramatically. The conditions at the later timepoints were less favourable to the inflamophilic

periodontitis-associated microbiome and more amenable to health-associated NO_2^- -producing species, almost certainly contributing to the microbiome changes (Mira, Simon-Soro and Curtis, 2017; Rosier, Marsh and Mira, 2018).

When resting salivary pH was measured in Study 3, no significant difference was detected between the trained and untrained groups. However, dehydration, elevated salivary lactate, pH changes, and the use of sports supplements during exercise, reported in Studies 3 and 4 as well as by previous athlete cohorts (Gallagher *et al.*, 2019), should still be considered as potential contributing factors to the heightening dental disease risk seen in competitive sports.

7.5 Exercise Training Alters Systemic NO_3^- and NO_2^- Levels

Plasma NO_3^- and NO_2^- were quantified in both chapters examining the effects of exercise training on human NO cycling. The average values for these metabolites are shown in Table 7-2. Previous data suggests an increased concentration of NO_3^- (Arefirad *et al.*, 2022) and NO_2^- (Rassaf *et al.*, 2007) in the plasma of trained individuals. Evidence that exercise training enhances NO bioavailability in skeletal muscle has also been found in some (Calvert *et al.*, 2011; Cocks *et al.*, 2013), but not all studies (Majerczak *et al.*, 2024). The research in this thesis did not find a consistent impact of exercise training on the concentration of either metabolite in the plasma. In Study 2 a significant decrease in plasma NO_2^- levels was observed following 8 weeks of thrice weekly HIIT, with a corresponding increase after detraining. In contrast, the trained participants of Study 3 demonstrated higher levels of plasma NO_2^- compared to the controls. Plasma NO_3^- increased following HIIT in study 2, again decreasing after the detraining period, while no difference was detected between the trained group of Study 3 when compared to the untrained controls. Levels of NO metabolites in the muscle were only measured in Study 2. The drop in NO_2^- levels mirrored results observed in rats following 8 weeks of HIIT (Majerczak *et al.*, 2024), suggesting the conversion of NO_2^- to NO to support aerobic exercise in both humans and rodents.

It is feasible that the HIIT depleted NO_2^- stores, with insufficient dietary NO_3^- intake and endogenous NO production to restore these to pre-training levels. In addition, exposure to UV radiation results in NOS-independent release of NO stores from the skin (Liu *et al.*, 2014; Monaghan *et al.*, 2018), resulting in links between seasonal sunlight exposure and increased systemic NO_2^- availability (Liddle *et al.*, 2022). Much of the exercise carried out by the trained

group of Study 3 took place outdoors, which may have increased plasma NO₂⁻ levels. Furthermore, the duration of the intervention used during Study 2 was far shorter than the time the trained cohort of Study 3 had spent exercising to improve their competitive performance. The nuances of the physiological adaptations to NO storage in response to exercise training are not yet fully understood. This means it is plausible that a longer period of consistent training (exceeding 6 months in Study 3 compared to 8 weeks in Study 2), combined with the higher training volume (exceeding 6 hours per week in Study 3, compared to ~75 minutes per week in Study 2), further impacted on endogenous NO cycling.

Table 7-2: The group mean ± SD for plasma NO metabolites. The values are displayed for each timepoint or group for Studies 2 and 3. Statistically significant differences between the ‘trained’ and ‘untrained’ conditions are indicated using asterixis * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$.

Study	Timepoint or Group	Plasma NO ₃ ⁻ (μM)	Plasma NO ₂ ⁻ (nM)
2	Baseline	21.3 ± 9.9	311.2 ± 162.2
	Post-Training	35.4 ± 21.8	129.5 ± 60.4*
	Post-Detraining	25.5 ± 16.3	183.2 ± 65.8**
3	Trained	17.1 ± 8.0	233.6 ± 113
	Untrained	13.7 ± 4.0	97.3 ± 38.2**

7.6 Changes to the Oral Microbiome as a Result of Environmental Changes

As previously described, periodontal treatment and regular exercise training modified the oral microenvironment. These changes were accompanied by alterations to the oral microbiome composition, with increases in the relative abundance of specific NO₂⁻-producing species.

Longitudinal changes in the NO₂⁻-producing microbiome following periodontal treatment had not been investigated prior to Study 1. The significant increase in NO₂⁻-producing bacteria following tissue healing has since been observed across multiple cohorts (Rosier *et al.*, 2024). This suggests these bacteria consistently increase in relative abundance when the oral microenvironment shifts from the inflamophilic, anaerobic environment of untreated disease to the conditions seen in stable disease.

A combination of factors is likely to contribute to the increase in NO₂⁻-producing species and to the negative association between these bacteria and periodontitis-associated species. Oral

inflammation is associated with decreases in NO₂⁻-producing bacteria (Joshi *et al.*, 2014; Corrêa *et al.*, 2019; Huang *et al.*, 2021), suggesting sensitivity to the inflammatory response. Periodontitis-associated species also demonstrate sensitivity to NO (Backlund *et al.*, 2015), so the metabolic activity of the NO₂⁻-producing microbiome may impair their growth.

The findings of Studies 2 and 3 suggest that regular aerobic exercise training is associated with alterations to the microbiome of the tongue dorsum, previously assessed as being home to the most efficient NO₂⁻-producing microbiome (Doel *et al.*, 2005). While the filter paper discs previously used may have overestimated the NO₃⁻-reduction capacity of the tongue dorsum compared to that of other oral sites, of the 9 species which increased in relative abundance post-HIIT, 5 have previously demonstrated NO₂⁻-production capacity, including *R. mucilaginosa*. In Study 3, exercise training was associated with alterations to the overall composition of the tongue dorsum microbiome and with an increased abundance of 2 species, again, including *R. mucilaginosa*. The consistent increases in *R. mucilaginosa* are suggestive that the relative abundance of this species on the tongue dorsum could be used as a marker of aerobic fitness level and should be considered by subsequent studies examining the impact of exercise training on oral health. As there are questions regarding the validity of the conclusions of Doel *et al.*, (2005), there is a rationale for further examining the oral NO₂⁻-production capacity and the microbiome composition across multiple oral sites, to determine if other effective health-associated NO₂⁻-producing species increase in abundance at other oral niches following exercise training.

While increases in oral NO bioavailability may be partially responsible for these changes, other oral environmental impacts of exercise training should be considered. For example, increases in salivary lactate during exercise may benefit lactate utilising species, such as *R. mucilaginosa*, during metabolic production of NO₂⁻ (Rosier, Moya-Gonzalvez, *et al.*, 2020). In Study 3, the oral NO₂⁻ production capacity was tested when the participants were at rest, when salivary lactate levels are not elevated, which may have impacted on NO₂⁻ production (Rosier, Moya-Gonzalvez, *et al.*, 2020). No differences in NO₂⁻ production were detected when the trained and untrained participants were compared. Methodological differences could have resulted in the contrast in results with a previous study, which detected a significant association between oral NO₂⁻ production capacity and aerobic fitness immediately post-exercise, when salivary lactate levels were elevated (Thomas *et al.*, 2019).

Other studies suggest further ways in which a host's microbiome can contribute to exercise performance. For example, in the gut, *V. atypica*, a species known to contribute to oral NO₂⁻ production, has been found to increase in relative abundance post-marathon (Scheiman *et al.*, 2019). Subsequent inoculation of mice with a strain of this species improved exercise performance, with bacterial metabolism of lactate to propionate proposed as the main contributing mechanism (Scheiman *et al.*, 2019). While more data is undoubtedly needed, especially in the oral cavity, it is feasible that encouraging the growth of specific bacterial species could support exercise performance, as well as oral health.

This thesis provides little evidence in support of previous findings which suggest exercise training is associated with an increase in dental disease-associated bacteria (Minty *et al.*, 2018). While *A. parvulum*, which increased post-HIIT, is associated with caries on non-shedding tooth surfaces (Torlakovic *et al.*, 2012), the oral microbiome's roles in pathology are niche-specific (Li *et al.*, 2022). Therefore, it is feasible that *A. parvulum* is an innocuous resident of the tongue dorsum. No exercise training associated increases were observed in the relative abundance of periodontitis- or halitosis-associated species within the microbiome of the tongue dorsum and no significant differences were found in the composition of the supragingival plaque. The differences in the caries-associated microbiome seen by Minty *et al.*, (2018) may therefore be a result of lifestyle or behavioural differences specific to the sport of rugby or from pursuing a career in competitive sports.

Table 7-3: The group median and IQR of summed NO₂⁻ producing species. The values are displayed for each timepoint or group for studies 1, 2 and 3. Statistically significant differences between baseline and the post-treatment timepoints in Study are indicated using asterixis. No statistically significant differences were observed between the ‘trained’ and ‘untrained’ conditions in Studies 2 and 3. * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$, **** $p < 0.0001$

Study	Timepoint or Group	Sampling Site	Relative Abundance of NO ₂ ⁻ -Producing Bacteria (%)
1	Baseline	Subgingival Plaque	16.0 (12.9 - 19.7)
	Day-1	Subgingival Plaque	18.2 (9.6 - 24.7)****
	Day-7	Subgingival Plaque	16.9 (9.8 - 31.5)****
	Day-90	Subgingival Plaque	27.6 (16.9 - 38.5)****
2	Baseline	Tongue Dorsum	34.9 (26.3 - 49.7)
	Post-Training	Tongue Dorsum	46.2 (27.7 - 60.8)
	Post-Detraining	Tongue Dorsum	38.5 (21.0 - 42.4)
3	Trained	Tongue Dorsum	47.1 (30.2 - 54.8)
	Untrained	Tongue Dorsum	41.04 (28.4 - 54.0)
	Trained	Supragingival Plaque	32.9 (26.1 - 49.8)
	Untrained	Supragingival Plaque	35.3 (22.8 - 62.5)

7.7 Athletes and Their Support Team are Unaware of Available Guidance to Support the Maintenance of Athlete Oral Health

Previous studies suggest behaviours carried out by athletes, such as poor oral hygiene, poor engagement with routine dental check-ups and frequent sugar consumption, may impact on their oral health (Needleman *et al.*, 2016; Minty *et al.*, 2018; Gallagher *et al.*, 2019; Gallagher, Ashley and Needleman, 2020). Educational guidance has been developed which is specific to the competitive sports environment and is free to access from several sources including the Eastman Dental Institute (2017) and World Dental Federation, (2019a, 2019b, 2019c, 2019d). While effectively evaluating oral health improvement interventions is complex (Kidd *et al.*, 2020), the exploratory evidence gathered in Study 4 suggests that both athletes and their support teams are unaware of the existence of these supportive materials.

While the performance level of athletes was lower compared to previous studies (Needleman *et al.*, 2016; Gallagher *et al.*, 2019; Kragt *et al.*, 2019) many respondents had still experienced impacts of poor oral health on their performance and quality of life. In addition, some self-reported oral hygiene behaviours suggested room for improvement. However, while carbohydrate supplementation consumption was common, its usage appeared lower compared with some elite-level cohorts (Gallagher *et al.*, 2019). This may be partly responsible for the high prevalence of dental caries (Needleman *et al.*, 2016; Gallagher *et al.*, 2018; Minty *et al.*, 2018; Merle, Richter, *et al.*, 2022) and increased abundance of caries-associated bacteria observed in elite-level athletes by other studies (Minty *et al.*, 2018). While few coaches had considered the importance of athlete oral health, they felt they held responsibility for delivering nutrition advice for well-being and performance. Furthermore, some suggested they already delivered advice which would support oral health, including advising against the consumption of sports supplements where not directly indicated. These coaches might be amenable to accepting a role supporting athlete oral health. Some of the DHP respondents indicated they had previous experience caring for athletes and that these experiences directly informed their current practice. In addition, some suggested that while they aimed to provide tailored prevention to each patient, this could be improved if patients were upfront about what sports supplements they use and why. While there was interest in targeted CPD, the small number of patients involved in competitive sports led participants to acknowledge that they were unlikely to spend much time utilising these resources.

7.8 Significance and Future Directions

This thesis demonstrates that periodontal treatment and exercise training are viable interventions to modulate the enterosalivary NO_3^- - NO_2^- -NO pathway. In addition, a lack of awareness of methods for dental disease prevention in the competitive sports environment was found among athletes, coaches and DHPs, alongside a willingness to upskill to benefit athlete oral health.

Future studies should examine how modulating the NO_2^- -producing microbiome could be harnessed to support oral health and further investigate how dental disease prevention can be improved in the competitive sports environment. Possible directions for this future research are described in greater detail below.

7.8.1 Interventions to Increase Salivary NO₃⁻ and NO₂⁻ as an Adjunctive Therapy for Periodontitis

Previous studies show interventions which increase oral NO₃⁻ availability, also support the growth of the NO₂⁻-producing microbiome (Velmurugan *et al.*, 2016; Vanhatalo *et al.*, 2018; Burleigh *et al.*, 2019; Jockel-Schneider *et al.*, 2021; Rosier *et al.*, 2021) and reduce oral inflammation (Jockel-Schneider *et al.*, 2016, 2021). It is feasible that these effects could be combined with those of treatment in patients with periodontitis. An increase in the concentration of salivary NO₃⁻ and NO₂⁻ throughout healing would support the growth of NO₂⁻-producing bacteria. Additionally, levels of residual inflammation could be decreased, due to both microbiome changes and increased bioavailability of antimicrobial NO, granting clinical improvements beyond the levels seen with treatment alone. Future studies should consider combining dietary NO₃⁻ supplementation and/or exercise training interventions with professional mechanical plaque removal and improved oral hygiene to improve clinical treatment outcomes in periodontitis. The microbiome results and salivary NO₃⁻ and NO₂⁻ levels reported in Study 1 provide useful data which could be consulted to inform the design of these future studies.

7.8.2 Sources of Salivary NO Metabolites

In Studies 2 and 3, significant increases were seen in the concentration of NO metabolites in the saliva and in the relative abundance of specific NO₂⁻-producing species, apparently as a consequence of regular aerobic exercise training. These findings may contribute to the positive association between physical activity and dental health among the general population (Ferreria *et al.*, 2019; Sanchez *et al.*, 2020; Medapati and Pachava, 2022). Despite this, oral NO₂⁻ production capacity was not associated with the completion of regular exercise training in Study 3 and the source of the increased concentrations of NO metabolites in the saliva among active individuals remains unclear.

Future studies may wish to investigate the exact source of these changes. It may be hypothesised that the increase in salivary NO₃⁻ and NO₂⁻ is a consequence of elevated endogenous NOS levels and increased systemic NO generation (Dyakova *et al.*, 2015), leading to an increase in NO₃⁻ secretion into the saliva. However, this is not fully supported by the data of Studies 2 and 3, where exercise was not associated with consistent changes in NO₃⁻ and NO₂⁻

levels in the plasma. Another possible explanation is that NO derived from bacteria which benefit from exercise may be oxidised to NO_2^- and then further to NO_3^- in the oral cavity (Rosier *et al.*, 2022).

As baseline salivary NO_3^- and NO_2^- levels and oral NO_2^- production capacity appear to be affected by multiple factors, which may all have implications for the efficacy of therapeutic interventions, further investigation of these factors is required among different populations.

7.8.3 Exercise-Induced Changes to the Oral Environment and Microbiome

The results of Studies 2 and 3 suggest oral bacteria capable of lactate metabolism during NO_2^- production may derive benefits from the completion of regular exercise training. Future studies should focus on the compositional and behavioural changes of the oral microbiome during or immediately after exercise, when environmental conditions are different compared to rest as the completion of more intensive exercise could have implications for the composition of the oral microbiome and further impact on NO bioavailability.

Encouraging the growth the NO_2^- -producing microbiome may prove especially beneficial for those who regularly use carbohydrate supplementation. Increasing salivary NO_3^- levels using dietary supplementation appears to have protective effects on salivary pH following the consumption of carbohydrate (Burleigh *et al.*, 2020; Rosier *et al.*, 2021). In addition, higher unsupplemented levels of salivary NO_3^- and greater oral NO_2^- -production capacity are associated with a decreased risk of dental caries (Doel *et al.*, 2004). Future studies should investigate whether other interventions that increase salivary NO metabolite levels and benefit the NO_2^- -producing microbiome-including the prompt and effective treatment of periodontal disease and interventions aimed at increasing an individual's activity levels-have protective effects against dental diseases exacerbated by the host's diet.

7.8.4 Effects of Different Exercise Training Modalities and Intensities on the Oral Microbiome

This thesis examines the oral microbiome among sedentary populations, individuals who meet, but do not exceed WHO recommendations for aerobic exercise, and individuals who carry out more than 6 hours per week of intensive, structured exercise training, but who are not elite-level athletes (McKay *et al.*, 2021). This means that full-length 16s rRNA sequencing of the

oral microbiome has not been carried out among ‘elite-level’ athletes, who have previously displayed disease-associated oral microbiome changes (Minty *et al.*, 2018). Future studies may wish to examine differences in the oral microbiome within different oral niches among elite-level athletes, comparing them to sedentary and moderately active populations.

To more decisively assess the impact of long-term aerobic exercise, a deliberate effort was made to recruit endurance trained athletes for Study 3. Consequently, team and explosive power sports were underrepresented throughout this thesis. Previous studies suggest differing levels of dental disease prevalence among athletes involved in team sports compared to individual sports (Gallagher *et al.*, 2018; de la Parte *et al.*, 2021). It is plausible that the training or behavioural differences influence the oral microenvironment and microbiota. Further investigation could better direct the provision of targeted preventative care to reduce the growth of oral pathogens and the diseases they cause.

7.8.5 Educating the Athlete and Their Support Team

Current guidance aimed at athletes and their support teams has been adapted by experts in the field from evidence-based guidance aimed at preventing dental disease in the general population (Eastman Dental Institute, 2017; World Dental Federation, 2019a, 2019b, 2019c, 2019d). The toolkit provided by the Eastman Dental Institute clearly demonstrates its links to evidence-based practice. However, when approached for comment, the World Dental Federation were unable to provide complete reference lists. Future guidance should incorporate new data regarding sports specific prevention as it becomes available and should be clear which sources have been used.

As only 2 DHPs were aware that any guidance existed regarding the prevention of dental disease in the competitive sports environment future groups may wish to consider how best to disseminate guidance. These groups should carefully consider the information sources consulted by the respondents of Study 4, to maximise the uptake of targeted educational interventions.

The coach respondents of Study 4 indicated they had a role in delivering advice to promote wellbeing and sports performance. Emerging evidence shows dental disease has a negative impact on both of these areas among UK-based athletes (Needleman *et al.*, 2016; Gallagher *et*

al., 2018). With sufficient support, these coaches may be prepared to deliver simple advice to promote athlete oral health to minimise the potential harmful effects of dental disease to the athletes in their care.

The DHP respondents indicated they had a responsibility to promote dental health amongst all patients in their care. However, they seemed less sure of how best to do this among athletes of a higher performance level and were unclear of the contents of some carbohydrate supplement products. Encouraging athletes to be frank with the dental team regarding the contents of any sports supplements they use may improve the quality of the preventative advice they receive and may prompt the dental team to treat some individuals as being at an increased risk of dental disease.

All three groups spoke of the importance of sports nutritionists, either as a well-informed, reliable source of information or as an individual whom respondents would feel reluctant to contradict. The questionnaire used in Study 4 could be adapted to collect information to inform any future guidance created to specifically target sports nutritionists. This would help to ensure that an athlete's dental health is considered when planning nutrition for sports performance.

It is important to highlight that although patient education plays a key role in fostering behavioural change, in isolation, it is insufficient to achieve lasting change (O'Malley *et al.*, 2016). To better support athletes, future interventions should adopt an evidence-based approach informed by behavioural change frameworks, such as the COM-B model utilized by Gallagher, Ashley, and Needleman (2020). This approach would not only ensure that athletes acquire the knowledge and manual skills necessary for maintaining good oral health behaviours but also encourage the development of social environments that prioritise oral health. Additionally, athlete-specific motivators, such as reducing missed training time and disrupted recovery and improved aesthetics could be leveraged to further enhance adherence to recommended practices (Gallagher, Ashley, and Needleman, 2020).

7.9 Strengths and Limitations

The studies carried out over the course of this thesis have many key strengths which should be highlighted. Of note, the collaboration with FISABIO in Valencia enabled high-fidelity

microbiome sequencing and subsequent analysis of the resulting microbiome datasets, while the equipment and expertise at the University of the West of Scotland allowed for accurate measurement of physiological NO_3^- and NO_2^- levels and of the aerobic fitness level of the participants of Study 3.

Sequencing of the 16S rRNA gene is the gold standard method to accurately assess the taxonomic composition of the microbiome (Starke, Pylro and Morais, 2021). Prior to this thesis, short-length Illumina Sequencing, relying mainly on amplification of the V3-V4 region of the 16S rRNA gene, had been used to quantify the NO_2^- -producing microbiome (Moran *et al.*, 2024) and a mixture of sequencing of the V2-V4 (Minty *et al.*, 2018) and V3-V4 regions (Kalabiska *et al.*, 2023) to examine the athlete oral microbiome. Illumina sequencing is cost-effective and efficient, especially when many samples must be sequenced, such as in Study 1 (Buetas *et al.*, 2024). The results are also broadly comparable with long-read sequencing, especially at the genus level (Buetas *et al.*, 2024). However, long-read sequencing enables a greater number of reads to be accurately assigned at the species level, an important consideration when only some members of a genus are implicated in pathology or NO_2^- production (Buetas *et al.*, 2024). As a result, the long-read Pac-Bio sequencing used in Studies 2 and 3 represents a significant methodological improvement compared to previous studies.

Correct handling of oral microbiome data requires specialist statistical methods. ANCOMBC-2 was used throughout this thesis, being the most appropriate data analysis method available for microbiome at this time. This addressed complications arising from the compositional nature of the data, accounted for differences in sequencing depth and microbial load, enabled correction for biases, accounted for the high number of zeros in the dataset and has improved sensitivity and specificity in detecting true differential abundances compared to previous methods (Lin and Peddada, 2020). However, bioinformatic analysis is a rapidly evolving field and it is likely that further improvements in the handling of microbiome data will arise in the future.

Despite improvements in technology, 16s rRNA sequencing is costly. This was especially true of the long-read Pac-Bio sequencing used in Studies 2 and 3 (Buetas *et al.*, 2024). In both studies, a larger sample size would have increased statistical power and increased certainty that the observed results were due to true biological differences. However, a combination of costs and the requirement for the completion of an intensive HIIT intervention precluded the

recruitment of a larger number of participants in Study 2. When designing Study 3, a decision was made to analyse the tongue dorsum and supragingival microbiota to provide pilot data relevant to both oral NO_2^- production and dental disease, again resulting in the recruitment of only 10 participants to each group.

Diet impacts on oral microbiome composition (Angarita-Díaz *et al.*, 2022; Moran *et al.*, 2024) and on physiological levels of NO_3^- and NO_2^- (Burleigh *et al.*, 2018; Avoort *et al.*, 2020). During Study 2 the participants' diet was recorded and replicated prior to sample collection, to reduce confounding. Study 3 examined 2 groups who followed different lifestyles and no restrictions in habitual diet were placed upon the participants to avoid microbiome shifts. Previous studies suggest that athlete groups habitually consume more dietary NO_3^- , albeit with high levels of inter-individual variation, similar to findings in the general population (Jonvik *et al.*, 2017). Despite this, weekly NO_3^- consumption was not found to differ between groups in Study 3. The diet diaries used to calculate this measurement relied on accurate recording of food intake by participants, and were likely to have had some inaccuracies (Bailey, 2021) and NO_3^- consumption on the days leading up to sample collection may have impacted on both physiological measurements of NO_3^- and NO_2^- and on the oral microbiome. As changes in the oral microbiome and oral microenvironment were not primary study outcomes for Study 1 and to ensure the participants were comfortable and healthy for the duration of each treatment appointment, no dietary controls were in place. This could have altered salivary NO_3^- and NO_2^- levels in a small number of participants. In the future, studies should carefully consider the dietary controls put in place to avoid confounding while maintaining participant wellbeing. In addition, other methods of measuring dietary NO_3^- consumption should be considered to enable participant compliance.

Careful consideration was paid during recruitment to ensure that differences seen within the oral microbiome resulted from periodontal treatment and exercise training. However, while no participant reported a diagnosis of any other medical or dental condition, the recruitment of a cohort of wholly normotensive adults with untreated periodontitis proved challenging for Study 1. In addition, while participants in Studies 2 and 3 reported they were dentally healthy, the presence of asymptomatic disease was a possibility. Future studies should include a full clinical and radiographic examination of all participants, collecting accurate and comprehensive information on their dental disease status (Gallagher, Ashley and Needleman, 2023). Finally, finding participants who did not take part in regular exercise training but were willing to carry

out either a behavioural change or maximal exercise test was a challenge during recruitment for Studies 2 and 3 and future studies should anticipate these difficulties when planning to recruit participants. Following feedback from study participants and from individuals who declined to participate, we would recommend maximal exercise testing using a cycle ergometer instead of a treadmill to reduce participant trepidation. We would also suggest liaising with local sports facilities to offer testing to individuals who are about to commence exercise programmes, with the offer of a second maximal exercise test once their exercise programme is complete. For sports science studies investigating oral health, the offer of comprehensive dental health screening, ideally with the option of sending participants who are not registered with a dentist to an outreach centre or similar for a single course of treatment, would both minimise the risk of confounding and encourage participation.

Previous studies investigating participant knowledge of dental disease prevention used questionnaires which tested knowledge of dental disease prevention out with the competitive sports environment (Richards, Filippini and Roberts-Burt, 2014; Gallagher, Ashley and Needleman, 2020). While the questionnaire used in Study 4 has not been robustly tested for validity and reliability, the questions used were formulated to be specific to the competitive sports environment as the dietary needs and behaviours of athletes, may differ from the untrained population. In addition, the participants recruited are unlikely to be representative of any of the three study groups. The coaches and athletes were primarily involved in endurance sports, reflecting the network of the researcher. It is also feasible that the subject matter of the questionnaire attracted athletes who had previously experienced performance impacts as a result of dental disease, or coaches who felt strongly about their role in maintaining athlete health. Similarly, a high proportion of the DHPs had an interest in sports, either as a participant or as a coach, and many worked in a teaching hospital, where high importance is placed on evidence-based prevention. This may mean the sample are more able to provide high-quality, individualised preventative advice compared to DHPs who feel their time is more limited and more likely to be spent carrying out clinical treatment. Furthermore, the samples were non-ethnically diverse and, as a result, the generalisability of the results should be interpreted with caution. Future studies should consider actively seeking out participants involved in team sports or sports with a greater anaerobic component, to explore reasons for differing levels of dental disease risk (de la Parte., *et al.*, 2021). Efforts should also be made to collect more data, and to further develop the skills of GDPs in the delivery of oral health advice to athletes, as the

individuals are likely to deliver the majority of preventative care, especially at the sub-elite level.

The prevention of non-communicable diseases are covered by an IOC consensus statement (Matheson, *et al.*, 2013). This encourages the development of simple interventions, with an emphasis on behavioural change by individual athletes, alongside engagement and participation from the rest of the athlete support network. A second consensus statement informed by a systematic review of the relevant literature, followed by discussion by a panel of experts suggests that this approach would work well in reducing dental disease risk among athletes (Needleman *et al.*, 2014). However, as highlighted by some of the responses to Study 4, engaging all the relevant stakeholders in this process will be a practical challenge. Many groups have a responsibility for athlete health and well-being, and oral health undoubtedly contributes (World Health Organisation, 2021). While DHPs can consult evidence-based guidance, which they can adapt to better support their patients (Public Health England, 2021), it is unclear where the responsibility for encouraging engagement and upskilling the rest of the athlete support network lies. It is not feasible that the expertise of the dental team regarding preventative care could be replaced. However, some sports' governing bodies already provide educational support relating to general health, performance nutrition, or the prevention of conditions like RED-S (Stodter and Cushion, 2019). These offer an opportunity for the rapid delivery of simple oral health advice, which could be effectively tailored to the audience and course content. For example, a workshop advising on how to effectively utilise carbohydrate supplementation to support performance during an endurance event could also include a few minutes emphasising the importance of food first nutrition and advising athletes to rinse with water to dilute acidic and cariogenic substances (Needleman *et al.*, 2018). This could target all three components of the COM-B model, encouraging more effective behavioural change among athletes.

Finally, with the exception of Study 1, which was registered as part of the initial NHS ethics approval process, none of the protocols were registered in an online database of clinical research studies. In hindsight, this should also have been done for Studies 2 to 4, as it would have enhanced transparency and promoted accountability by providing a publicly accessible record of the objectives, methods, and planned analyses of all conducted research. This would make it clear to the reader that the results were not reported selectively. Attempts were made to retrospectively register the final three studies in a suitable database; however, this was not

possible due to a combination of prohibitive costs and administrative challenges. Moving forward, as part of good research practice, all research study protocols should be registered during the ethical approval process and prior to participant recruitment.

7.10 Conclusion

This thesis presents significant novel findings suggesting multiple interventions could be used to increase NO_3^- and NO_2^- levels, both local to the oral cavity and at other systemic sites. In addition, we demonstrate that both periodontal treatment and exercise training alter the NO_2^- -producing microbiome, appearing to benefit key NO_2^- -producing species. The importance of bacterial NO_2^- -production in dental health is starting to be understood and it appears feasible that these changes could contribute to homeostasis of the oral microenvironment and support eubiosis.

Chapter 3 shows that successful treatment of periodontitis increases the relative abundance of NO_2^- -producing bacteria in the subgingival plaque, with these species negatively associated with disease-associated species at all investigated timepoints. A summary of the apparent impacts of periodontal treatment on the oral microenvironment and microbiome and the implications of successful treatment of periodontitis on oral NO_2^- -production is shown in Figure 7-1.

Changes to the subgingival environment following treatment

Changes to the subgingival microbiome following treatment

Future directions for the manipulation of the enterosalivary NO_3^- - NO_2^- - NO pathway in the treatment of periodontitis

Figure 7-1: Summary of the effects of periodontal treatment on the oral environment and microbiome in patients with periodontitis and discussion of possible future directions for research aiming to manipulate oral NO_2^- production to improve clinical treatment outcomes. While periodontal treatment alters the oral microenvironment, salivary NO_3^- and NO_2^- levels remained unchanged. Despite this, the relative abundance of NO_2^- -producing increased and the relative abundance of periodontitis-associated bacteria immediately decreased post-treatment. These changes persisted once periodontal healing was complete. These groups of bacteria have a strong negative correlation within the subgingival plaque, which may suggest inhibition of the disease-associated microbiome when the relative abundance of NO_2^- -producing bacteria is increased. Finally, periodontal treatment restores the ability of the oral microbiome to generate NO_2^- , with implications for NO bioavailability in the oral cavity and elsewhere in the body. These findings may inform future periodontal research. Interventions which increase NO metabolite availability in the saliva, such as dietary supplementation and exercise training may further increase the relative abundance of key NO_2^- -producing bacteria, inhibit the growth of periodontitis-associated species and reduce residual gingival inflammation, improving treatment outcomes. *Data from Rosier et al., 2024. Figure created in Biorender.com

Chapter 4 provided the first evidence that specific NO_2^- -producing bacteria increase on the dorsal surface of the tongue following consistent HIIT, alongside evidence of alterations to the storage of NO metabolites at multiple sites. Chapter 5 demonstrated that long-term training for competitive sports could alter the composition of the bacterial community of the tongue and increase in the relative abundance of 2 species of bacteria, including effective NO_2^- -producing species *R. mucilaginosa*. Finally, Chapter 6 showed that, while the athlete support team prioritise athlete health and well-being, oral health may be overlooked, with a lack of confidence among coaches and DHPs in how best to prevent dental disease in the competitive sports environment. Figure 7-2 summarises the results of these 3 chapters and shows the apparent effects of regular aerobic exercise training on the oral cavity.

Figure 7-2: Summary of the effects of exercise training on the individual and their oral cavity. Exercise training appears to increase NO_3^- and NO_2^- levels in the saliva. These changes are accompanied by changes to the microbiome of the tongue dorsum, with apparent increases in the relative abundance of NO_2^- -producing species. While more data is needed, these changes appear more profound when the volume of exercise training is greater. Finally, individuals involved in competitive sports report behaviours which could negatively impact oral health. *Inferred from previous data (Santos et al., 2006; Oliveira et al., 2015; Thomas et al., 2019).^{2,3,4} Data taken from Studies 2-4. Figure created in Biorender.com

This thesis demonstrates that periodontal treatment and exercise training impact the oral microenvironment and the composition and behaviour of the oral microbiome. These changes

appear especially relevant to bacteria with a role in oral NO_2^- production. In addition to the physiological changes which accompany consistent intensive exercise training, investigation of some behavioural changes likely to impact the oral microbiome are also explored, providing possible avenues for the direction of preventative advice and care, ensuring the development of an oral microbiome which will not be detrimental to host health.

8. References

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9. Appendices

9.1 Appendix 1 Food Diary

Dates of Nutritional Monitoring:

Instructions:

- Please fill out this food diary, including all food and drink consumed throughout the day, including at mealtimes and as snacks.
- Record the estimated weight of each food type (grams) and volume (mls).
- Please breakdown each food consumed by ingredient. For example, if you have a sandwich, record how many slices of bread and what sort of filling. If you have a salad, please include what type of lettuce etc was included.
- If you take any supplements in addition to your meals, please include these in the food diary.
- Please note the approximate time every time you eat or drink and the times you carry out oral hygiene (brushing and/or flossing your teeth and/or using mouthwash)

Day 1

Breakfast:

Lunch:

Dinner:

Snacks:

Times oral hygiene carried out:

Day 2

Breakfast:

Lunch:

Dinner:

Snacks:

Times oral hygiene carried out:

Day 3

Breakfast:

Lunch:

Dinner:

Snacks:

Times oral hygiene carried out:

Day 4

Breakfast:

Lunch:

Dinner:

Snacks:

Times oral hygiene carried out:

Day 5

Breakfast:
Lunch:
Dinner:
Snacks:
Times oral hygiene carried out:

Day 6

Breakfast:
Lunch:
Dinner:
Snacks:
Times oral hygiene carried out:

Day 7

Breakfast:
Lunch:
Dinner:
Snacks:
Times oral hygiene carried out:

9.2 Appendix 2 Training Diary

Please write down details of all exercise activity you carry out during your week. This should include very light activity such as walking to the supermarket, as well as formal training sessions you carry out alone or as part of a group to train for your sport.

Day	Description of activity	Duration	Rated perceived exertion (1-10)
Monday			
Tuesday			
Wednesday			
Thursday			
Friday			
Saturday			
Sunday			

Rated perceived exertion (1-10)

The Rated Perceived Exertion Scale

The rated perceived exertion scale is used to determine how much intensity you felt while carrying out a physical activity, such as a training session. It is a measurement of how easy or difficult you found the activity. Scale adapted from (Borg, 1982).

Borg, G. A. (1982) 'Psychophysical bases of perceived exertion', *Med Sci Sports Exerc*, 14(5), pp. 377-81.

Score	Level of perceived exertion
0	None
0.5	Very, very slight
1	Very slight
2	Slight
3	Moderate
4	Somewhat severe
5	Severe
6	
7	Very severe
8	
9	Very, very severe
10	Maximal

9.3 Appendix 3 Study 4 Questionnaire

The complete questionnaire used in Study 4 can be accessed on Dropbox using this [link](#).